

Curtin University

Curtin HIVE

Five-Year Report - July 2018 to June 2023.

Make tomorrow better.

[HIVE.curtin.edu.au](https://hive.curtin.edu.au)

Citation:

Andrew Woods, Daniel Adams, Carley Tillett, Wesley Lamont (2023) "Curtin HIVE Five-Year Report - July 2018 to June 2023", Annual Report, Curtin University, Perth,

Curtin HIVE Five-Year Report

Authors: Andrew Woods, Daniel Adams, Carley Tillett, Wesley Lamont

Curtin University

Copyright 2023

Front Cover Image:

Goal Striving Bicycle VR project with (L-R) psychology honours students Merrill Lombard and Sarah Paduano, and supervisor Dr Hugh Ridell.

Photo Credit: Frances Andrijich

Rear Cover Image:

Australian Prime Minister Anthony Albanese visits Curtin University and the HIVE on 21 October 2022.

(Front L-R) Professor Phil Bland, Prime Minister Anthony Albanese, Professor Chris Moran, and Zaneta Mascarenhas, Member for Swan.

Photo Credit: Ezra Alcantra

Executive Summary and Introduction

The HIVE was launched in November 2013 to support, encourage and enable the use of visualisation technologies in research projects across the University. After ten years of operation, the HIVE has actively engaged with many hundreds of Curtin staff, supported nearly a hundred student projects, and showcased Curtin's visualisation related research activities to many thousands of visitors.

In the last five years the HIVE has been cited in or supported \$49M worth of grant applications (including \$8.7M of ARC grants) of which \$30M worth of grants have been successful (including \$2.3M of ARC grants) (see Section 2.7 "Grants and Grant Applications" and Appendix B).

HIVE related media coverage has been extensive. In this reporting period HIVE related media coverage has had an estimated Advertising Sales Revenue (ASR) of \$477,000 and a cumulative audience of over 3.1 million (see Section 3.1 "Media Coverage").

The number of academic publications that have been supported by the HIVE has grown substantially. During the period of this report there have been a total of 87 publications comprising 5 books, 9 book chapters, 49 journal articles, 20 conference papers, 3 general articles, and 1 PhD Thesis (see Section 2.8 "Publications"). Additionally, there have been 37 technical reports citing the HIVE or supported by the HIVE (see Section 2.10 "Technical Reports"). Academic publications citing or supported by the HIVE have accumulated a total of 1325 citations since 2018 (see Section 2.10 "Citations").

The HIVE has developed and facilitated many important collaborative opportunities – including with the Western Australian Museum, State Library of Western Australia, and many more (see Section 6.2 "Key External Collaborators").

The HIVE promotes three main aspects of visualisation research projects – Insight, Communication and Showcasing - using visualisation to gain further **insight** from research data, using visualisation to **communicate** ideas with colleagues and students, and using visualisation to **showcase** results to help engage with industry and community. Since opening, the HIVE has supported or approved over 400 visualisation research projects. (see Appendix B for full list).

The largest project the HIVE has supported to date is the *Sydney-Kormoran* Project, which has involved staff from the Faculty of Humanities and the Faculty of Science and Engineering. The project relates to the 3D reconstruction of the wreck sites of the Australian vessel HMAS *Sydney II* and the German raider HSK *Kormoran* which are located off the Western Australian coast. This project has a very high media profile, high research output opportunity, demonstrated growth potential with further spin-off projects, has impressive visuals which amply illustrate the advanced and innovative nature of the project and the HIVE facility, and a high level of public exposure through museum exhibitions. This work is currently supported by an ARC Linkage Project "*Photogrammetric Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences*" (LP180100284).

The highest level of research engagement has been with staff from the Faculty of Health Sciences, closely followed by the Faculty of Humanities and the Faculty of Science and Engineering. Some large projects have run with the Faculty of Business and Law, but there remains some untapped potential for more projects in that area. It is interesting to note that some projects are fast movers, but many do have a slow development time and a long tail.

Faculty of Business and Law

During this reporting period the HIVE has supported projects with the following FBL staff: Michael Volgger, Katharina Wolf, S Zuang Nau, Peter Dell, Joyce Khuu, Felix Chan, Brian von Konsky, Rohini Balapumi, Tomayess Issa, Billy Sung, Stephanie Thomas, and Kirsten Holmes. The HIVE has hosted a complex immersive indigenous experience for students from the School of Marketing and Management unit "ISYS5009 Societal Impact of Tech Innovation" in semester one and two since April 2021 culminating in nearly 100 students attending the semester one, 2023 sessions. 2016 HIVE summer internship student Shree Lakshmi who was supervised by Fran Ackermann on the project "Assessing Different Visualisation Techniques (for risk network visualisation)" commenced a PhD with Fran in 2019 in collaboration with the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre.

Faculty of Health Sciences

During this reporting period the HIVE has supported projects with the following Health Sciences staff: Marina Ciccarelli, Susan Morris, Lisa Tee, Ricardo Mancera, Rima Caccetta, Zhonghua Sun, Peter Buzzacott, Kylie Hill, Flavia Di Pietro, Daniel Rudaizky, Hugh Riddell, Lyn Mueleners, Stephanie Parkinson, Sharon Keesing, Simone Pettigrew, Nikos Ntoumanis, Morgan Titmus, Gary Whittaker, Catherine Boisvert, Ryu Takechi, Ben Mullins, Sarah Sterne, Shirley Jansen, and Leon Straker. The HIVE Dome display was used in a successful PhD completion *"The Postural Control System in Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Insights from Exploring the Effects of Visual Information on Postural Control"* by Dr Yi Huey Lim, supervised by Dr Susan Morris. There are a wide range of visualisation projects in the health sciences which span across the three HIVE focus areas of VR/AR, Volume Visualisation, and photogrammetry. Many HIVE supported projects in the health sciences are cross-disciplinary, within and across faculties.

Faculty of Humanities

During this reporting period the HIVE has supported projects with the following Humanities staff: Reena Tiwari, Mihye Won, Kath Dooley, Chamila Subasinghe Arachchilage Don, Kit Messham-Muir, Rebecca Walker, Stuart Bender, Natalie Pretorius, Bri McKenzie, Antonio Traverso, Artur Lugmayr, Renee Parnell, Erik Champion, Crystal Abadin, Eleanor Sandry, Jo Li Tay, Jonathan Pillai, Parisa Izadpanahi, and Jo Jones. The HIVE has supported a range of highly productive projects including MissionsConnect (Prof Reena Tiwari), Chemistry Education in VR ARC Discovery Project (A/Prof Mihye Won), and more. The Historical Panoramas project which commenced as an SLWA supported HIVE internship project in 2015 led to the award-winning Museum exhibition "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" at the WA Maritime Museum. HIVE supported projects in the Humanities have received 10 separate public awards (see Section 2.12 "Awards").

Faculty of Science and Engineering

During this reporting period the HIVE has supported projects with the following Science and Engineering staff: Gretchen Benedix, Chris Elders, David McMeekin, Katarina Miljkovic, Carla de Tomas, Nigel Marks, Martin Towner, Petra Helmholtz, David Belton, Luc Doucet, Siavash Khaksar, Iain Murray, Anthony Lagain, Hanieh Bakhshayesh, Will Rickard, Tele Tan, Susannah Soon, Andrew Rohl, Hannes Hermann, Charlie Ironside, Phil Bland, Renee Sayers, Catherine Boisvert, Dom Wolff-Boenisch, Luke Daly, Sonia Ferns, Lucy Forman, Nik Timms, Aaron Cavosie, John Morgan, Iain Parnum, and Natasha Hurley-Walker. The HIVE has supported a wide range high level visits for the Curtin Spare Science and Technology Centre – for example Deputy Premier Roger Cook, US Ambassador to Australia Caroline Kennedy, WA Governor Kim Beasley, and NASA Scientist Henry Troop – which are amply illustrated by a wide range of space related HIVE supported visualisation projects on screens around the HIVE.

Central (including ROC, CTL, International, Corporate Services, and the VC's office)

The HIVE has hosted numerous high-profile high-level visits for the University including the Australian Prime Minister Anthony Albanese, numerous state and federal politicians, the Ambassador to The Netherlands Marion Derckx, Kerry Stokes, and many more (see also Section 5 "VIP Visitors"). The HIVE is an often chosen visit location because it allows visitors to quickly experience a wide range of dynamic and engaging research projects. The high media profile and innovative nature of the HIVE benefits the whole of Curtin to exemplify the University as a future-focused leading university. ROC staff often host visiting industry representatives to the HIVE including Navy Innovation Centre, Nuclear Submarines Task Force, US Navy, Office of Naval Research, Defence Science and Technology Group, Chief of Navy, Australian Signals Directorate, the Chief Defence Scientist, and many more. The HIVE hosts the monthly Welcome to Curtin meetings which expose new staff to the HIVE. The HIVE has been buzzing with activity across the five years of this report and is demonstrating significant and growing impact across the University. (pardon the necessary pun)

Interestingly and coincidentally, in this year that the Curtin HIVE is marking its 10th year of operation, the Electronic Visualization Laboratory (EVL) at the University of Illinois Chicago (UIC) is celebrating its 50th year of operation*. The EVL and its staff have had a major worldwide impact on visualisation technologies, including development of the CAVE and CAVE 2 immersive displays which have inspired the development of similar systems in visualisation facilities around the world, including the HIVE. The EVL also provided digital visualisations for the first Star Wars film. The EVL serves as a very good inspiration for the continued success of the Curtin HIVE. Many Universities around the world have a visualisation facility and the HIVE stands tall amongst them. In Australia the HIVE is arguably either the top 1 or 2 University visualisation facility.

* Andrew E. Johnson, Luc Renambot, G. Elisabeta Marai, Daria Tsoupikova, Michael E. Papka, Lance Long, Dana Plepys, Jonas Talandis, Maxine D. Brown, Jason Leigh, Daniel J. Sandin, Thomas A. DeFanti; "Electronic Visualization Laboratory's 50th Anniversary Retrospective: Look to the Future, Build on the Past". PRESENCE: Virtual and Augmented Reality 2024; 33 77–127. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/pres_a_00421

Table of Contents

Executive Summary and Introduction	3
1 About the HIVE	8
1.1 Vision	8
1.2 Mission	9
1.3 Governance	9
1.4 Governance - Advisory Board	9
1.5 Governance - Operational Committee	9
1.6 Strategic Plan 2019-2023	10
2 Research and Innovation	13
2.1 Highlighted Projects	13
2.2 Highlighted Student Projects	16
2.3 Highlighted Projects in HIVE Focus Areas	21
2.4 HIVE Focus Area: Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction	21
2.5 HIVE Focus Area: Volume Visualisation	24
2.6 HIVE Focus Area: Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality	25
2.7 Grants and Grant Applications	27
2.8 Publications	27
2.9 Theses	34
2.10 Technical Reports	34
2.11 Citations	36
2.12 Awards	37
3 Engagement and Impact	40
3.1 Media Coverage	40
3.2 Conference Presentations	53
3.3 VIP Visitors	55
3.4 HIVE Public Events	57
3.5 Showcasing	59
3.6 Utilisation Statistics	61
3.7 Social Media	63

3.8	YouTube Statistics:	64
3.9	Sketchfab Statistics	65
3.10	Exhibitions.....	66
3.11	Expos and External Events.....	68
3.12	Feedback.....	69
4	Learning and Student Experience	80
4.1	HIVE Summer Internships.....	80
4.2	HIVE Internships leading to ongoing Research Projects.....	99
4.3	Visualisation in Curtin Teaching Units.....	101
5	Research Infrastructure	104
5.1	Facility	104
5.2	Recent and Future AV Upgrades.....	105
5.3	Staff.....	106
5.4	Technology Partnerships.....	107
6	Sustainable Future	109
6.1	Wider Deployment of HIVE Visualisation Technologies	109
6.2	Key External Collaborations.....	109
7	References	112
8	Appendices	120

1 About the HIVE

The Curtin HIVE (Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch) is an advanced visualisation facility launched on 27 November 2013 to serve the growing demands of researchers for visualisation capabilities in Western Australia. The HIVE is a University-wide facility servicing academic staff and research projects across all faculties. The HIVE operationally managed through the Faculty of Humanities.

The HIVE is both a physical facility and also a small team of staff that run and maintain the facility, support University staff and students to use the facility, and develop visualisations that support research activity and use the HIVE systems.

The HIVE is fitted with five large-scale visualisation systems:

- The Tiled display
- The Cylinder display
- The Wedge display
- The Hologram Table, and
- The Dome display

Each of these systems provide unique and distinct capabilities that allow a range of visualisation options. Different visualisation projects make use of the displays in various ways, and this varies considerably from one project to another. Additional information is provided in Section 5.1 Facility.

In addition to the large-scale displays, the HIVE has a wide selection of Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality headsets, as well as other portable displays. Content developed at the HIVE is designed to work across a wide range of devices to maximise audience and impact – from the HIVE to researcher's office and laboratories, and to the field. The HIVE also has a wide range of technical equipment which facilitates the development of immersive content, including ultra-high-resolution, 360°, 180° and 3D cameras.

Projects developed at the HIVE serve as exemplars for future work - inspiring other researchers and industry to use similar capabilities in their own areas of expertise.

Visualisation projects regularly provide benefit for the discipline area they are applied, but additionally, visualisations are often highly accessible to a broader audience and hence lend themselves well to public outreach, further expanding the impact of Curtin research projects.

1.1 Vision

To establish Curtin regionally and nationally as a key player in research and creative production innovation through data visualisation, virtualisation and simulation technology applications.

1.2 Mission

The role of the Curtin HIVE is to produce research innovation. It is designed to leverage the power of data visualisation and:

- create new knowledge from the enrichment of research data;
- enable better and more efficient training environments;
- facilitate new modes of creative expression.

1.3 Governance

An Advisory Board guides the development of the HIVE's strategic and business plans, review performance and assists with building the profile of the facility's visualisation, virtualisation and simulation capabilities. A Technical Manager, reporting to the Dean, Humanities Research and Graduate Studies, is responsible for Curtin HIVE's day to day operations. An Operational Committee oversees the implementation of the HIVE's strategic and operational objectives and provide guidance and direction to the Technical Manager.

1.4 Governance - Advisory Board

An Advisory Board comprising acknowledged experts from academia and industry guides the development and review of strategic and business plans, to raise awareness of the HIVE and promote technology transfers in the area of visualisation, virtualisation and simulation.

1.5 Governance - Operational Committee

As an advisory committee to the Humanities Dean, Research and Graduate Studies, the role of the HIVE Operational Committee is to advise on operational matters pertaining to the management of the HIVE. This advice extends to operational strategies, priorities and initiatives, as well as innovation in the HIVE's operations that contribute to the University's research, learning and creative production objectives, and external engagement with industry and the community.

1.6 Strategic Plan 2019-2023

The HIVE 'Plan on a Page' (2019-2023) was developed in 2018 to provide a guiding strategy for the operations of the HIVE.

HIVE Strategic Priority Areas 2019-2023:

Research and Innovation

1. Support, encourage and enable the use of visualisation technologies in research projects across the University. (HEADLINE AIM)
2. Encourage research academics to progress supported projects to the next stage
3. Enable research training of undergraduate and postgraduate research project students
4. Grow demand-driven research revenue by strengthening existing relationships and building new partnerships, with a clear pipeline of new funding
5. Develop and grow capability in key visualisation capability areas and deploy into new projects and new partnerships

Engagement and Impact

1. Showcase the facility and multi-disciplinary visualisation research project examples that highlight Curtin Research & Innovation to visitors and VIPs
2. Run a selection of engagement activities targeting both internal and external groups
3. Host technical presentations, workshops, conferences and events which communicate and promote visualisation techniques and technologies
4. Encourage connections between research academics and industry
5. Strengthen the "Curtinnovation" brand
6. Develop a high-quality online experience reflecting the HIVE capability and projects
7. Support media exposure of projects through media shoots in the HIVE and delivery of visualisations
8. Assist with the growth of philanthropic support

Research Infrastructure

1. Maintain a high-technology and up-to-date visualisation facility that ensures support of high-quality research
2. Develop software tools and libraries which support projects and have code re-use capability
3. Maintain a team proficient in visualisation project development and with project showcasing capability
4. Foster staff development and autonomy
5. Maintain a client focused attitude which supports use of and engagement with the facility
6. Seek grant funding to refresh the facility and duplicate key visualisation systems (e.g. HIVE Cylinder) at key partner locations
7. Work with technology partners to identify technology co-development opportunities using new and emerging technologies
8. Support a Special Interest Group in Visualisation Research

Learning and Student Experience

1. Offer the successful HIVE summer internship scheme as a leading undergraduate research training opportunity, researcher engagement technique and project delivery mechanism
2. Encourage the inclusion of visualisation technologies and HIVE visits in undergraduate and postgraduate courses/units, and student projects (undergraduate and postgraduate)
3. Support the inclusion of visualisation skills and topics in undergraduate and postgraduate degrees, executive education, stackable offerings and microcredentials
4. Support school visits aligned with key university events such as Open Day
5. Deliver a distinctive Curtin experience

Sustainable Future

1. Grow commercial income
2. Encourage grant applicants to include funds for research assistance that can be based at the HIVE
3. Explore how visualisation technologies can be used to promote Curtin capabilities and campuses globally and also be used for recruitment
4. Explore ways that key visualisation facilities and technologies can be deployed more widely across Curtin's campuses
5. Build collaborations with industry, technology companies, and Curtin research institutes

This report presents the HIVE's major achievements for the 5 years July 2018 to June 2023. The report is organised into same five sections that are used in the Plan on a Page: "Research and Innovation", "Engagement and Impact", "Learning and Student Experience", "Research Infrastructure" and "Sustainable Future".

Research and Innovation

Support and encourage use of visualisation technologies

"The HIVE is a jewel at Curtin and you oversee its success with style."
Professor Chris Moran, Deputy Vice-Chancellor of Research, May 2023.

2 Research and Innovation

The primary role of the HIVE is to support the use of visualisation technologies in research projects across the University. Visualisation technologies are riding an incredible wave of innovation currently and the HIVE has been very successful in supporting Curtin academic staff and students to help their projects ride this wave. Successful projects create publications, grant applications, strong collaborations, and in turn spawn new research projects. This section highlights a selection of the wide range of visualisation research projects supported over the period of this report.

2.1 Highlighted Projects

MissionsConnect – Cultural healing through Virtual reality: stolen Generation survivors and Mission sites

Professor Reena Tiwari (School of Design and the Built Environment, Faculty of Humanities), et al – in cooperation with Bringing Them Home WA

The MissionsConnect project develops virtual reality recreations of former aboriginal mission sites for the purposes of truth telling and healing. The MissionsConnect team have developed VR simulations of several sites including the Wandering Aboriginal Mission in the South West of WA, and the Mogumber Aboriginal Mission in Moore River region. The project has been supported by grants from BHP, LotteryWest and the Bringing Them Home Foundation. The project also produced an exhibition – "Limn 'At the fence' with Stolen Generations Survivors" – at the State Library of Western Australia, and Building 418 Curtin University.

The HIVE has provided guidance and support to this project since its early incarnations visualising point-clouds of a mission site captured using a laser scanner. The project makes very good use of all the visualisation displays in the HIVE, both as a research space exploring the experiences of survivors, through to showcasing the project to various groups and individuals.

Chemistry Education VR project

A/Prof Mihye Won, David Treagust (School of Education, Faculty of Humanities), Dewi Ungu, Henry Matovu, Bruno Hernandez (PhD students), et al.

This project is exploring the use VR technologies to allow chemistry students visualise the molecular world to help them understand complex chemical processes which can be hard to understand using conventional learning approaches. "VR gives a superior sense of what is happening in the molecular world – you can zoom in and out, and move around in an intuitive way. It makes it much easier to see molecular structures and key parts of a reaction, which is not done as well via other modes" (A/Prof Won).

The HIVE supported the first iteration of this project through a HIVE Summer Internship Project (Adam Mathewson, 2017?). Subsequently, the School of Education supported the further development of the

simulation through to a small user study with first-year chemistry students conducted in the HIVE. The next major step was a successful ARC Discovery Project "Using Immersive Virtual Reality to Enhance Students' Science Visualisation" (DP190100160) led by A/Professor Won which is currently in progress with two PhD students (Dewi Ungu and Henry Matovu – pictured above) deeply involved. A new PhD student (Bruno Hernandez) has also just started on the project.

VR for Spinal Cord Injury Rehabilitation

A/Prof Marina Cicarelli, Dr Sue Morris (School of Allied Health, Faculty of Health Sciences), with Gary Barnes and Greg Hewitt.

This project explores the use of VR technologies for rehabilitation purposes with subjects who have an incomplete spinal cord injury. The HIVE developed a VR cooking simulation in Unity for use with a VR Head-Mounted Display by a patient/subject. The initial user trials were conducted over a period of 7 weeks as part of a Master's project. Analysis of results showed a high level of improvement in Gary Barnes's movement. The VR simulation was ported to Oculus Quest by the HIVE team. The next stage of the project has been supported by a grant from the Insurance Council of Western Australia (which is nearing completion) and a few other small grants. The results collected so far indicate that the project offers considerable opportunity to help improve the quality of life for subjects with incomplete spinal cord injury.

Mars Surface and Moon Surface Impact Crater Visualisations

A/Prof Gretchen Benedix and Dr Anthony Lagain (Curtin Space Science and Technology Centre, School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering)

A machine learning algorithm was developed by the project team which identifies and counts craters on the surface of Mars. The output of this algorithm is presented on extremely large image (213k pixels x 106k pixels) provided as a series of image tiles. The HIVE team supported the project by developing an agile website which allows end-users to explore and view the extremely large image without having to download the full image to their computer. The website uses the same back-end as the Historical Panoramas project, which allows end-users to explore high-resolution images by quickly panning and zooming through the content whilst minimising the amount of data downloaded. The HIVE team have helped the project team to visualise a range of different depictions of the data which in-turn helps gain further research insights. With support from DTS (Curtin's Digital and Technology Solutions), the HIVE team were able to host the website on a local server which was publicly visible. This was particularly important because the dataset hosted on the website is extremely large and to host this dataset on a commercial host would have been prohibitively expensive for the project. This work was published in Nature Communications "The Tharsis mantle source of depleted shergottites revealed by 90 million impact craters" <<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26648-3>> which also includes a link to the HIVE hosted visualisation <<http://HIVE.curtin.edu.au/research/CDA-94M->

[release](#)>. The HIVE team have also helped visualise a similar dataset for the Moon surface which is currently under publication review embargo. The visualisations look particularly impressive on the HIVE Tiled, Cylinder and Dome displays and are regularly showcased to visitors.

"Bidi Walbraanini (Path to Healing)" Cultural Empathy Training using VR180 Video

A/Prof Marina Ciccarelli (School of Allied Health, Faculty of Health Sciences)

This project explores the use of VR180 video to provide cultural empathy training for health-sciences students. The produced video explores the experience of Aboriginal man Badi who has had a workplace injury to his arm. Viewers follow Badi on his journey to meet with an occupational physician, hand therapist and finally a difficult conversation with his employer. The hypothesis is that VR180 video helps improve students' engagement with the content and provide them with a feeling of being there. The final VR180 video can be viewed on head-mounted displays, on the HIVE Cylinder Display, and on the HIVE Dome Display. The HIVE team have also generated a regular 16:9 wide-screen version of the film (from the VR180 original) which allows the film to be viewed in a wider range of environments. The film is now actively being used with Health Sciences students at Curtin.

The HIVE helped conceive the original idea for this project, helped apply for funding through the ROC supported Cross-Faculty Research Grant scheme, provided guidance during the delivery of the project, and hosted the launch of the final VR180 video production.

Examining the Effect of Store Atmospherics with Immersive Technology

Prof Billy Sung, A/Prof Min Teah, et al (School of Management and Marketing, Faculty of Business and Law), Siobhan Hatton-Jones, Emma Regolini (honours students).

The project used immersive technologies to examine how store design, sensory pleasantness, and a store's perceived luxury influence brand and product evaluation for a commercial food outlet. A series of 360° photo captures were collected by the HIVE team at the Gabriel Chocolate Factory store in Fremantle. The HIVE team developed a visual experience to be shown on the HIVE Tiled display which was subsequently viewed individually by over 600 first year business students. The use of the 360° photos and the Dome display ensured every student received the same experience, other than two parameters that were changed. Some subjects received a taste test at the end of the experience, and some subjects had an aroma of chocolate in the space. The large pool of subjects helped increase the sensitivity and reliability of the analysis.

This work resulted in the publication of two journal papers:

- Duong, Van Chien; Sung, Billy; Barber, Matthew; Regolini, Emma; Teah, Min; (2022). Exploring store atmospherics of FMCG brands flagship stores with an immersive 180-degree dome-shaped display. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 32(4), 554-578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21639159.2022.2033131> [Journal Article]

- Duong, Van Chien; Regolini, Emma; Sung, Billy; Teah, Min; Hatton-Jones, Siobhan; (2022). Is more really better for in-store experience? A psychophysiological experiment on sensory modalities. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 39(2), 218-229. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-02-2020-3656> [Journal Article]

Visualisation of Sentiment Analysis

Felix Chan and Joyce Khoo (School of Accounting, Economics and Finance, Faculty of Business and Law)

This project explored the use of sentiment analysis to interpret the annual report of Twitter authored by then CEO Jack Dorsey. Data analysis was performed by Daniel Marrable from the Curtin Institute for Computation (now Curtin Institute for Data Science) and the visualisation of the analysis data was formed by the HIVE team. The visualisation can be displayed on the HIVE Cylinder display in 3D. This project was a proof of concept and we are exploring how this analysis can be expanded further.

2.2 Highlighted Student Projects

Pelvic Development in the Earliest Vertebrates: Elephant Shark as a Model for the Evolution of Pelvic Fins and Copulatory Organs

Jacob Pears (PhD Student), Dr Catherine Boisvert (School of Molecular and Life Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering)

Two sets of fins evolved with the first jawed vertebrates. Copulatory structures (claspers in sharks) have been described in jawless extinct vertebrates but their origin is contentious. In order to understand the origins and evolution of pelvic appendages, this project aimed to analyse the development of the pelvic musculature and associated girdle and clasper cartilages to gain a better understanding of the evolutionary processes. Data for the project consisted of nano-CT of elephant shark pelvic girdles. The project task was to identify and model the different muscles as well as the cartilage of the pelvic girdle and clasper.

The HIVE team provided a significant amount of support for this project. The project started at the outset of COVID and the original plans for this PhD were deemed impossible when all international travel was stopped. Carley Tillett from the HIVE provided guidance on an alternative project that would not require travel. The HIVE team helped to determine the best way to segment the data, help with software training and final visualisation and animation.

The project has resulted in two published journal articles:

1. **Pears, Jacob B; Tillett, Carley; Tahara, Rui; Larsson, Hans CE; Boisvert, Catherine A;** (2022). Imaging With the Past: Revealing the Complexity of Chimaeroid Pelvic Musculature Anatomy and Development. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 9, 999. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.812561> [Journal Article]

2. **Pears, Jacob B; Tillett, Carley; Tahara, Rui; Larsson, Hans CE; Trinajstic, Kate; Boisvert, Catherine A;** (2022). The Development of the Chimaeroid Pelvic Skeleton and the Evolution of Chondrichthyan Pelvic Fins. *Journal of Developmental Biology*, 10(4), 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jdb10040053> [Journal Article]

The PhD student is nearly finished and has already been offered a post-doctoral fellowship at Imperial College London.

Quantitative Assessment of Visual Motion Processing of Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)

Yi Huey Lim (PhD student), Dr Susan Morris (School of Allied Health, Faculty of Health Sciences), A/Prof Hoe Lee, Prof Torbjorn Falkmer, Prof Tele Tan, Prof Garry Allison

Individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) have been associated with sensorimotor difficulties, commonly presented by poor postural control. This project used the HIVE Dome display to provide subjects with a custom visual stimuli whilst monitoring their balance using a force plate. A total of 66 subjects were tested in the HIVE as part of this study - Thirty-three children (8–12 years old) and 33 adults (18–50 years old) with and without ASD. The study found that adults with ASD appeared more responsive to forward-moving optic flow in the peripheral visual field compared with typically developed adults.

HIVE staff supported the development of the visual stimulus that was used in the study. A VR HMD version of the test stimulus was created for use at exhibitions and demonstrations (including Autism Open Day).

This project resulted in the publication of three journal articles and the final PhD thesis:

1. **Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L;** (2018). Effect of Optic Flow on Postural Control in Children and Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorder. *Neuroscience*, 393, 138-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2018.09.047> [Journal Article]
2. **Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L;** (2019). Effect of visual information on postural control in adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 49, 4731-4739. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-018-3634-6> [Journal Article]
3. **Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L;** (2019). Postural control adaptation to optic flow in children and adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Gait & Posture*, 72, 175-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2019.06.007> [Journal Article]
4. **Lim, Yi Huey;** (2019). The Postural Control System in Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Insights from *Exploring the Effects of Visual Information on Postural Control*, Curtin University PhD Thesis. <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/bitstream/handle/20.500.11937/78788/Lim%20Y%20H%202019%20partial.pdf?sequence=1> [PhD Thesis]

The PhD student, Yi Huey Lim, graduated in 2019 and is now working for Telethon Kids Institute.

Yarrabubba Impact Crater Drone Data P3DR Processing

Wallace Maillot (student), A/Prof Nick Timms (School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering)

This project involved using photogrammetric 3D reconstruction processing to generate a detailed 3D model of the Yarrabubba Impact Crater in mid-west Western Australia from drone data. Honours thesis by

student Wallace Maillot used an ortho-mosaic of Barlangi granophyre, Yarrabubba generated by HIVE team member Daniel Adams. While Wallace completed his Honours in 2021 with flying colours, his thesis publication is 'on hold' for the time being because he has embarked on an upgrade to a Master of Research, for which his Honours research counts for the first year and he forgoes his Honours thesis. Wallace received a first-class Honours for his thesis before upgrading.

Effect of Competitors on Goal Striving and Motivation

Merrill Lombard, Sarah Paduano, Scott Dunk (psychology honours students), Dr Hugh Riddell (School of Population Health, Faculty of Health Sciences)

This study investigated whether conscious effort, ease of goal striving, physiological effort, and the number of obstacles encountered mediate relations between motives and goal attainment for a competitive cycling goal. 66 subjects underwent a bicycle riding experience in the HIVE using the newly upgraded HIVE Cylinder Display.

The HIVE team developed a custom bike riding experience in Unity which interfaced with an exercise bike and ran on the HIVE Cylinder Display. This experience was used to conduct the user trials and also collected trial data.

This project resulted in the publication of a journal article in very quick order:

Riddell, Hugh; Lamont, Wesley; Lombard, Merrill; Paduano, Sarah; Maltagliati, Silvio; Gucciardi, Daniel F; Ntoumanis, Nikos; (2023). Autonomous motivation promotes goal attainment through the conscious investment of effort, but mental contrasting with implementation intentions makes goal striving easier. *The Journal of Social Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.2022.2163610> [Journal Article]

3D Visualisation of Abnormal Gastrointestinal System

Dior Etherton (HIVE internship student), A/Prof Lisa Tee (Curtin Medical School, Faculty of Health Sciences)

MRIs and CT scans are a visualisation technique which enable medical professionals to interpret the three-dimensional structure of a patient by viewing a set of two-dimensional cross-sectional images. Projecting something of three dimensions into two-dimensions does limit the viewers understanding of the complex anatomy and three-dimensional relationships between these structures. This project has used MRIs and CT scans to construct a three-dimensional object, in order to heighten a professional's understanding of a patient's anatomy and pathology.

This project was conducted as part of the HIVE Summer Internship program. The HIVE team provided guidance and support to this project in the areas of volume visualisation and segmentation.

In 2020, Dior was announced as winner of the Peter Fillery Undergraduate Tertiary Student Project of the Year in the Lateral INCITE Awards for her HIVE Summer Internship Project.

Clinical Value of 3D Printed Models in Pre-Surgical Planning of Pancreatic Cancer Resectability

Cleo Wee (student), Prof Zhonghua Sun (Curtin Medical School, Faculty of Health Sciences)

This project focused on segmenting and visualising pancreatic cancer from a CT scan. Currently, the only cure for pancreatic cancer is complete resection of the primary tumour. Resection of primary pancreatic tumours has been linked to a long-term survival of about 25%. Surgeons currently use 2D CT or MRI scans to plan preoperatively for surgical resection. For surgeons with less experience in spatial perception, particularly trainees, accurately visualizing the 3D relationship between the tumor and surrounding vasculature is particularly challenging. 3D printing is an emerging approach that will enable surgeons to familiarize themselves with patient-specific anatomy and enhance spatial perception.

The HIVE team provided guidance on the process of segmenting and visualising volumetric data, and subsequent 3D printing of the results.

In May 2023 Cleo was awarded a prestigious Global Voices World Health Assembly (WHA) Scholarship, which provides opportunities for young leaders to make a difference on global healthcare issues.

Historical Panoramas Project

Marcia Scheider (HIVE internship student 2015), Brenton Sheer (HIVE internship student 2018), Shuchi Ganesh (HIVE internship student 2020), Claudia Dickson (HIVE internship student 2021), Corey Battersby (HIVE internship student 2021), Petra Helmholz, David Belton (School of Earth and Planetary Sciences), Dr Bri McKenzie (School of Media and Creative Arts, Faculty of Humanities), Andrew Woods (Curtin HIVE), Debra Jones (SLWA), et al.

The Historical Panoramas project started in 2015 with a SLWA supported HIVE internship and was launched as a public website www.HistoricalPanoramas.com.au in 2016. With more than 50 panoramas across 20 locations, this website allows visitors to take an unprecedented look at the history of the development of Perth and Fremantle. Stage 2 of the project website launched in September 2019. In 2020 work commenced on the development of an exhibition based on the Historical Panoramas project and this exhibition launched at the WA Maritime Museum in September 2022 for a five month run. The exhibition was seen by 30,000 visitors and won two awards (see Section 2.12 Awards). The project has involved five internship students with scholarships supported by SLWA, WA Museum and Fremantle Ports.

OldPerth Project

Will Olman (HIVE internship student 2017), Mark Shelton (HIVE internship student 2017), Max Collins (HIVE internship student 2020), Leesa Gibbons (School of Media Creative Arts and Social Enquiry, Faculty of Humanities), Andrew Woods (Curtin HIVE), Debra Jones (SLWA), et al.

The OldPerth project started as an idea with SLWA staff in 2017 to explore how photographs from the State Library collection could be browsed by their geo-location. The first student reviewed existing available options and found a candidate website which included source-code. Another intern explored the implementation of the site, and a third intern rewrote the back-end code to customise the site for the SLWA collection and the Perth location. The OldPerth site was launched as a public website www.OldPerth.org.au in April 2021. The site hosts over 10,000 images from the SLWA collection and since launch has had over 23,000 users. In 2021 the OldPerth project was a finalist in the WA Heritage Awards in the Interpretation category. (see Section 2.12 Awards)

2.3 Highlighted Projects in HIVE Focus Areas

2.4 HIVE Focus Area: Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction

Photogrammetry is the process of using photographs to collect survey accurate measurements. In contrast, *Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction* is the process of creating realistic digital 3D models of real-world objects from photographs of those objects. The HIVE team have developed considerable expertise in this field and is helping to apply those techniques across a wide range of discipline areas. A selection of projects in this focus area are:

3D Anatomy Photogrammetry Project

Margan Titmus, Dr Gary Whittaker (Curtin Medical School, Faculty of Health Sciences), et al.

Dissected cadaveric specimens are considered a 'gold standard' anatomical learning resource but can only be used within specialised licenced laboratories. Photogrammetry has recently been applied to produce 3D visualisations of cadaveric specimens. This enables the creation of digital specimen libraries, allowing anatomy students to learn outside of a traditional setting from any location.

Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction of Meteorites

Dr Lucy Forman, Prof Gretchen Benedix (School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering)

The Murrili meteorite fell in South Australia, south of Lake Eyre, in November of 2015, where the fall was recorded by the Desert Fireball Network camera observatory. It was recovered on 31st December 2015 following a search and recovery effort permitted and supported by the Arabana people, who are the traditional custodians of the land on which the meteorite fell. This rock is classified as an H5 ordinary chondrite, and was originally heart-shaped when recovered. This is the third meteorite to be recovered using the Australia Desert Fireball camera network. Murrili is on loan from the SA Museum. Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction by Andrew Woods, Curtin HIVE - with support and equipment from Gregor MacFarlane, Lucy Forman, Paul Bourke - for the Curtin Space Science Technology Centre and Desert Fireball Network.

ARC Linkage Project "Photogrammetric Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences" (Part of the *Sydney- Kormoran* Project)

Andrew Woods, Erik Champion, Petra Helmholz, David Belton, David McMeekin, Derek Lichti, Alec Coles, Catherine Belcher, Ross Anderson, Danny Murphy, Michael Harvey, James Hunter, Peter Hobbins, Jason Fair, Tanya Edwards, Ashi Doshi, Daniel Adams, Michael Wiebrands, Taylor Gray (Curtin Uni, University of Calgary, WA Museum, Australian National Maritime Museum)

This project aims to enable significant underwater cultural heritage sites such as shipwrecks to be recreated in immersive underwater virtual heritage experiences. Photogrammetric 3D reconstruction techniques will be used to generate complex digital 3D models of shipwreck sites from hundreds of thousands of underwater images. This will allow vivid experiences to be created which explain the stories of these wrecks. The project will conduct audience engagement studies to recommend the most appropriate methods to implement underwater virtual heritage experiences for Australian audiences. The sites which will be used as test datasets are some of the most significant Australian shipwreck sites, including HMAS Sydney (II) and HMAS AE1. Successful award of the ARC Linkage project grant - \$462k. Two PhD students alongside two software developers, one of whom is a MPhil student are working on the project.

HMAS AE1 3D Reconstruction Project

Andrew Woods, Joshua Hollick

Australia's first submarine HMAS AE1 was lost with no survivors on 14 September 1914 off the coast of Papua New Guinea during the first World War. The wreck was finally located in December 2017 near Rabaul in Papua New Guinea.

In April 2018 a detailed ROV survey of the wreck was conducted from the vessel RV Petrel. The digital 3D model you see here was generated using photogrammetric 3D reconstruction methods from the more than 8000 images of the wreck captured during the 2018 survey.

Interim full 3D model of the wreck of HMAS AE1 port side
3D model by Curtin University from footage courtesy of Vulcan Inc, Find AE1, ANMM and Curtin University. © Curtin University

"American B17 Bomber – Black Jack"

Andrew Woods, Daniel Adams

This American B-17F Bomber named "Black Jack" crash landed 11 July 1943 off the coast of Papua New Guinea near Boga Boga (~300km East of Port Moresby). The aircraft was on a bombing mission to Rabaul from Port Moresby, but bad weather and engine failure forced it to ditch on the return journey. The 10 crew all survived the ditching. The wreck is in 50m of water. The aircraft is 23m long and has a wingspan of 32m. The original photos of the wreck were captured by recreational divers Grant Thomas and Andrew Hamilton in June 2023.

Digital 3D model by Daniel Adams, Curtin University HIVE.

"SS Bonnie Dundee"

Andrew Woods, Daniel Adams

This 3D model shows the Stern of the historic wreck SS Bonnie Dundee, located off the coast near Swansea, NSW, Australia. The Bonnie Dundee was a 40m long steamship built in Scotland in 1877 for its Australian owners. The Bonnie Dundee was lost on 10 March 1879 following a collision with another vessel, the SS Barrabool. The original photos were captured by recreational diver Grant Thomas. Digital 3D model by Curtin University HIVE (Daniel Adams and Andrew Woods)

"SS Duckenfield".

Andrew Woods, Daniel Adams

This 3D model shows the wreck of the SS Duckenfield, located ~2.3km off the coast near Narrabeen, NSW, Australia in 24-25m water depth.

The Duckenfield was a 49m long steamship built in London UK in 1875 for its Australian owners J & A Brown who were coal merchants in Newcastle, NSW.

The Duckenfield was lost on 24 May 1889 when it struck a reef, drifted off and foundered.

The original photos of the wreck were captured by recreational divers Grant Thomas and Andrew Hamilton during a single dive on 11 March 2023.

Digital 3D model by Daniel Adams

Kyrenia Shipwreck (300 BCE) Temporal Reconstruction Project

Andrew Woods, Jeremy Green,
Daniel Adams, et al

This project allows visitors to interactively visualise the multiple three-dimensional layers of a shipwreck site. The shipwreck site was discovered in 1965 and excavated 1967-1969. During the excavation, individual layers of the excavation were extensively photographed. Photogrammetric 3D reconstruction techniques have been used to create digital 3D models of the individual layers. Additionally, the three-dimensional layout of the amphorae and millstones in the cargo have been turned into a CAD model, and the two parts of the separated hull have been rejoined to closely match the original form at the time of sinking. The resultant 3D model can be explored in a way that has never been possible before via this webpage: <https://hive.curtin.edu.au/kyrenia>

A total of more than 40 wreck sites have been reconstructed by the HIVE team to date.

2.5 HIVE Focus Area: Volume Visualisation

The term “Volume Visualisation” refers to the technique of using advanced visualisation tools to view, interpret and understand datasets that are intrinsically volumetric in nature – containing data which characterises a three-dimensional volume. Such datasets are typically CT (computed tomography) and MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) as used in medical applications, micro-CT as used in geological analysis applications, and acoustic multi-beam survey datasets as used in marine applications. A selection of projects in this focus area includes are:

Aortic 3D models on the Hologram Table

A/Prof Lisa BG Tee, Prof Zhonghua Sun (Curtin Medical School, Faculty of Health Sciences).

MRIs and CT scans are a visualisation technique which enable medical professionals to interpret the three-dimensional structure of a patient by viewing a set of two-dimensional cross-sectional images. Projecting

something of three dimensions into two-dimensions does limit the viewers understanding of the complex anatomy and three-dimensional relationships between these structures. This project has used MRIs and CT scans to construct a three-dimensional object, in order to heighten a professional's understanding of a patient's anatomy and pathology.

Developing digital 3D models of native animal skulls

Andrew Woods, Carley Tillett (Curtin HIVE), DBCA (Department of Biodiversity Conservation and Attractions).

The project aims to develop a digital 3D model of a native Australian animal skulls suitable for sharing on Sketchfab or a VR/AR platform. A total of 10 skulls models were imaged and modelled from physical post-mortem specimens. The DBCA have included this content in an online educational resource for school children called “Boneheads”. See the “Return to 1616 Educational Package” here: <https://www.sharkbay.org/restoration/dirk-hartog-island-return-1616/education/#1652676922996-ca3ce5d2-50ea> (Boneheads 3D Skulls Activity) and <https://skfb.ly/oAEZx> (Boneheads 3D Skulls models).

2.6 HIVE Focus Area: Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality

The HIVE team have considerable expertise in the development of Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) experiences. An often used umbrella term for VR and AR technologies is the term XR – for Extended Reality. We have seen a broad interest in using VR across a wide range of projects and as a result the HIVE has supported a wide range of projects using VR and AR tools across wide range of disciplines. We foresee this continuing interest and development continuing as technologies, products and software improve and more people become aware of the possibilities offered by this technology. A selection of projects in this focus area are:

Mars in VR

Professor Gretchen Benedix (School of Earth and Planetary Sciences) – with Curtin Computer Science student Jack McNair

Topographic data from the HiRISE Mars satellite has been used to create a realistic depiction of the Martian environment. Users can traverse this environment in simulated air and ground vehicles, as well as on foot. The environment can be viewed using a VR head-mounted-display allowing users to explore the Martian landscape in full stereoscopic 3D and allowing for more immersive visualisation than was ever possible with conventional 2D rendering.

Visualising carbon nanostructures using MDV

Associate Professor Nigel Marks and Dr Carla de Tomas (Carbon Group, Discipline of Physics) – in cooperation with Professor Ricardo Mancera (School of Pharmacy and Biomedical Science) and Professor Andrew Rohl (Curtin Institute for Computation)

Activated carbons are man-made disordered nanoporous materials. Visualisation of the structures using the HIVE Cylinder display and MDV software give an unparalleled view to aid in understanding the role of morphological features. Visualisation also allowed us to assess how oxygen bonded to the carbon structure. These results provide, for the first time, a realistic approach to modelling the complex structures of activated carbons. The underlying VR application “Molecular Dynamics Visualiser” (MDV) has been developed at Curtin.

VR for Spinal Cord Injury Rehabilitation

Associate Professor Marina Ciccarelli, Dr Sue Morris (Curtin School of Allied Health) with Gary Barnes and Greg Hewitt.

The use of VR in this project is particularly impactful because we believe it has demonstrated measurable improvements after sustained use of the technology.

See extended project description in Section 2.1 Highlighted Projects.

Chemistry Education in VR

Associate Professor Mihye Won, David Treagust (Curtin School of Education), Dewi Ungu, Henry Matovu, Bruno Hernandez (PhD students), et al.

A custom VR environment has been developed which allows two users wearing head-mounted-displays to be shrunk down to molecular level to learn about and experience the docking of atoms and proteins.

See extended project description in Section 2.1 Highlighted Projects.

MissionsConnect - Cultural healing through Virtual reality: stolen Generation survivors and Mission sites

Professor Reena Tiwari (School of Design and the Built Environment), et al – in cooperation with Bringing Them Home WA

The reconstructed virtual environment of Aboriginal Mission Sites can be used as a digital story-telling tool, not only for the Stolen Generation survivors and their families, but as an education tool for the wider Aboriginal and non-indigenous community.

See extended project description in Section 2.1 Highlighted Projects.

Examining the Effect of Store Atmospheric with Immersive Technology

Prof Billy Sung, A/Prof Min Teah, et al (School of Management and Marketing, Faculty of Business and Law), Siobhan Hatton-Jones, Emma Regolini (honours students).

This project presents a selection of "VR" 360-degree still images captured at the Gabriel Chocolate Factory store in Fremantle on the HIVE Dome display.

See extended project description in Section 2.1 Highlighted Projects.

The full range of HIVE projects using VR and AR technologies is extensive.

A full list of all projects supported by the HIVE across all disciplines and faculties in this reporting period is provided in Appendix A.

2.7 Grants and Grant Applications

The HIVE offers a range of support to grant applications. The HIVE is often cited in sections of applications relating to research infrastructure and research environment. The HIVE also advises applicants on the opportunities for including visualisation aspects in their applications.

A fully itemised list of grants that have been supported by the HIVE or that have cited the HIVE from 2018 – 2023 is provided in Appendix B. The list includes some data from prior years since grants (especially successful ones) are often a multi-year initiative.

Over the period 2018-2023, the HIVE was been cited in or supported \$51M worth of grant applications and \$31M worth of successful grants. Additionally the HIVE has been cited in or supported 16 ARC grant applications, and 6 successful ARC grants.

A summary of the grants is provided below:

	2018		2019		2020		2021		2022		2023 YTD		Total	
	Applied	Success-ful	Applied	Success-ful	Applied	Success-ful	Applied	Success-ful	Applied	Success-ful	Applied	Success-ful	Applied	Success-ful
ARC	3	1	4	2	2	1	1	0	6	2	0	0	16	6
Other	10	8	6	3	14	7	11	9	13	8	6	3	59	38
Total	13	9	10	5	16	8	12	9	19	10	6	3	75	44
Value (\$)	5,732,807	4,294,763	2,536,650	1,354,660	6,693,272	1,724,985	22,348,136	20,317,784	12,672,072	3,198,595	1,166,813	285,661	51,149,751	31,176,450

2.8 Publications

A detailed listing of all published outputs citing the HIVE or supported by the HIVE for the period of this report are listed below. In summary, during the period of this report there have been a total of 87 publications comprising 5 books, 9 book chapters, 49 journal articles, 20 conference papers, 3 general articles, and 1 PhD Thesis.

2018

- **Wiebrands, Michael; Malajczuk, Chris J; Woods, Andrew J; Rohl, Andrew L; Mancera, Ricardo L;** (2018). Molecular dynamics visualization (MDV): stereoscopic 3D display of biomolecular structure and interactions using the Unity game engine. *Journal of integrative bioinformatics*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2018-0010> [Journal Article]
- **Woods, Andrew; Bourke, Paul; Oliver, Nick;** (2018). Beacon Virtua. *2018 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, 844-844. <https://doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/VR.2018.8446239> [Conference Paper]
- **Joseph, Pauline;** (2018). Developing visualisation prototypes from EZproxy server logs to understand information seeking behavior of Curtin Library users. *Preservation, Digital Technologies & Culture*, 47(1), 23-26. <http://doi.org/10.1515/pdct-2018-0007> [Journal Article]
- **Sommer, Björn; Baaden, Marc; Krone, Michael; Woods, Andrew;** (2018). From Virtual Reality to Immersive Analytics in Bioinformatics. *Journal of integrative bioinformatics*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2018-0043> [Journal Article]
- **Broderick, M;** (2018). Fading Lights: Digital Visualization and the Legacy of Hiroshima and Nagasaki. <https://scholar.google.com.au/scholar?oi=bibs&cluster=2850133461394571749&btnI=1&hl=en> [Book Chapter]

- **O'Halloran, Kay L; Tan, Sabine; Wiebrands, Michael; Sheffield, Rachel; Wignell, Peter; Turner, Paul;** (2018). The Multimodal Classroom in the Digital Age: The Use of 360 Degree Videos for Online Teaching and Learning. *Multimodality Across Classrooms*, 84-102. <http://doi.org/10.4324/9780203701072> [Book Chapter]
- **Greenfeld, Adam; Lugmayr, Artur; Lamont, Wesley;** (2018). Comparative Reality: Measuring User Experience and Emotion in Immersive Virtual Environments. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 204-209. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00048> [Conference Paper]
- **Woods, Andrew J; Holliman, Nicolas S; Favalora, Gregg E; Kawai, Takashi; Sommer, Björn;** (2018). Stereoscopic Displays and Applications XXIX-Introduction. *Electronic Imaging*, 2018(4), 476-1-476-7. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2018.04.SDA-476> [Conference Paper]
- **Sun, Zhonghua;** (2018). Coronary CT Angiography in the Quantitative Analysis of Coronary Plaques. https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814725620_0001 [Book]
- **Kear, Robin; Joranson, Kate;** (2018). Digital humanities, libraries, and partnerships: a critical examination of labor, networks, and community. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2016-0-01794-1> [Book]
- **Sun, Zhonghua;** (2018). 3D Printing As a New Technique in Management of Right Heart Pathology. *Right Heart Pathology: From Mechanism to Management*, 641-653. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73764-5_38 [Book Chapter]
- **Sun, Zhonghua; Liu, Dongting;** (2018). A systematic review of clinical value of three-dimensional printing in renal disease. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*, 8(3), 311. <https://doi.org/10.21037/qims.2018.03.09> [Journal Article]
- **Liu, Dongting; Sun, Zhonghua; Chaichana, Thanapong; Ducke, Werner; Fan, Zhanming;** (2018). Patient-specific 3D printed models of renal tumours using home-made 3D printer in comparison with commercial 3D printer. *Journal of Medical Imaging and Health Informatics*, 8(2), 303-308. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jmihi.2018.2294> [Journal Article]
- **Givehchi, Sogol; Safari, Mohammad Javad; Tan, Sock Keow; Shah, Mohammad Nazri Bin Md; Sani, Fadhli Bin Mohamed; Azman, Raja Rizal; Sun, Zhonghua; Yeong, Chai Hong; Ng, Kwan Hoong; Wong, Jeannie Hsiu Ding;** (2018). Measurement of coronary bifurcation angle with coronary CT angiography: A phantom study. *Physica Medica*, 45, 198-204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2017.09.137> [Journal Article]
- **Cozens, Paul; McLeod, Sam; Matthews, Jane;** (2018). Visual representations in crime prevention: exploring the use of building information modelling (BIM) to investigate burglary and crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED). *Crime Prevention and Community Safety*, 20(2), 63-83. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41300-018-0039-6> [Journal Article]
- **Chu, Michael; Matthews, Jane; Love, Peter ED;** (2018). Integrating mobile building information modelling and augmented reality systems: an experimental study. *Automation in Construction*, 85, 305-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2017.10.032> [Journal Article]
- **O'Halloran, Kay L; Tan, Sabine; Pham, Duc-Son; Bateman, John; Vande Moere, Andrew;** (2018). A digital mixed methods research design: Integrating multimodal analysis with data mining and information visualization for big data analytics. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 12(1), 11263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689816651015> [Journal Article]
- **Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkner, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L;** (2018). Effect of Optic Flow on Postural Control in Children and Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorder. *Neuroscience*, 393, 138-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2018.09.047> [Journal Article]
- **Lugmayr, Artur; Lim, Yi Juin; Hollick, Joshua; Khuu, Joyce; Chan, Felix;** (2018). Financial Data Visualization in 3D on Immersive Virtual Reality Displays. *International Workshop on Enterprise Applications, Markets and Services in the Finance Industry*, 118-130. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19037-8_8 [Conference Paper]
- **Soon, Susannah; Lugmayr, Artur; Woods, Andrew; Tan, Tele;** (2018). Understanding Head-Mounted Display FOV in Maritime Search and Rescue Object Detection. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 116-119. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00023> [Conference Paper]
- **Soon, Susannah; Lugmayr, Artur; Woods, Andrew; Tan, Tele;** (2018). Head-Mounted FOV Simulator for User Testing of Maritime Object Detection Tasks. *2018 IEEE International Conference*

on *Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 183-184. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00039> [Conference Paper]

- **Zhu, Kening; Lugmayr, Artur; Ma, Xiaojuan; Mueller, Florian Floyd; Engelke, Ulrich; Simoff, Simeon; Trescak, Tomas; Bogdavych, Anton; Aguilar, Juan Rodriguez; Vu, Huyen;** (2018). Interface and Experience Design with AI for VR/AR (DAIVAR'18) and AI/ML for Immersive Simulations (AMISIM'18). *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 227-228. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00052> [Conference Paper]
- **Beynon, David; Datta, Sambit; Hollick, Joshua;** (2018). Digitised connections: Reflections on the image analysis and spatial modelling of Southeast Asian temples. *Proceedings of digital cultural heritage: FUTURE VISIONS Brisbane 2017 Conference*, 36-52. https://dro.deakin.edu.au/articles/conference_contribution/Digitised_connections_reflections_on_the_image_analysis_and_spatial_modelling_of_Southeast_Asian_temples/21027187/1 [Conference Paper]
- **Briggs, Peter;** (2018). "Research Vessel Petrel Baseline Survey of HMAS AE1" Australian National Maritime Museum. https://www.sea.museum/-/media/anmm/files/support/ae1_petrel_report-final-print-version.pdf?la=en [Book]
- **Hunter, J; Woods, A;** (2018). Imaging Australia's First Naval Loss. *Signals Magazine*, 2-7. [General Article]

2019

- **Woods, Andrew; Oliver, Nick; Bourke, Paul; Green, Jeremy; Paterson, Alistair;** (2019). Beacon Virtua: A Virtual Reality Simulation Detailing the Recent and Shipwreck History of Beacon Island, Western Australia. *3D Recording and Interpretation for Maritime Archaeology*, 197-210. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03635-5_13 [Book Chapter]
- **Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L;** (2019). Effect of visual information on postural control in adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 49, 4731-4739. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-018-3634-6> [Journal Article]
- **O'Halloran, Kay L; Tan, Sabine; Wignell, Peter; Bateman, John A; Pham, Duc-Son; Grossman, Michele; Moere, Andrew Vande;** (2019). Interpreting text and image relations in violent extremist discourse: A mixed methods approach for big data analytics. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 31(3), 454-474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2016.1233871> [Journal Article]
- **Won, Mihye; Mocerino, Mauro; Tang, Kok-Sing; Treagust, David F; Tasker, Roy;** (2019). Interactive immersive virtual reality to enhance students' visualisation of complex molecules. *Research and Practice in Chemistry Education: Advances from the 25th IUPAC International*

- Conference on Chemistry Education* 2018, 51-64. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-6998-8_4 [Conference Paper]
- **Joseph, Pauline; Kent, Aaron Justin; Green, Peter Damian; Robinson, Matthew; Bellenger, Amanda;** (2019). Analysis of EZproxy server logs to visualise research activity in Curtin's online library. *Library Hi Tech*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-04-2018-0050> [Journal Article]
 - **Adams, Daniel; Steven Pham, Tri Tai; Watts, Kale; Ramakrishnan, Subhash; Ackland, Emily; Tran Ly, Ham; Hollick, Joshua; Woods, Andrew;** (2019). Development of a Camera-Based Projection Mapping System for Non-Flat Surfaces. *Electronic Imaging*, 2019(3), 660-1-660-8. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2019.3.SDA-660> [Conference Paper]
 - **Woods, Andrew J; Holliman, Nicolas S;** (2019). 30 Years of the Stereoscopic Displays and Applications conference-Milestones and Statistics. *Electronic Imaging*, 2019(3), C03-1-C03-12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2019.3.SDA-C03> [Conference Paper]
 - **Woods, Andrew J; Holliman, Nicolas S; Favalora, Gregg E; Kawai, Takashi; Sommer, Björn;** (2019). 30th Annual Stereoscopic Displays and Applications Conference-Introduction. *Electronic Imaging*, 2019(3), B03-1-B03-7. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2019.3.SDA-B03> [Conference Paper]
 - **Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L;** (2019). Postural control adaptation to optic flow in children and adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Gait & Posture*, 72, 175-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2019.06.007> [Journal Article]
 - **Albahri, Mohammed; Barifcani, Ahmed; Dwivedi, Deepak; Iglauer, Stefan; Lebedev, Maxim; MacLeod, Ian D; Machuca, Laura L;** (2019). X-ray micro-computed tomography analysis of accumulated corrosion products in deep-water shipwrecks. *Materials and Corrosion*, 70(11), 1977-1998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/maco.201910842> [Journal Article]
 - **Martin, Jacob W; de Tomas, Carla; Suarez-Martinez, Irene; Kraft, Markus; Marks, Nigel A;** (2019). Topology of disordered 3D graphene networks. *Physical Review Letters*, 123(11), 116105. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.123.116105> [Journal Article]
 - **Holliman, Nicolas S; Coltekin, Arzu; Fernstad, Sara J; McLaughlin, Lucy; Simpson, Michael D; Woods, Andrew J;** (2019). Visual entropy and the visualization of uncertainty. arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.12879. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1907.12879> [Journal Article]
 - **Lee, Shen-yuan; Squelch, Andrew; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2019). Quantitative assessment of 3D printed model accuracy in delineating the normal heart anatomy based on in vitro phantom experiments. *Australasian Medical Journal*. <http://doi.org/10.35841/1836-1935.12.10.276-284> [Journal Article]
 - **Sun, Zhonghua; Jansen, Shirley;** (2019). Personalized 3D printed coronary models in coronary stenting. *Quantitative Imaging in Medicine and Surgery*, 9(8), 1356. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8040522> [Journal Article]
 - **Lau, Ivan Wen Wen; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2019). Dimensional Accuracy and Clinical Value of 3D Printed Models in Congenital Heart Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 8(9), 1483. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8091483> [Journal Article]
 - **Sun, Zhonghua; Lau, Ivan; Wong, Yin How; Yeong, Chai Hong;** (2019). Personalized three-dimensional printed models in congenital heart disease. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 8(4), 522. <https://doi.org/10.21037%2Fqims.2019.06.21> [Journal Article]
 - **Lau, Ivan; Wong, Yin How; Yeong, Chai Hong; Aziz, Yang Faridah Abdul; Sari, Nor Ashikin Md; Hashim, Shahrul Amry; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2019). Quantitative and qualitative comparison of low-and high-cost 3D-printed heart models. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*, 9(1), 107. <https://doi.org/10.21037%2Fqims.2019.01.02> [Journal Article]
 - **Aldosari, Sultan; Jansen, Shirley; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2019). Patient-specific 3D printed pulmonary artery model with simulation of peripheral pulmonary embolism for developing optimal computed tomography pulmonary angiography protocols. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*, 9(1), 75. <https://doi.org/10.21037%2Fqims.2018.10.13> [Journal Article]
 - **Fordham, Drew; Lewis, David; Bellenger, Amanda;** (2019). Swimming In The Deep End: Curtin Library's Deep Dive Into Data.... <https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/iatul/2019/value/2/> [Conference Paper]
 - **Brant, Nicholas;** (2019). Seeing clearly. *Create*, 5(8). <https://search.informit.org/doi/pdf/10.3316/informit.906065511533282> [Magazine article]

- **Dawson, Beata; Joseph, Pauline; Champion, Erik;** (2019). The story of the Markham car collection: a cross-platform panoramic tour of contested heritage. *Collections*, 15(1), 62-86. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550190619832381> [Journal Article]

2020

- **Benedix, GK; Lagain, A; Chai, K; Meka, S; Anderson, S; Norman, C; Bland, PA; Paxman, J; Towner, MC; Tan, T;** (2020). Deriving Surface Ages on Mars using Automated Crater Counting. *Earth and Space Science*, e2019EA001005. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019EA001005> [Journal Article]
- **Sun, Zhonghua;** (2020). Use of three-dimensional printing in the development of optimal cardiac CT scanning protocols. *Current medical imaging*, 16(8), 967-977. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1573405616666200124124140> [Journal Article]
- **Tiwari, Reena; Stephens, John Richard;** (2020). Trauma and healing at Western Australia's former native missions. *AlterNative: An International Journal of Indigenous Peoples*, 16(3), 248-258. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1177180120948277> [Journal Article]
- **Woods, Andrew; Oliver, Nick; Hollick, Joshua; Green, Jeremy; Baker, Patrick;** (2020). 3D Reconstruction of the Batavia (1629) Wreck Site from Historical (1970s) Photography. *Shared Heritage: Proceedings of the Sixth International Congress for Underwater Archaeology 2016*, 382-391. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/5245226#page=402> [Conference Paper]
- **Helmholz, Petra; Belton, David; Oliver, Nick; Hollick, Joshua; Woods, Andrew;** (2020). The Influence of the Point Cloud Comparison Methods on the Verification of Point Clouds Using the Batavia Reconstruction as a Case Study. *IKUWA6 Shared Heritage: Proceedings of the Sixth International Congress for Underwater Archaeology*, 6, 370-381. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11937/81628> [Conference Paper]
- **Rickard, William DA; Ramos Coelho, Jéssica Fernanda; Hollick, Joshua; Soon, Susannah; Woods, Andrew;** (2020). Application of Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction to Scanning Electron Microscopy: Considerations for Volume Analysis. *Journal of Imaging Science and Technology*, 64(6), 60404-1-60404-9. <https://doi.org/10.2352/J.ImagingSci.Technol.2020.64.6.060404> [Journal Article]
- **Green, Jeremy; Paterson, Alistair;** (2020). Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties: Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks, UWA Publishing. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias-> [Book]
- **Green, Jeremy; Shaw, Lachlan; Hollick, Joshua; Woods, Andrew; Helmholz, Petra; Belton, David;** (2020). "Working with Legacy Data: Santo Antonio de Tanna." in "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties - Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks", 239-245. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias-> [Book Chapter]
- **Woods, Andrew; Oliver, Nick; Hollick, Joshua; Green, Jeremy; Baker, Patrick;** (2020). "3D Reconstruction of the Batavia Wreck Site." in "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties - Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks", 232-238. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias-> [Book Chapter]
- **Woods, Andrew; Bourke, Paul; Oliver, Nick;** (2020). "Beacon Virtua." in "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties - Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks", 223-232. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias-> [Book Chapter]
- **Adams, Daniel; Baker, Patrick; McAllister, Madeline; Winton, Trevor; Woods, Andrew;** (2020). Successful Creation of a Photogrammetric Model of the James Matthews (1841) Wrecksite from Legacy Photography. *Australasian Journal of Maritime Archaeology*, 44, 71-89. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357822825_Successful_3D_digital_modelling_of_the_James_Matthews_1841_excavated_wrecksite_using_legacy_photography [Journal Article]
- **Etherton, Dior; Tee, Lisa; Tillett, Carley; Wong, Yin Hong; Yeong, Chai Hong; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2020). 3D visualization and 3D printing in abnormal gastrointestinal system manifestations of situs ambiguus. *Quantitative Imaging in Medicine and Surgery*, 10(9), 1877. <https://doi.org/10.21037/qims-20-661> [Journal Article]

- **Helmholz, P; Mousa, Y; Snow, T; Haebich, A; Piggot, G; Tonkin, J; Lamont, W;** (2020). Geo-Locating Historical Survey Data and Images—A Case Study for the Canning River, Perth, Western Australia. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*, 43. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B4-2020-575-2020> [Peer-reviewed Conference Paper]

2021

- **Woods, Andrew J;** (2021). Sourcing and Qualifying Passive Polarised 3D TVs. *Electronic Imaging*, 2021(2), 100-1-100-6. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2021.2.SDA-100> [Conference Paper]
- **Beynon, David; Datta, Sambit;** (2021). Architectonic connections: virtual reconstruction to disseminate understanding of South and Southeast Asian temples. *Access and Control in Digital Humanities*, 130-152. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429259616> [Book Chapter]
- **Lagain, A; Benedix, GK; Servis, K; Baratoux, David; Doucet, LS; Rajšić, A; Devillepoix, HAR; Bland, PA; Towner, MC; Sansom, EK;** (2021). The Tharsis mantle source of depleted shergottites revealed by 90 million impact craters. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), 6352. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26648-3> [Journal Article]
- **Lagain, Anthony; Servis, Konstantinos; Benedix, GK; Norman, Christopher; Anderson, Seamus; Bland, PA;** (2021). Model age derivation of large martian impact craters, using automatic crater counting methods. *Earth and Space Science*, 8(2), e2020EA001598. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001598> [Journal Article]

2022

- **Pears, Jacob B; Tillett, Carley; Tahara, Rui; Larsson, Hans CE; Boisvert, Catherine A;** (2022). Imaging With the Past: Revealing the Complexity of Chimaeroid Pelvic Musculature Anatomy and Development. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 9, 999. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.812561> [Journal Article]
- **Duong, Van Chien; Sung, Billy; Barber, Matthew; Regolini, Emma; Teah, Min;** (2022). Exploring store atmospherics of FMCG brands flagship stores with an immersive 180-degree dome-shaped display. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 32(4), 554-578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21639159.2022.2033131> [Journal Article]
- **Duong, Van Chien; Regolini, Emma; Sung, Billy; Teah, Min; Hatton-Jones, Siobhan;** (2022). Is more really better for in-store experience? A psychophysiological experiment on sensory modalities. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 39(2), 218-229. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-02-2020-3656> [Journal Article]
- **McCarthy, John Kennington;** (2022). Jeremy Green and Alistair Paterson, Editors: Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties: Researching Some of Australia's Earliest Shipwrecks: *UWA Publishing*, Crawley, 2020, 316 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-021-09321-0> [Book]
- **Lagain, Anthony; Kreslavsky, Mikhail; Baratoux, David; Liu, Yebo; Devillepoix, Hadrien; Bland, Philip; Benedix, Gretchen K; Doucet, Luc S; Servis, Konstantinos;** (2022). Has the impact flux of small and large asteroids varied through time on Mars, the Earth and the Moon?. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 579, 117362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2021.117362> [Journal Article]
- **Lagain, A; Benedix, GK; Servis, K; Baratoux, D; Doucet, L-S; Rajšić, A; Devillepoix, HAR; Bland, PA; Towner, MC; Sansom, E;** (2022). The Tharsis Mantle Source of Depleted Shergottites Revealed by 90 Million Impact Craters. *LPI Contributions*, 2678, 1011. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2022LPICo2678.1011L> [Conference Paper]
- **Geerlings-Batt, Jade; Tillett, Carley; Gupta, Ashu; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2022). Enhanced Visualisation of Normal Anatomy with Potential Use of Augmented Reality Superimposed on Three-Dimensional Printed Models. *Micromachines*, 13(10), 1701. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi13101701> [Journal Article]
- **Khaksar, Siavash; Pieters, Stefanie; Borazjani, Bitia; Hyde, Joshua; Booker, Harrison; Khokhar, Adil; Murray, Iain; Campbell, Amity;** (2022). Posture Monitoring and Correction Exercises for Workers in Hostile Environments Utilizing Non-Invasive Sensors: Algorithm Development and Validation. *MDPI Sensors*, 22(24), 9618. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22249618> [Journal Article]

- **Pears, Jacob B; Tillett, Carley; Tahara, Rui; Larsson, Hans CE; Trinajstic, Kate; Boisvert, Catherine A;** (2022). The Development of the Chimaeroid Pelvic Skeleton and the Evolution of Chondrichthyan Pelvic Fins. *Journal of Developmental Biology*, 10(4), 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jdb10040053> [Journal Article]
- **Green, Jeremy; Adams, Daniel; Woods, Andrew;** (2022). The Kyrenia Ship Three-dimensional Modelling Project. *Australasian Institute for Maritime Archaeology*, 39(2), 45112. [General Article]
- **Duncan, Brad;** (2022). Wollongbar (II) Shipwreck Inspections 2019 Off Crescent Head, NSW. <https://heritagensw.intersearch.com.au/heritagenswjsui/handle/1/10662> [Book Chapter]
- **Won, Mihye; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Matovu, Henry; Treagust, David F; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Park, Jungho; Mocerino, Mauro; Tasker, Roy;** (2022). Diverse approaches to learning with immersion virtual reality identified from a systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 195104701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104701> [Journal Article]
- **Matovu, Henry; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Won, Mihye; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Treagust, David F; Mocerino, Mauro; Tasker, Roy;** (2022). Immersive virtual reality for science learning: Design, implementation, and evaluation. *Studies in Science Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057267.2022.2082680> [Journal Article]
- **Lau, Ivan; Gupta, Ashu; Ihdahid, Abdul; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2022). Clinical Applications of Mixed Reality and 3D Printing in Congenital Heart Disease. *Biomolecules*, 12111548. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12111548> [Journal Article]
- **Zhao, Ruzhen; Volgger, Michael; Thomas, Ben; Guo, Xiumei;** (2022). Perception of tourism atmosphere at mine sites: A cross-cultural analysis of atmospheric interventions. *CAUTHE 2022 Conference Online: Shaping the Next Normal in Tourism, Hospitality and Events: Proceedings of the 32nd Annual Conference*, 638-641. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.417838712901453> [Conference Paper]
- **Volgger, M; Zhao, R; Sung, B; Marques, S;** (2022). Atmospheric interventions in anthropogenic and natural landscapes: An inter-cultural analysis. International colloquium on 'Quo vadis research on spatial atmospheres?'. [Conference Paper]

2023

- **Titmus, Morgan; Whittaker, Gary; Radunski, Milo; Ellery, Paul; IR de Oliveira, Beatriz; Radley, Hannah; Helmholtz, Petra; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2023). A workflow for the creation of photorealistic 3D cadaveric models using photogrammetry. *Journal of Anatomy*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joa.13872> [Journal Article]
- **Delpech, Kian; Tillett, Carley; Bhandari, Mayank; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2023). Investigation of 3D virtual reality in pre-surgical planning of malignant hepatic tumours. *Australasian Medical Journal*, 16(3), 556-577. <https://doi.org/10.21767/AMJ.2023.3942> [Journal Article]
- **Tang, William; Wang, Shijie; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2023). Role of three-dimensional printing and virtual reality in medical applications: A medical student's reflection. *Australasian Medical Journal*, 16(4), 604-607. <https://doi.org/10.21767/AMJ.2023.3947> [Journal Article]
- **Williams, Ally; Tillett, Carley; Wong, Yin How; Yeong, Chai Hong; Sun, Zhonghua;** (2023). How 3D Printing Software Enhances and Rewards Student Learning of Brain Anatomy. *Australasian Medical Journal*, 16(3), 552-555. <https://doi.org/10.21767/AMJ.2023.3936> [Journal Article]
- **Riddell, Hugh; Lamont, Wesley; Lombard, Merrill; Paduano, Sarah; Maltagliati, Silvio; Gucciardi, Daniel F; Ntoumanis, Nikos;** (2023). Autonomous motivation promotes goal attainment through the conscious investment of effort, but mental contrasting with implementation intentions makes goal striving easier. *The Journal of Social Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.2022.2163610> [Journal Article]
- **Matovu, Henry; Won, Mihye; Treagust, David Franklin; Mocerino, Mauro; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Tasker, Roy;** (2023). Analysis of students' diagrams of water molecules in snowflakes to reveal their conceptual understanding of hydrogen bonds. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RP00175F> [Journal Article]
- **Matovu, Henry; Won, Mihye; Treagust, David Franklin; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Mocerino, Mauro; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Tasker, Roy;** (2023). Change in students' explanation of the shape of snowflakes after collaborative immersive virtual reality. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RP00176D> [Journal Article]

2.9 Theses

2019

- **Lim, Yi Huey;** (2019). The Postural Control System in Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Insights from Exploring the Effects of Visual Information on Postural Control, Curtin University PhD Thesis.
<https://espace.curtin.edu.au/bitstream/handle/20.500.11937/78788/Lim%20Y%20H%202019%20partial.pdf?sequence=1> [PhD Thesis]

2.10 Technical Reports

A detailed listing of all technical reports citing the HIVE or supported by the HIVE for the period of this report are listed below:

2018

- **Soon, S., Tan, T., Woods, A.,** 2018, Exploring Target Detection and Tracking in Real-Time Video of Submarine Periscope Imagery for Head Mounted Displays, Technical Report, 55p., Curtin University. Prepared for DSTG. [Project Report]

2019

- **Soon, S., Tan, T.,** 2019, Factors Affecting the Human Visual Search Task for Maritime Imagery, Technical Report, 15pp., Curtin University. Prepared for Defence Science Technology Group. [Project Report]
- **Allahham, A., Miljkovic, K.,** 2019, Scientific Visualisation of Asteroid Strikes and Cratered Worlds. Final Report, 28pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Thomas, A., de Tomas, C.,** 2019, Visualizing carbon nanostructures: a realistic model of activated carbons. Final Report, 28pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Cheng, B., Won, M.,** 2019, Shooting arrows in an immersive virtual reality: experiencing and modelling science experiments to learn Newtonian physics concepts. Final Report, 34pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Nagarsheth, D., Ciccarelli, M., McMahon, D., Soon, S., Wiebrands, M.,** 2019, A mobile educational resource for the safe and efficient use of public transportation in Perth. Final Report, 25pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Jackson, E., McMeekin, D., Woods, A., Green, J.,** 2019, Transforming the Journals of Francisco Pelsaert, Commander of the Dutch VOC Ship Batavia, into a Web Archive moving towards Linked Open Data. Final Report, 26pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Found, L., Elders, C., Cunneen, J.,** 2019, Application of automatic horizon picking software to seismic interpretation. Final Report, 32pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **McCormack, I., Lugmayr, A., Woods, A., McKenzie, T., Underwood, A.,** 2019, Living Historical Documents - The Diaries of Frances Bussell (1807-1881). Final Report, 23pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

2020

- **Xing, D(J)., Miljkovic, K., Lagain, A., Soon, S., Wiebrands, M.,** 2020, Mars Craters. Final Report, 17pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Etherton, D., Tee, L., Sun, Z., Tillett, C.,** 2020, 3D Visualisation of Abnormal Gastrointestinal System – When the Right is Not Right, and the Left is Not Left. Final Report, 16pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Lu, M., Elders, C., Olierook, H.,** 2020, Indian Ocean Tectonics from Detailed Bathymetry Data. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

- **Bi, M., Walker, R., Morey, V., Dinham, J., Dobson, M., Sims, C., Lamont, W.,** 2020, Building student engagement and supporting learning through interactive virtual reality environments. Final Report, 43pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Collins, M., Woods, A., Lamont, W., Jones, D.,** 2020, OldPerth – Mapping Historical Photographs of Perth. Final Report, 68pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Greif, M., Mancera, R., Ruiz-Perez, L.,** 2020, What happens when you rub on that cream? Understanding how drug molecules penetrate our skin by molecular visualization. Final Report, 13pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **O’Sullivan, M., Shoher, P., Towner, M., Tillett, C.,** 2020, Visualising the Orbits of Small Solar System Bodies Using Data from the Desert Fireball Network. Final Report, 47pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Spear, O., Jones, J., Glitsos, L., Jones, C., Tillett, C.,** 2020, Two Rivers Deep. Final Report, 29pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Tenedero, P., Helmholz, P., Green, J., Woods, J.,** 2020, Photogrammetric Analysis of 4th Century BC Kyrenia Shipwreck. Final Report, 30pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Mousa, Y., Helmholz, P., Snow, T., Haebich, H.,** 2020, The Canning River in 1841 and today. Final Report, 22pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

2021

- **Soon, S., Collins, M., McNair, J., Tan, T.,** 2021, Human Detection and Display Modalities. Final Report, 67pp., Curtin University. Prepared for Defence Science Technology Group (DSTG). [Project Report]
- **Zhao, R(C), Volgger, M., Thomas, B., Guo, X., Lamont, W., Tillett, C.,** 2021, Using Virtual Reality to Explore the Perception of Tourism Atmospheres at Mine Sites: A Cross-Cultural Analysis of Atmospheric Interventions. Final Report, 63pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Hall, C., Mancera, R., Malajczuk, C., Rozano, L.,** 2021, The spike protein of SARS-Cov-2: its interactions with antibodies and receptors and the role of mutations. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Bell, S., Izadpanahi, P., Pillai, J., Newman, P., Mouritz, M., Hargroves, C., Lamont, W., Woods, A.,** 2021, Visualising 21st Century Boulevards. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Athreya, S., McKenzie, B., Tillett, C., Woods, A., Wallis-Smith, D., Edwards, T.,** 2021, Fremantle Panoramas: Exhibition. Final Report, 25pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Dann, C., Sun, Z., Jansen, S., Tillett, C.,** 2021, Virtual reality-assisted assessment of type B aortic dissection for preoperative planning. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Hyde, J., Khaksar, S., Lamont, W.,** 2021, 3D Modelling of Hand Movement in Children with Cerebral Palsy. Final Report, 43pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Abbott, L., Murray, I., Khaksar, S., Lamont, W.,** 2021, VR Guide Dog Training. Final Report, 67pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Andiambololonaharisoamalala, R., Lagain, A., Benedix, G., Lamont, W.,** 2021, Tool for visualising planetary and all-sky astronomical data. Final Report, 22pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Elsayed, H., Belton, D., Green, G., Woods, A., Adams, D.,** 2021, Creating 3D models of the Kyrenia shipwreck amphorae. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

2022

- **Dickson, C., Woods, A., Lamont, W., Wallis-Smith, D., Edwards, T.,** 2022, Fremantle Historical Panoramas Audio-Visual Tours. Final Report, 20pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Battersby, C., Woods, A., Li Tay, J., Lamont, W., Pearce, A.,** 2022, Fremantle Harbour Animated Panorama Project. Final Report, 24pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

- **Geerlings-Batt, J., Sun, Z., Tillett, C.,** 2022, Enhanced visualisation of normal anatomy with augmented reality superimposed on three-dimensional printed models. Final Report, 18pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Conradie, M., Sandry, E., Peaty, G., Tillett, C.,** 2022, VR Communicative Robots. Final Report, 26pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Mnahy, Y., Buzzacott, P., Perera, N., Lamont, W.,** 2022, Helping Developing World Diving Harvesters Avoid the Bends – A Humanitarian Project. Final Report, 28pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

2023

- **Bak, B., Abidin, C., Tillett, C.,** 2023, How Platforms See Influencers. Final Report, 23pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Delpech, K., Sun, Z., Bhandari, M., Tillett, C.,** 2023, Clinical value of virtual reality in pre-surgical planning of malignant hepatic tumours. Final Report, 22pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- **Natalotto, J., Sun, Z., Tillett, C., Jansen, S., Hodder, R., Hockley, J.,** 2023, Interactive 3D Virtual Reality Imaging of Abdominopelvic Sarcoma to Improve Surgical Planning. Final Report, 24pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

2.11 Citations

The number of publications that have been supported by the HIVE or cite the HIVE has been growing substantially.

The Curtin HIVE Google Scholar account is available at:

<https://scholar.google.com.au/citations?user=SYzbiegAAAAJ&hl=en>

Cited by

	All	Since 2018
Citations	1403	1325
h-index	20	18
i10-index	35	34

as of 27 July 2023

2.12 Awards

The HIVE has contributed to projects which have received the following awards:

2019

- **Joint Winner** - WA State Heritage awards - "Heritage Perth Weekend" for the "Heritage Tourism Product" category.
Curtin was a partner in the 2019 Heritage Perth Weekend through a presentation on the "Historical Panoramas Project" at the Old Perth Boys School.
- **Winner** - MAGNA (Museums and Galleries National Awards) - Research Category Level 4 - WA Museum, "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties". Curtin was a Chief Investigator on the ARC Linkage Roaring Forties project and lead of the visualisation theme.
- **Highly Commended** - MAGNA (Museums and Galleries National Awards) – Temporary or Travelling Exhibition Category. Level 4 - Australian National Maritime Museum, "James Cameron: Challenging the Deep".
An SEM image of HMAS Sydney (II) rusticles from the Sydney-Kormoran Project appears in the exhibition.

2020

- **Winner** - CurtinInnovation Award, Humanities category
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** – Lateral INCITE Awards, Peter Fillery Undergraduate Tertiary Student Project of the Year "3D Reconstruction of Abnormal Viscera" led by HIVE intern Dior Etherton

2021

- **Winner** - WA Heritage Awards, Interpretation Category
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Finalist** - WA Heritage Awards, Interpretation Category
OldPerth Project led by Andrew Woods
- **Winner** - National iAwards Merit Award for Not for Profit and Community Solution of the Year
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** - WA INCITE Awards Merit Award for Social Impact
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** - Planning Institute of Australia (WA) awards, Award for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Planning category
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** - Planning Institute of Australia (WA) awards, Technology & Digital Innovation for Planning Excellence category
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** - CurtinInnovation award, Humanities category
ViTools: learning difficult concepts in pharmacology - Dr Rima Caccetta, Associate Professor Lisa Tee, Associate Professor Francesco Mancini, Mr Jonathan Pillai, Mr Justin Owen, Associate Professor Aneesh Krishna, and Mr Matt Reed.
- **Awardee** - The 2021 Planetary Science Honours Prize (The academically outstanding student completing a planetary science project as part of the BSc(Science) (Honours) Geology Major) Honours thesis by student Wallace Maillot using ortho-mosaic of Barlangi granophyre, Yarrabubba generated by Daniel Adams, Curtin HIVE. Maillot, W.M.A., 2021, Petrogenesis of impact melts: Barlangi granophyre, Yarrabubba, Western Australia. Honours Thesis, Curtin University, 68 pp. Note that while Wallace completed his Honours in 2021 with flying colours, his thesis publication is 'on hold' for the time being because he has embarked on an upgrade to a Master of Research, for which his Honours research counts for the first year and he forgoes his Honours thesis. Also note that Wallace received a firstclass Honours for his thesis before upgrading.

2022

- **Winner** - Planning Institute of Australia National Awards, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Planning, Award for Planning Excellence
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** - ACS (Australian Computer Society) Digital Disruptors Award for ICT Service Transformation for the Digital Consumer (NFP/NGO)
The MissionsConnect project led by Reena Tiwari
- **Winner** – 2022 WA Heritage Awards, Interpretation Category
Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas exhibition
- **Finalist** - 2022 Australian Cardiovascular Alliance (ACvA) Excellence in Cardiovascular Research Game Changer Award
Ivan Lau, Curtin Student, Medical Imaging Science whose project was supported by the HIVE.
- **Awardee** - The Australasian Hydrographic Society Annual Education Award of \$3,500 AUD. "Daniel Adams is the 2022 recipient of the AHS Education Award. Daniel is an Australian citizen who is studying towards a Master of Philosophy - Computer Science at Curtin University, Australia on improving underwater photogrammetric 3D reconstruction processing of shipwreck sites."
"Reviewers noted that underwater imaging is relevant to hydrography while also covering a breadth of disciplines and that the complexity of undertaking this type of work cannot be underestimated. While Daniel's work focusses on processing improvements for 3D models to support maritime archaeology, our members may also be interested in how underwater photogrammetry can help us better understand change in other areas such as coral reefs and subsea infrastructure. Daniel is harnessing legacy datasets in his study sites and using newer processing technologies along with supercomputing power to bring greater understanding to the wreck areas chosen, as well as generating workflows that support others who wish to use underwater imaging in their own areas. The Panel enjoyed exploring some of the models Daniel has worked on that are available online, which we think is a fantastic way to share this work as it brings attention to hydrography, photogrammetric technology and the opportunities available to those that use it."

2023

- **Highly Commended** - Australian Museums and Galleries Association (AMAGA) awards. "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas exhibition" led by Andrew Woods, Curtin HIVE and WA Museum.
- **Awardee** - Global Voices World Health Assembly (WHA) Scholarship
Cleo Wee, who is studying a Bachelor of Medicine and Surgery at Curtin, will complete a Policy Fellowship and attend the World Health Assembly Conference in Geneva, Switzerland, as part of the scholarship, alongside other influential healthcare leaders and policy makers from around the world.

Engagement and Impact

Showcasing Curtin Research

**"I found this mind-blowing!
Absolutely mind-blowing!"
Leadership WA visit attendee**

3 Engagement and Impact

"Research engagement is the interaction between researchers and research end-users outside of academia, for the mutually beneficial transfer of knowledge, technologies, methods or resources. Research impact is the contribution that research makes to the economy, society, environment or culture, beyond the contribution to academic research." Engagement and Impact Assessment 2018-19, Australian Research Council.

<https://dataportal.arc.gov.au/EI/NationalReport/2018/pages/introduction/index.html?id=definitions>

Research supported by the HIVE has considerable engagement and impact. This section identifies the wide range of engagement and impact of HIVE supported research.

3.1 Media Coverage

- **8 Jul 2018:** BBC (UK) "The Sky at Night" full episode (30mins) "Outback Astronomy" featuring MWA, GLEAM, Steven Tingay, Natasha Hurley-Walker. Part filmed in the HIVE.
- **26 Jul 2018:** The West, Inside Cover "Shrink the Kids". (see Right →)
Audience 147,676, AUD 2,788

SHRINK THE KIDS

Experience the scientific version of classic 1989 film Honey, I Shrank the Kids at Curtin University's open day this weekend.

The Curtin HIVE project has harnessed the potential of virtual reality to allow students to digitally interact with chemicals at the atomic scale, which is a dramatic improvement on traditional ball-and-stick plastic molecule models.

Shrinking people to the size of atoms is just one of many activities taking place at the uni's Bentley campus on Sunday, from 10am to 4pm.

VR program prototype.

- **2 Aug 2018:** Media Release "New ARC centre works to improve productivity for the resources sector" (launched and photographed in the HIVE)
<https://news.curtin.edu.au/media-releases/new-arc-centre-works-improve-productivity-resources-sector/>

- **Aug 2018:** Curtin University News "The sweet spot: Gabriel Chocolate's focus on product position", <https://www.curtin.edu.au/news/sweet-spot-gabriel-chocolates-focus-product-position/>

- **1 Sep 2018:** Forge, Sydney “Global mindset puts Curtin at the forefront of change”

- **1 Sep 2018:** AIMA Newsletter, “The discovery and documentation of Australia’s first submarine HMAS AE1” (cover article) (below left)

- **14 Sep 2018:** Ten Daily, ‘Brought Our Men Home’: New Evidence Helps Solve Australia’s Oldest Naval Mystery, <https://tendaily.com.au/news/australia/a180914tue/brought-our-men-home-new-evidence-helps-solve-australias-oldest-naval-mystery-20180914>
- **14 Sep 2018:** Australian National Maritime Museum media release, “104 years on, Australian experts reveal new evidence behind WWI submarine HMAS AE1’s tragic loss” <https://www.medianet.com.au/releases/167567/> announcing the release of the survey report about the HMAS AE1 wrecksite.

- **14 Sep 2018:** The West Australian, "Submarine's hull imploded" (below)

Submarine's hull imploded

The last moments for 35 doomed submariners has been revealed for the first time.

Investigators have finally established how and why Australia's first E-class submarine was lost to the sea for more than a century.

A team of experts, led by retired rear-admiral Peter Briggs, will today mark the 104th anniversary with the release of a report detailing what went wrong.

They determined the entire crew died instantly at an unknown depth when

WWI Submarine AE1 and crew.

the forward pressure hull imploded in a diving accident.

"They would have known they were in trouble but they would not have even seen it

coming," Mr Briggs said. "It was a high-energy event — like a truck bomb going off in the control room."

The findings end claims the submarine was attacked.

AE1 was found in 300m of water off Duke of York Island near Rabaul in Papua New Guinea in December.

Investigators believe it was hunting a German steamer and had its torpedo tubes open when it descended on September 14, 1914. It was the first Allied sub lost in World War I.

Aaron Langmaid

- **14 Sep 2018:** Herald Sun, "War Sub Mystery Solved" by Aaron Langmaid. (below)

WAR SUB MYSTERY SOLVED

AARON LANGMAID

THE excruciating last moments for 35 doomed submariners has been revealed for the first time.

Investigators have finally established how and why Australia's first E-class submarine was lost to the sea for more than a century.

A team of experts, led by Victorian retired rear admiral Peter Briggs, will today mark the 104th anniversary with the release of a report detailing what went wrong.

They found the entire crew was killed instantly at an unknown depth when the forward pressure hull imploded as a result of a diving accident.

"They would have known they were in trouble, but they would not have even seen it coming," Mr Briggs said.

"It was a high energy event — like a truck bomb going off in the control room."

The findings end claims the submarine was attacked.

AE1 was found in 300m of water off the Duke of York

Island, near Rabaul, Papua New Guinea, in December.

It was considered the most significant discovery in Australian maritime history and used the same state of the art technology rolled out to find missing plane MH370.

Investigators believe AE1 was on the hunt for a German steamer and had its torpedo tubes open when it descended on September 14, 1914.

It was the first Allied submarine loss of WWI.

Analysis of the imagery

showed a critical ventilation valve in the hull was partially open, allowing water to flood the engine room.

The report was done by experts from the Australian National Maritime Museum, Find AE1 Ltd, Curtin University, and independents from Australia and Britain.

Mr Briggs said finding AE1 after more than a century offered hope to the families of passengers aboard the

Malaysian Airlines flight.

He said the plane was likely sitting on the ocean floor about 100km further south of the existing search area off Western Australia.

"I have no doubt if they were looking in the right area they would find it," he said.

ANSWERS AT LAST, PAGES 22-23

Retired navy admiral Peter Briggs led the exploration team that helped locate HMAS AE1. Picture: JASON EDWARDS

- **14 Sep 2018:** 9 News online, "Revealed at last, why HMAS AE1 sank without trace at the start of World War One with 35 sailors on board" <https://www.9news.com.au/2018/09/14/12/24/140918-hmas-ae1>
- **17 Sep 2018:** Australian National Maritime Museum website, "Solving Australia's most enduring naval mystery" <https://stories.anmm.gov.au/ae1-found/>
- **18 Sep 2018:** NZ Herald, "Mystery surrounding World War I Kiwi sailor's death solved a century on" NZ Herald https://www.nzherald.co.nz/nz/news/article.cfm?c_id=1&objectid=12127240
- **24 Sep 2018:** Navy Daily "AE1 remembered 104 years on" <http://news.navy.gov.au/en/Sep2018/Fleet/4854>

- **24 Sep 2018:** Australian Mining Review “ARC training centre to improve productivity” (see Right →)
- **24 Sep 2018:** Navy Daily “AE1 remembered 104 years on” <http://news.navy.gov.au/en/Sep2018/Fleet/4854/AE1-remembered-104-years-on.htm#.XFcQ3lwzaTF>
- **10 Oct 2018:** Navy News Sydney “Found and remembered” “Coinciding with the 104th anniversary, a new report issued by the Australian National Maritime Museum reveals new evidence into the circumstances surrounding AE1’s demise. The report was compiled by a team of experts from the museum, Find AE1 Ltd, Curtin University, as well as independent experts.”
- **Nov 2018:** Southern Gazette, Perth “Lost but not forgotten” audience 30,326, AUD 1,162

ARC training centre to improve productivity

WA
A NEW government-funded Australian Research Council (ARC) Industrial Transformational Training Centre will be built at Curtin University, WA that will use data science to transform asset maintenance for the Australian resources sector.

The centre, led by Curtin, will be run in partnership with the University of Western Australia, CSIRO, the University of Adelaide, and industry partners Alcoa, BHP, Roy Hill, CORE Innovation Hub and the Minerals Research Institute of WA.

ABC Training Centre for Transforming Maintenance through Data Science director Professor Andrew Rohl said maintenance practices had changed little in the last 20 years, and were due for a digital overhaul which will see new developments in computational methods, statistics, artificial intelligence and more.

4 NEWS

www.communitynews.com.au

November 6, 2018

Lost but not forgotten

Nadia Budihardjo

THE public is invited to view a 3D digital re-creation of Australia’s first submarine, which sunk more than a century ago, for the 100th anniversary of Armistice Day at John Curtin Gallery this Friday.

HMAS AE1 was sunk in September 1914 and the wreck was found near Duke of York islands off the coast of Papua New Guinea, in December 2017.

Curtin University Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch started a research project to map the wreck of *AE1* following a survey in April this year.

HIVE Manager Andrew Woods said the survey was conducted with an underwater vehicle to retrieve 8000 images of the wreck.

“We used an advanced image processing technique for the 3D model of the wreck site,” he said.

“This technique allows visualisation of the wreck as a complete item and illustrates what happened on that eventful day in 1914.”

Dr Woods said the *AE1* was the first vessel lost in World War I.

“There will be display panels on the history of *AE1* and on the research expedition and photographs from the wreck itself,” he said.

Curtin HIVE manager Dr Andrew Woods and John Curtin Gallery director Chris Malcolm with the digital recreation of Australia’s first submarine. **Picture: David Baylis** d488265

“The work we’ve been doing is helping to answer and illustrate what happened.”

The 3D recreation of the wreck will be on display as part of the Warship exhibition launch after the commemorative ceremony.

The exhibition at John Curtin Gallery continues until December 2.

THE ESSENTIALS

WHAT: Commemorative ceremony of 100th anniversary of Armistice Day and Warship exhibition launch

WHEN: Friday, November 9

TIME: 10.45am - 11.30am

WHERE: John Curtin Gallery, Building 200A, Curtin University, Kent Street

TICKETS: Free but register at www.eventbrite.com.au/e/day-of-remembrance-launch-of-warship-registration-51451163816

- **20 Nov 2018:** The Canning Times, Perth “Pages of history salvaged in art”. Audience 24,899, AUD 1,957
- **30 Jan 2019:** VC’s Communications “Chief of Navy visits Curtin”
- **28 Feb 2019:** The West Australian, Inside Cover.
- **Mar 2019:** VC’s Communications “Labor’s election commitment to Curtin HIVE”
- **19 Mar 2019:** VC’s Communications “Moving Pictures launch”
- **16 May 2019:** Curtin University Media release “Art and research intersect as Curtin wins national museum award”, Western Australian Museum also won a MAGNA for its research project titled ‘Shipwrecks of the Roaring 40s’.
- **20 May 2019:** VC’s Communications “John Curtin Gallery successes”

- **28 Jun 2019:** Digital Tower at Yagan Square, XR:WA conference promotion. Curtin University was a sponsor.
- **1 Jul 2019:** BN Technology "Its reality, but not as you know it"
- **Winter 2019 issue:** WA Works: Supply Chain and Major Project News. "The Big Picture". HMAS AE1 project featured on page 6 and 7.

- **3 Jul 2019:** Channel 7, Today Tonight "Watch how virtual reality is helping Perth man Gary Barnes move again after a workplace accident left him a quadriplegic"
<https://www.facebook.com/TodayTonight/videos/320782038802552/>

- **4 Jul 2019:** 9 News Perth, 4pm and 6pm bulletins, "Space Race". HIVE hosted an announcement by @CurtinSpaceSci which resulted in a story featuring Professor Phil Bland and his team.

- **4 Jul 2019:** 10 News First Perth "Regular Segment: Around the Town with Beau Pearson, Channel 10 Correspondent" audience 46,630, AUD 6,970
<https://www.facebook.com/10NewsPer/videos/503121433561270/>

- **4 Jul 2019:** Australian Research Council, Announcement of Funding - ARC Linkage Projects scheme, Australian Government, "Photogrammetric Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences"
<https://www.arc.gov.au/news-publications/media/network-messages/announcement-funding-arc-linkage-projects-scheme-July19>
- **5 Jul 2019:** Channel 7, Today Tonight "A virtual reality technology produced by Curtin University is helping an Australian man learn to move again after suffering from quadriplegia following an accident at work". Audience 77,655, AUD 30,148
- **12 Jul 2019:** Mirage News, Curtin virtual reality research opens up new worlds at XR:WA.
<https://www.miragenews.com/curtin-virtual-reality-research-opens-up-new-worlds-at-xr-wa/>
- **15 Jul 2019:** VC's Communications "XR Welcome reception"
- **17 Jul 2019:** Canning Times Community, Innovation meets education at Open Day,
<https://www.communitynews.com.au/canning-times/news/innovation-meets-education-at-open-day/>
- **17 Jul 2019:** AZO Optics, Curtin Virtual Reality Research Opens up New Worlds at XR:WA.
<https://www.azooptics.com/News.aspx?newsID=24427>
- **9 Aug 2019:** ABC Perth TV News - NASA Scientist Dr Mitch Schulte was interviewed at the HIVE by ABC TV News presenter James McHale about the NASA Mars 2020 Rover mission which will launch in July 2020 and land on Mars on 18 February 2021.

- **5 Sep 2019:** Curtin Media Release “Historical Panoramas project further opens window on Perth’s past” <https://news.curtin.edu.au/media-releases/historical-panoramas-project-further-opens-window-on-perths-past/>
- **5 Sep 2019:** 6PR radio interview “A Look Into Our Past” with Simon Beaumont for Historical Panoramas Stage 2 launch. Audience 14,000 AUD 1,078 <https://www.6pr.com.au/podcast/a-look-into-our-past/> [podcast]
- **5 Sep 2019:** Mirage News “Historical Panoramas project further opens window on Perth’s past” Audience 190,881 <https://www.miragenews.com/historical-panoramas-project-further-opens-window-on-perth-s-past/>
- **5 Sep 2019:** National Tribune “Historical Panoramas project further opens window on Perth’s past” Audience 188,792 <https://www.nationaltribune.com.au/historical-panoramas-project-further-opens-window-on-perth-s-past/>
- **12 Sep 2019:** Canning Examiner “A glimpse of how we lived” <https://view.publitas.com/examiner-newspapers/canning-examiner-newspapers-4th-september/page/2-3> (see Right →)

Historical panorama taken from Perth Esplanade and Elizabeth Quay.

A glimpse of how we lived

By **GERALDINE ALPHONSE**

If you are passionate about history and want to have a sneaky look at the old Perth, make sure you don't miss the Historical Panoramas tour website.

The award-winning Curtin University research project holds an online collection of interactive images of historical views of Perth and Fremantle to provide an even more stunning insight into how the cities have changed over the past 150 years.

Project Supervisor and Curtin Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch manager Dr Andrew Woods said the project's website had more

than doubled in size and now featured more than 30 new or updated wide-angle panoramic views dating as far back as 1858. “Highlights of the new site include the view from the Perth Town Hall tower, which has been upgraded to a full 360 degree view as seen in 1885, 1906, 1925 and 2016,” he said.

Originally launched in 2016, the project has already been recognised at the 2017 Western Australian Heritage Awards and received a framed certificate and an engraved medalion from The Perth Mint in recognition of its contribution to Western Australia's heritage.

To go on a historical tour go to www.historicalpanoramas.com.au

- **12 Sep 2019:** Create – the Journal of Engineers Australia, "Deep Dive" / "Seeing clearly", (Cover Article), 11 pages, AUD 52,540.
<https://search.informit.org/doi/pdf/10.3316/informit.906065511533282>

- **12 Sep 2019:** Create digital magazine website, Engineers Australia, "Bold vision: Andrew Woods is using virtual reality to explore the most distant frontiers" <https://www.createdigitalmagazine.org.au/bold-vision-andrew-woods-is-using-virtual-reality-to-explore-the-most-distant-frontiers/>
- **25 Sep 2019:** SpinalCure Australia media release "SpinalCure Australia supports six new research projects" <https://www.spinalcure.org.au/spinalcure-australia-supports-six-new-research-projects/>
- **27 Sep 2019:** Today Tonight, Channel 7 Perth "High-Tech Window" (Historical Panoramas project Stage 2). Audience 109,000, AUD 18,504 <https://www.facebook.com/TodayTonight/videos/2489456864618423/>

- **25 Oct 2019:** Kalgoorlie Miner "Shipwrecks lit up for exhibition" <https://www.pressreader.com/australia/kalgoorlie-miner/20191025/page/8>

Shipwrecks lit up for exhibition

Kalgoorlie's maritime relations with the world are being celebrated in a new photographic exhibition opening this weekend at the German Cultural Centre for modern and contemporary art.

The exhibition, titled 'Shipwrecks lit up for exhibition', is a collaboration between the German Cultural Centre and the Kalgoorlie Miner. It features a collection of historical photographs and maps that tell the story of the city's maritime history.

The exhibition is held at the German Cultural Centre, located at 100 Sturt Street, Kalgoorlie. It is open from Friday, October 25, to Sunday, October 27, from 10am to 5pm.

For more information, visit www.gcc.kalgoorlie.com.au

A remotely operated vehicle.

- **26 Oct 2019:** Scoop magazine "Deep Light: Illuminating The Wrecks Of Sydney And Kormoran" <https://scoop.com.au/perth-wa/guides/arts-events/kalgoorlie/events/listing/deep-light-illuminating-the-wrecks-of-sydney-and-kormoran/>
- **29 Oct 2019:** VC's Communications "Cisco and Curtin signing ceremony"
- **31 Oct 2019:** Today Tonight, Channel 7 Perth. "Curtin University is unveiling a table that can project a hologram" audience 150,000, AUD 25,608 <https://www.facebook.com/TodayTonight/videos/448455812451359/>

- **1 Nov 2019:** Curtin Media Release “Hologram Table takes Curtin research to new heights and depths” <https://news.curtin.edu.au/media-releases/hologram-table-takes-curtin-research-to-new-heights-and-depths/>
- **1 Nov 2019:** Mirage News “Hologram Table takes Curtin research to new heights, and depths” AUD 2,128 <https://www.miragenews.com/hologram-table-takes-curtin-research-to-new-heights-and-depths/>
- **1 Nov 2019:** National Tribune “Hologram Table takes Curtin research to new heights, and depths” AUD 246,572 <https://www.nationaltribune.com.au/hologram-table-takes-curtin-research-to-new-heights-and-depths/>
- **Nov 2019:** iTnews “Curtin Uni adds an interactive Hologram Table” AUD 2,306 <https://www.itnews.com.au/news/curtin-uni-adds-an-interactive-hologram-table-533324>
- **Nov 2019:** Channel News Australia “Hologram Table Allows 3D Objects To Spring Into Life” Audience 97,557 AUD 862 <https://www.channelnews.com.au/hologram-table-allows-3d-objects-to-spring-into-life/>
- **12 Nov 2019:** AARNET Case Study “Visualising the story of Australia’s largest ever naval loss” <https://www.aarnet.edu.au/case-studies/visualising-the-story-of-australias-largest-ever-naval-loss>
- **14 Nov 2019:** RTRFM radio program “The Mag: Hologram Table” Dr Andrew Woods was interviewed live on air by presenter Jorja Keay.
- **20 Nov 2019:** Curtin News Story “Reactive realities: VR in the chemistry classroom” <https://news.curtin.edu.au/stories/reactive-realities-vr-in-the-chemistry-classroom/>
- **23 Nov 2019:** Fremantle Herald, Perth “Wave of support” audience 69,058, AUD 881
- **13 Jan 2020:** FOX News “Sunken US WWII plane revealed in stunning seabed images” <https://www.foxnews.com/science/sunken-wwii-plane-revealed-in-stunning-seabed-images>
The new 6000m cameras were used on this expedition.

Other coverage of this story:

- <https://www.geek.com/news/wreck-of-us-wwii-plane-revealed-in-detailed-images-1816193/>
- <https://scripps.ucsd.edu/news/new-detail-deep-sea-wreckage-find>
- <https://www.themorningbulletin.com.au/news/eerie-images-of-plane-at-bottom-of-ocean/3920410/>
- <https://www.warhistoryonline.com/news/grumman-tbf.html>
- <http://www.sandiegometro.com/2020/01/daily-business-report-jan-13-2020/>
- **2 Apr 2020:** Gizmodo “More Of Australia’s Most Intriguing, Unexplained Phenomena” <https://www.gizmodo.com.au/2019/10/more-of-australias-most-intriguing-unexplained-phenomena/>
- **23 Jun 2020:** 6PR “Exploring WA’s amazing shipwrecks – without getting wet” audience 274, AUD 15,946 <https://www.6pr.com.au/podcast/exploring-was-amazing-shipwrecks-without-getting-wet/>

- **24 Jun 2020:** Spatial Source “Virtual history: project recreates shipwrecks in 3D” audience 892, AUD 242 <https://www.spatialsource.com.au/virtual-history-project-recreates-shipwrecks-in-3d/>
- **30 Jun 2020:** VC’s Communications “Curtin embarks on research project to recreate shipwrecks in 3D”
- **June 2020:** The HIVE featured in the 2020 Research Rumble video

- **August 2020:** The HIVE features in Curtin’s new marketing campaign video “Change is Here” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uOUqJijcvdq&feature=youtu.be>

- **14 Sep 2020:** 7 News Perth “There’s a powerful new weapon in Perth medicine” <https://www.facebook.com/7NEWSPerth/posts/10157926225354072>

- **31 Mar 2021:** Curtin University Media Release “Perth’s visual past on show at Curtin/State Library initiative - OldPerth”
- **31 Mar 2021:** ABC Radio Perth 2.24pm “OldPerth” audience 16,000, AUD 535
- **31 Mar 2021:** ABC Radio Perth 3.27pm “OldPerth” audience 18,000, AUD 2,031

- **31 Mar 2021:** ABC News Perth TV 7.10pm "OldPerth" audience 14,000, AUD 1,530

- **7 Apr 2021:** West Australian, Perth "OLDPERTH HISTORICAL IMAGES AND VR EXPERIENCE" audience 135,996, AUD 171,652
- **11 Apr 2021:** 6PR Interview "OldPerth website" audience 7,000, AUD 1,341
- **13 Apr 2021:** VC's Communications "OldPerth website"
- **19 Apr 2021:** Curtin FM "Interview with Associate Professor Andrew Woods, Manager, Curtin HIVE, about the Old Perth website developed by Curtin HIVE" AUD 1,142
- **21 Apr 2021:** Canning Examiner "Take a trip back in time" audience 29,603, AUD 738
- **4 May 2021:** Curtin FM interview "Associate Professor Andrew Woods about the launch of the OldPerth website"
- **2 Aug 2021:** VC's Communications "WA Incite Awards"
- **25 Oct 2021:** VC's Communications "School of Education Research Showcase and Partnerships"
- **17 Dec 2021:** AV Technology Magazine "Satellite MLS powers Curtin University HIVE"
- **21 Jan 2022:** VC's Communications "MissionsConnect wins WA Awards for Planning Excellence"
- **15 Feb 2022:** AV Technology Magazine "HIVE Mind - AV technology" <https://av.technology/case-studies/hive-mind>
- **24 Mar 2022:** Projector Central "Curtin University's HIVE Installs Digital Projection Satellite MLS System" AUD 108,760
<https://www.projectorcentral.com/Curtin-University-Digital-Projection-Satellite.htm>
- **2 May 2022:** Installation International "Satellite Modular Laser System takes centre stage" AUD 181,366 <https://www.installation-international.com/ise-daily/satellite-modular-laser-system-takes-centre-stage>
- **20 Jul 2022:** Connected Magazine "Good Things Come To Those Who Wait..." AUD 42,236 <https://connectedmag.com.au/good-things-come-to-those-who-wait/>
- **20 Jul 2022:** Canning Examiner, Perth "'Black Beauty' could hold the secrets to Mars" Audience 22,000, AUD 1,108
- **23 Sep 2022:** VC's Communications "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas"
- **14 Oct 2022:** VC's Communications "US Ambassador visits Space Science and Technology Centre"
- **1 Oct 2022:** PerthNow Fremantle, Fremantle "Fremantle's changing face"
- **25 Oct 2022:** Australian Photography "New exhibition shows changing face of Fremantle" audience 7,162, AUD 401
<https://www.australianphotography.com/news/new-exhibition-shows-changing-face-of-fremantle>
- **2 Nov 2022:** West Australian "Fremantle then and now in spectacular exhibition" audience 992, AUD 1,675 <https://thewest.com.au/travel/fremantle-then-and-now-in-spectacular-exhibition-c-8723056>

- **19 Nov 2022:** Release of large 3D model of *Kormoran* engine room hull to commemorate 81st Anniversary of the loss of HMAS Sydney (II) and HSK Kormoran

7 News (National)

9 News Perth

10 News Perth

- **22 Nov 2022:** Geraldton Guardian, Geraldton "New images put Kormoran's fate in perspective". Audience 3,673, AUD 2,362
- **23 Nov 2022:** Midwest Times & Northern Guardian, Geraldton "Kormoran images revealed". Audience 20,730, AUD 951
- **2 Dec 2022:** VC's Communications "2022 Western Australian Heritage Awards"
- **14 Dec 2022:** Canning Examiner, Perth "Shark fins origin defined". Audience 22,000, AUD 836
- **12 Mar 2023:** 6PR, "Remember When", radio interview with Harvey Deegan, Andrew Woods discusses "SS Bonnie Dundee shipwreck 3D model"
- **24 Mar 2023:** West Australian, Perth "Presentation All ages: OldPerth: Navigating Perth's history through the State Library of WA's historical photograph collection". Audience 349,000, AUD 12,535
- **26 May 2023:** VC's Communications "Australian Museums and Galleries Association Awards"
- **7 June 2023:** Curtin FM Radio interview with Jenny Seaton, Andrew Woods and Daniel Adams discuss "SS Duckenfield shipwreck 3D model release"
- **13 June 2023:** Western Australian of the Year Awards 2023 - John Barrington - Finalist Business Category. This video screened during the award ceremony.

3.2 Conference Presentations

This section lists presentations at national and international conferences that do not have an accompanying published manuscript.

2018

- **Palmer, R.**, "Metrics for scanning and interpretation of Maritime Panoramic Imagery" IEEE VIS 2018 conference, Berlin, October 29-31, 2018.
- **Tan, S.** (2018), 'Mapping student engagement with 360 degree video content through user-annotations and analytic visualisations'. Paper presentation at Media & Learning 2018: Video in Higher Education Conference in Leuven, Belgium, 14-15 June 2018.
- **Hunter, J., Woods, A.** (2018) 'Imaging Australia's First Naval Loss: The 2018 Archaeological Survey of Submarine AE1' Archaeology of War conference, Australian National Maritime Museum, 22-23 June 2018.
- **Won, M., Tang, K. S., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R.**, (2018) "Using interactive Immersive Virtual Reality to enhance students' visualisation of complex molecules" 25th IUPAC International Conference on Chemistry Education (ICCE2018), 10-14 July 2018, Sydney.
- **Woods, A., Hollick, J.** (2018) "Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction Processing of the wreck of HMAS AE1" OzViz 2018, UNSW, Sydney. <https://sites.google.com/site/ozvizworkshop/ozviz-2018/program>

2019

- **Adams, D., Tri Tai Pham, S., Watts, K., Ramakrishnan, S., Ackland, E., Tran Ly, H., Hollick, J., Woods, A.** "Development of a Camera Based Projection Mapping System for Non-Flat Surfaces" Stereoscopic Displays and Applications 2019, California, USA. <http://www.stereoscopic.org/2019/index.html> [presented, manuscript in published proceedings]
- **Ciccarelli, M.** (July 2019). Panel: VR & AR in Healthcare. Invited talk at XR:WA.
- **Woods, A.** (July 2019). Workshop: Photogrammetry in Immersive. Invited talk at XR:WA.

2021

- **Woods, A., Elsayed, H., Adams D., Green J., Belton, D.** (2021). Creating 3D models of the Kyrenia shipwreck cargo. Australasian Institute for Maritime Archaeology, Townsville, QLD. www.aima-underwater.org.au
- **Adams D., Woods, H., Green J.** (2021). Photogrammetric 3D reconstruction of the Santo Antonio de Tanna shipwreck (1698) from legacy photography. Australasian Institute for Maritime Archaeology, Townsville, QLD. www.aima-underwater.org.au
- **Ciccarelli, M., Morris, S.** (June, 2021). Virtual Reality as a Viable Physical Rehabilitation Tool. Invited talk at the Immerse Australia, online.
- **Won, M.** (April, 2021). Future of VR: VR in education. Research Rumble, Curtin University, Perth, WA.
- **Won, M.** (October, 2021). Immersive VR for collaborative interactive science learning. School of Education Research Showcase, Curtin University, Perth, WA.
- **Won, M.** (September, 2021). Collaborative interactive science learning in immersive VR: Design for learning. Invited talk at the Immerse Australia, online.
- **Won, M.** (August, 2021). Immersive virtual reality for collaborative interactive science learning. Invited talk at the Future of Work Institute, Curtin University.
- **Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., Tsai, C.-C., Ungu, D., & Matovu, H.** (March, 2021). Using immersive virtual reality to enhance students' learning of science. Invited talk at a quarterly meeting of Royal Australian Chemical Institute, Perth, WA.
- **Matovu, H., Ungu, D., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (September, 2021). Walking into a protein molecule together: Students' exploration of an enzyme-substrate interaction in immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the Australian Conference on Science and Mathematics Education (ACSME), Online.
- **Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (September, 2021). Interacting with molecules using physical models, computer simulation, and

immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the Australian Conference on Science and Mathematics Education (ACSME), Online.

- **Matovu, H., Ungu, D., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (July, 2021). Sweet and bitter tasting forms of a substance: Exploring the difference in immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Science Teacher Association of Western Australia (STAWA), Perth, Australia.
- **Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (July, 2021). Dive into a snowflake at the molecular level with physical models, computer simulation, and immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Science Teacher Association of Western Australia (STAWA), Perth, Australia.
- **Matovu, H., Ungu, D., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (July, 2021). What physical models and textbook illustrations don't show us: Students' exploration of hydrogen bonding in immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association, online.
- **Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (July, 2021). Educational affordances of physical models, computer simulation, and immersive virtual reality in improving students' chemistry learning. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association, online.
- **Won, M., Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (July, 2021). Design and evaluation of science learning activities in immersive virtual reality through an immersive learning framework. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association, online.

2022

- **Matovu, H., Ungu, D., Won, M., Treagust, D., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (July, 2022). Exploring the chemistry of taste substance in immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association (ASERA), Perth, Australia.
- **Ungu, D., Won, M., Matovu, H., Treagust, D., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (June, 2022). Students' interactions in immersive virtual reality to learn the formation of snowflakes. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association (ASERA), Perth, Australia.
- **Won, M., Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Treagust, D., Mocerino, M., Tsai, C.-C., & Tasker, R.** (June, 2022). Collaborative science learning in immersive virtual reality: It takes more than a couple of VR headsets. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association (ASERA), Perth, Australia.
- **Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Won, M., Treagust, D., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (April, 2022). Embodied actions and exploratory talk for learning chemistry within an immersive virtual reality environment. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Education Research Association (AERA), Online.
- **Matovu, H., Won, M., Ungu, D., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (March, 2022). Progression of students' interactions over three immersive virtual reality learning activities. Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), hybrid-online and Vancouver, Canada.
- **Treagust, D. F., Ungu, D., Won, M., Matovu, H., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (March, 2022). Comparative analysis on the impact of scaffolding on students' interactions within immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), hybrid-online and Vancouver, Canada.
- **Ungu, D., Won, M., Matovu, H., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (March, 2022). Students' construction of learning activities to understand the formation of snowflakes with three different modes. Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), hybrid-online and Vancouver, Canada.
- **Won, M., Ungu, D., Matovu, H., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (March, 2022). An analytical framework for spatial analysis of students' interactions in immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), hybrid-online and Vancouver, Canada.

2023

- **Matovu, H., Won, M., Hernandez-Alvarado, R. B., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Ungu, D., Tsai, C.-C., & Tasker, R.** (June, 2023). Analysis of students' social interactions while learning science concepts in collaborative immersive virtual reality. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association (ASERA), Cairns, Queensland.
- **Ungu, D., Won, M., Hernandez-Alvarado, R. B., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Matovu, H., Tasker, R., & Tsai, C.-C.** (June, 2023). Students' perceptions of immersive virtual reality to learn chemistry. Paper presented at the annual conference of the Australasian Science Education Research Association (ASERA), Cairns, Queensland.
- **Won, M., Matovu, H., Ungu, D., Treagust, D. F., Tsai, C.-C., Mocerino, M., & Tasker, R.** (April, 2023). Students' collaborative interactions and evaluations of immersive virtual reality to learn and explain science. Paper presented at the annual conference of the American Educational Research Association (AERA), Chicago, USA.
- **Matovu, H., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Ungu, D., Tsai, C.-C., & Tasker, R.** (April, 2023). Influence of an immersive virtual reality experience on students' understanding of the shape of snowflakes. Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), Chicago, USA.
- **Ungu, D., Won, M., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Matovu, H., Tsai, C.-C., & Tasker, R.** (April, 2023). How do chemistry students bridge macro-micro scale with magnetic models and immersive virtual reality? Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), Chicago, USA.
- **Won, M., Matovu, H., Ungu, D., Treagust, D. F., Tsai, C.-C., Mocerino, M., & Tasker, R.** (April, 2023). Social interactions in immersive virtual reality: How students negotiate and contribute to learn science. Paper presented at the annual conference of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching (NARST), Chicago, USA.

3.3 VIP Visitors

2018

- **Jul:** "Science Your Future Competition" winners event with Indonesian Consulate General, hosted by Prof Simon Leunig
- **Aug:** Australian Research Council August Funding Announcements of \$180M in grants including \$10.3M to Curtin. Guests included the Hon Simon Birmingham Minister for Education and Training, and Professor Sue Thomas ARC CEO
- **Oct:** visitors from Mindaroo Foundation with Ian Callahan
- signing of agreement between CISCO and Curtin. Curtin VC and CISCO Vice-President.

2019

- **Jan:** Visit by Chief of Navy to see HMAS AE1, Sydney and Kormoran projects.
- **Feb:** visit by Jeff Simmons, ONRG (US Office of Naval Research Global)
- visit by Commodore Ivan Ingham, COMFLOT (Commodore of the Flotilla), Royal Australian Navy
- Pre-election funding announcement in the HIVE by Tanya Plibersek, deputy leader of the Federal Opposition, Australian Labor Party, and Hannah Beazley, Labor candidate for Swan.
- **Mar:** visit by Manager, Kalgoorlie Visitor Centre hosted by University Advancement)
- **Apr:** Visualisation event for Anglo American, "FUTURESMART MINING OPEN FORUM: DISCOVERY UNDER COVER - STIMULUS VISIT". Four presenters: Dr Uwe Woessner, HLRS, Uni of Stuttgart; Don Pridmore, HiSeis; Ben McKinley, CIRA; Andrew Woods, Curtin HIVE.
- visit by Karen Andrews MP, Federal Minister for Industry, Science & Technology; and Ian Goodenough MP hosted by Chris Moran
- **May:** Submarine Institute of Australia 2019 SubSTEC Conference Launch including minister Paul Papalia
- Veronica Dobner General Manager Kalgoorlie Boulder Visitors Centre and John Walker CEO City of Kalgoorlie Boulder – hosted by Curtin Advancement
- **July:** Mr Richard Sowada Festival Director, Revelation Perth International Film Festival, Hon. Minister David Templeman MLA - Welcome XR Reception for XR:WA conference

- **Aug:** Hosted visit from CTO of Mitsubishi Heavy Industries (Japan) with Andrew Bell (ROC) and Alec Duncan (CMST)
- ABC TV filming with NASA Mars Rover Program Scientist Dr Mitch Schulte
- **Sep:** Presentation of Cultural Healing VR projects to Department of Communities by Reena Tiwari
- **Nov:** Hosted visit by Dutch Ambassador Marion Derckx and Dutch Honorary Consul Mr Anthony Willinge
- hosted visit by Damian Shephard, Director, State Records Office of WA with Leisa Gibbons

2020

- **Jan:** hosted visit by Alan Good, Chairman, Feilman Foundation along with members of the board.
- **Feb:** hosted visit by Fiona Dowse appointed WA's most senior officer role in the RAAF, succeeding Brett Dowsing
- **Apr:** hosted visit by Steve Coughlan CEO of Byrnedcut
- **Jul:** hosted visit by Tim Day and Kate Osborn from BHP
- hosted visit by Governor Kim Beazley

2021

- **Feb:** hosted visit by Deputy Head of Mission at the Netherlands embassy Erik de Feijter along with staff
- **Mar:** hosted visit by Prof Emily Hilder from DST
- **Apr:** hosted visit by Mark Stewart, President, East Fremantle Football Club
- **May:** hosted visit by Richard Johnson, Director, Infinitive Group
- hosted visit by Nick Hogan, Air Commodore, Director General Space Domain Review
- hosted visit by Enrico Palermo, Head of Australian Space Agency
- **Jun:** hosted visit by Aleksey Pavlovsky, Ambassador of the Russian Federation to the Commonwealth of Australia
- hosted visiting delegation from Development WA with Kelli Howell (Senior Development Manager) and David Tomasich (Manager of Industrial) giving presentations
- hosted visit by WA Defence Advocate Rear Admiral (Rtd) Raydon Gates
- hosted visit by Prof Jason Scholz (CEO Trusted Autonomous Systems) and team
- hosted visit by Hon. Minister Roger Cook MLA minister for Science
- **Aug:** hosted visit by Hon. Minister David Scaife MLA, WA Labor Member for Cockburn and Acting Speaking Member of the Economics and Industry Standing Committee
- **Oct:** hosted visit by BHP executives Brandon Craig (Western Australian Iron Ore Asset President) and Meath Hammond (Head of Corporate Affairs Western Australia)
- **Nov:** hosted visit by Hon. Minister Don Punch, minister for Innovation and ICT

2022

- **Jan:** hosted visit by Hon. Minister Stephen Dawson MLC minister for Aboriginal Affairs
- **Jun:** hosted visit by Dale Furse (Chief Operating Officer) and Steve McGlynn (First Assistant Director-General People, Property and Legal) from the Australian Signals Directorate
- hosted visit by Governor Kim Beazley
- **Aug:** hosted visit by Dr Katerina Agostino (Chief, Human and Decision Sciences) and Prof Emily Hilder (Chief, Platforms) from DSTG
- hosted visit by Commodore Ivan Ingham
- hosted visit by Air Vice-Marshal Cath Roberts (Commander, Space Command)
- **Oct:** hosted visit by U.S. Ambassador Caroline Kennedy and U.S. Consul General Siriana Nair
- hosted visit by Prime Minister Anthony Albanese
- hosted visit by Aude Vignelles (CTO, Australian Space Agency)
- **Nov:** hosted visit by Dr. Stuart Milner (President, SMILNERS, Inc)
- **Dec:** hosted visit by Vijay Anand (CEO, iTNT Hub in Tamil Nadu)

2023

- **Mar:** hosted visit by Julie Stanley (COO, Veris)
- hosted visit by Commodore Stewart Dunne (AHO)
- **Apr:** hosted visit by Dr Henry Throop (Program Scientist, NASA)

- hosted visit by Nathan Quadros (Head of Digital Strategy, Veris)
- **May:** hosted visit by Catherine Clark (CEO, SLWA)
- **Jun:** hosted visit by Dave West (President of Asia Pacific, Japan, and Greater China, CISCO)

The Australian Prime Minister Anthony Albanese visits Curtin University and the HIVE on 21 October 2022. (Front L-R) Professor Phil Bland; Madeline King, Minister for Resources; Prime Minister Anthony Albanese; Professor Chris Moran; Zaneta Mascarenhas, Member for Swan. Photo Credit: Ezra Alcantra

3.4 HIVE Public Events

HIVE public events serve multiple purposes: foster the growth of a community of researchers interested in and active in visualisation, share knowledge and education about visualisation topics, and raise the profile of Curtin, the HIVE and visualisation amongst a wide audience.

2018

- **7 Jul:** NAIDOC week event viewing of Healing Centres (MissionsConnect) visualisation project in the HIVE (Saturday)
- **19 Jul:** BBC's The Sky at Night featuring the Murchison Radio-astronomy Observatory and Curtin HIVE
- **27 Jul:** Pelagios LAMLOD - Landscapes Art Models Linked Open Data workshop/conference hosted by Erik Champion. ~30 attendees.
- **29 Jul:** Curtin Open Day – open exhibition style display of various HIVE supported research projects across the day
- **6 Aug:** Optus-Curtin Partnership Launch
- **16 Aug:** Presentation of the 2018 ANZAAS Medal to Professor Kliti Grice
- **24 Aug:** CMST Seminar: Shipwreck reconstruction processing – HMAS Sydney (II), HKS Kormoran, and HMAS AE1
- **29 Aug:** Curtin Alumnus Dr Tom Shannon, Vicon two presentations in the HIVE
- **25 Sep:** Researchers & Educators Forum 2018
- **9 Oct:** evening event for local and overseas staff from Fugro Survey – presented work on AE1, Sydney and Kormoran.
- **20 Oct:** Historical Panoramas presentation at Old Perth Boys School for Perth Heritage Weekend
- **23 Oct:** signing of agreement between CISCO and Curtin. Curtin VC and CISCO Vice-President.
- **11 Dec:** Technical Presentation by Prof. Nick Holliman: Automating Data Visualization: Improving human comprehension of 3D data and its uncertainty
- **12 Dec:** Workshop by Prof. Nick Holliman: Visualization Tools and Techniques

2019

- **15 Feb:** HIVE Intern Showcase (full day event)
- **14 Mar:** "Moving Pictures" WA Launch event
- **25 Mar:** Research Rumble in the HIVE - 3D Imaging of Shipwrecks
- **26 Mar:** Research Rumble in the HIVE - Visualising the Surface of Mars
- **27 Mar:** Australian Computer Society, Young IT event – VR and Immersive Technologies
- **10 Apr:** Anglo American, FUTURES MINE MINING OPEN FORUM: DISCOVERY UNDER COVER - STIMULUS VISIT event. Four presenters: Dr Uwe Woessner, HLRS, Uni of Stuttgart; Don Pridmore, HiSeis; Ben McKinley, CIRA; Andrew Woods, Curtin HIVE.
- **28 May:** Virtual Prototyping of Maritime Systems and Digital Twins
- **20 Jun:** VR Technologies Update
- **2 Jul:** ResBas - Research Visualisation Using Immersive Technology
- **4 Jul:** ResBas - Research Visualisation Using Immersive Technology
- **5 Sep:** Historical Panoramas Stage 2 launch event, including Ms Margaret Allen, CEO and State Librarian, State Library Western Australia -
- **10 Sep:** VR Technologies Update
- **25 Sep:** Archives Visualisation: LARIS Research Seminar
- **4 Oct:** Labour History Conference visit
- **31 Oct:** Extended Reality CRC Industry Workshop
- **26 Nov:** HoloLens II for Interactive Learning
- **5 Dec:** HIVE Tour for OzCHI Delegates
- **11 Dec:** FBL Visualisation Showcase
- **18 Dec:** Visualization for Data Science and AI

2020

- **13 Jan:** Dr. Helen Farr Deepwater archaeology and the shipwrecks of the Black Sea
- **14 Feb:** HIVE Intern Showcase (full day event)
- **29 Feb:** Astrofest - Decoding the Surface Age of Mars
- **17 Mar:** International Workshop on Design and Data Science (presentations from Prof Robert Woodbury - Simon Fraser University, Prof Yasushi Ikeda - Keio University, Prof Tom Kvan - Melbourne University)
- **27 Jul:** Curtin Open Day – open exhibition style display of various HIVE supported research projects across the day
- **16 Sep:** HIVE Summer Internship Information Session for Academics

2021

- **19 Feb:** HIVE Intern Showcase (full day event)
- **16 Apr:** OldPerth: Mapping Historical Images, and an Experimental VR Experience
- **19 Apr:** Research Rumble - Impact beyond the night sky: a VR experience
- **19 Apr:** Research Rumble - VR in education
- **20 Apr:** Research Rumble - VR in Maritime Archaeology
- **20 Apr:** Research Rumble - VR in Rehabilitation
- **21 Apr:** Research Rumble - VR in Economics
- **21 Apr:** Research Rumble - VR in Planetary Exploration
- **22 Apr:** Research Rumble - Molecules to save endangered species
- **22 Apr:** EMICOL networking event
- **30 May:** Curtin Open Day – open exhibition style display of various HIVE supported research projects across the day
- **15 Oct:** Presentation: Deep-sea corrosion rusticles from iron-hulled shipwrecks
- **1 Dec:** Symposium for WA Hub of the Australian and New Zealand Association of Clinical Anatomists

2022

- **11 Feb:** HIVE Intern Showcase (full day event)
- **8 Apr:** One year on – Exploring Old Perth through the OldPerth website
- **29 Apr:** Photogrammetry Network Seminar 2: Determining coral growth rates

- **20 May:** Photogrammetry Seminar 3: Reconstruction - Santo Antonio de Tanna shipwreck
- **30 Jun:** Photogrammetry Seminar 4: Anatomy from the dissection table to anywhere
- **24 Aug:** HIVE Summer Internship Information Session for Academics
- **7 Sep:** Curtin to GoPro - David Newman (GoPro) Adventures in Custom Camera Solutions
- **22 Nov:** HMAS Sydney (II) and HSK Kormoran 81st Anniversary

2023

- **10 Feb:** HIVE Intern Showcase (full day event)
- **26 Mar:** Curtin Open Day – open exhibition style display of various HIVE supported research projects across the day
- **30 Mar:** Australasian Hydrographic Society Technical Meeting
- **27 Apr:** “OldPerth: Navigating Perth's history through SLWA's photograph collection”, State Library Theatre.

3.5 Showcasing

Visitors to the HIVE receive a quick overview of a selection of projects from across the University, experience the technically advanced facilities at the HIVE, and gain a positive experience of Curtin as an innovation activity centre. Content shown to visitors is now often customised to suit the discipline area of the visitors since we now have a wide range of content to illustrate HIVE activities. Due to the large number of projects undertaken at the HIVE, it is only possible for visitors to see a relatively small snippet of the HIVE's activities. Collaboration opportunities are also explored during visits.

A representative, but not exhaustive, listing of HIVE visitors is provided below:

2018

Representatives from Optus; delegation from Australian Society of Archivists; WA Museum Maritime Archaeology Advisory Committee.

2019

Delegation from Royal Australian Navy; Delegation from FMG; Students from Lynwood Senior High School; Representatives from HP; Representatives from Immersive Technologies; Board of the Gravity Discovery Centre; Signature Program Innovation Day run by Leadership WA; Pearson Australia; Representatives from the Koya Aboriginal Corporation

2020

Delegation from WA Department of Education; Cisco with Senior Executives from La Trobe University; Delegation from BHP; Wollongong University; Blekinge Institute of Technology, Euclidean Unlimited 3D; Women in Technology in WA; Delegation from Australian Defence Clearance Diving Team; representatives from Singular Health; Management team from Bethanie Aged Care; representatives from Knight Frank; delegation from Calibre Group; Main Roads; Students from Maths Association of WA; delegation of officers from the Army; representatives from Rio Tinto

2021

Students from the National Youth Science Forum; Horizon Power; delegation from Gruyere JV Gold Mine; researcher from Icon Films; Wesley School student visit; representatives from Euclidean Holographics; representatives from CleanSubSea; ABC Catalyst; representatives from HP; representatives from Vection Technologies; key personnel from the Federal Attorney-General's department; SSTC partners from Juicebox; delegation from Naval Group; representative from Kanopy; delegation from CanningsPurple; Representatives from Clarity; delegation from Bethanie Group; delegation from Platinum Surveys and Handley Surveys; representatives from Topaz Subsea; delegation from Woodside; representatives from Fortescue Future Industries; delegation from Department of Primary Industries and Regional Development; virtual tour for students of Cyprus University of Technology and Khulna University; representatives from Dell; representatives from FrameVR; delegation from WA Primary Health Alliance; Representatives from City of Albany; The Mathematical Association of Western Australia; delegation from BAE Systems; representatives from ASC (Australian Shipbuilding Company); live cross with JAXA; representatives from CamWA; delegation from Mineral Resources; representatives from NGIS and Skyline; students from Ellenbrook Christian College; representatives from Blue Ocean Monitoring; representatives from Terra15; representatives from Dell

2022

Representatives from MMA Offshore; representative from WA Health; representative from HP; delegation from Department of Premier and Cabinet; students from Prendiville Secondary; workshop for BHP; AV.Technology magazine; launch event for Remsense; delegation from Engine Room Business Innovation; St Mary's school; representatives from Telstra Purple; students from Kalamunda SHS; Delegation from Westrac CAT; students from Kyoto Sangyo University; delegation of policy makers from Vietnam; representative from US Navy; delegation from Healing Foundation; representative from AMD; Delegation from DSTG, representatives from Phase Zero; representatives from Capricorn Space; representatives from SMART SAT CRC; delegation from MIT; representatives from Rio Tinto; delegation from Engine Room Business Innovation; Telethon Kids' Institute; high-level delegation from the UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya; representatives from Barco

2023

Representatives from Continental AG; delegation from DTSG; WA Government Delegates and Education Business Development Managers from Vietnam and Japan; delegation from QEERI - a Qatar alliance in corrosion; delegation from Thriveni; delegation from Woodside; delegates from Universitas Indonesia; delegation from BAE Systems Australia R&D | Cockburn Blue Innovation hub; delegation from Sunshine Grammar School Bangladesh; delegation from Hydrogen Fuel Cell Association Singapore; Office of Naval Research Global; Australian National Maritime Museum; delegation from Nuclear Powered Submarine Task Force; WA Museum; Delegation from Universitas Negeri Malang; representatives from AROSE; delegation from Department of Jobs, Tourism, Science and Innovation with India-Gulf education delegation; delegation from MIT; representatives from HiSeis; representatives from Engineering Army regiment; delegation from Navy Innovation Centre.

3.6 Utilisation Statistics

The HIVE is used as research project space, an events space and a workspace for the HIVE team. In 2018-2023 period of this report, 52.09% of bookable time was consumed by projects and events bookings when workspace time is excluded. HIVE utilisation is 100% when HIVE team workspace usage is included.

The peaks in the booking utility graph are mostly aligned with when the HIVE is being used intensively for user trials such as the Autism Visual Fields Study (Health Sciences), Consumer Behaviour Study (Business), Chemistry Education in VR (Humanities / Science & Engineering), Beacon Virtua User Experience Study (Humanities).

These figures are calculated via an analysis of the HIVE booking calendar using a custom written script, and manual categorisations of individual bookings.

On an annual basis, the booking utility of the HIVE is shown in the table below. All bookings require some level of overhead to organise, prepare and support which is not included in the figures below.

Year	Annual Booking Utility
2014	45.94%
2015	45.13%
2016	48.49%
2017	51.72%
2018	51.93%
2019	54.67%
2020	54.69%
2021	55.67%
2022	46.46%
2023 (to date)	42.41%

HIVE annual booking utility – 2014-2023.

A breakdown of HIVE bookings by booking type is shown in the table below across 10 years, expressed as a percentage of bookable time. Across the last 5 years, the average HIVE booking usage directly for research projects was 17.7%. The average usage for showcasing

(tours, visits, etc) was 10.41% of bookable time. It can be observed that the HIVE is used for a rich mix of different activities including projects, tours, and events as well as supporting visualisation research projects. The HIVE is a valuable way of showing visitors a wide range of University research activity in an impactful way. Presentations and Events are also a useful way of exposing a large target audience to projects supported by the HIVE.

Booking Type	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023 (To Date)
Maintenance				2.54%	3.04%	6.74%	30.49%	11.98%	8.98%	9.2%
Marketing				0.09%	1.31%	1.94%	2.86%	1.50%	1.63%	0.84%
Meeting				0.28%	4.82%	8.36%	5.80%	7.11%	8.82%	9.67%
Project/Research				1.99%	19.59%	20.76%	9.96%	24.30%	16.25%	8.71%
Setup/Misc				0.55%	4.39%	7.54%	2.26%	3.36%	5.43%	6.22%
Talk/Event				0.42%	1.58%	5.68%	2.85%	5.76%	5.29%	7.45%
Tour				0.43%	2.53%	6.38%	1.27%	4.10%	2.93%	3.69%
Uncategorised	45.94%	45.13%	48.49%	45.44%	15.95%					
	45.94%	45.13%	48.49%	51.72%	51.93%	54.67%	54.69%	55.67%	46.46%	42.41%

HIVE booked time by type for indicative months 2014-2023. Each number is a percentage of the total bookable hours for that month excluding HIVE team usage.

The table below shows a small analysis of booked time across the different University areas.

Faculty/Area	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023 (To Date)
Business				0.13%	0.10%	0.47%	0.59%	5.92%	1.73%	3.51%
ROC				0.10%	0.53%	1.89%	0.47%	1.85%	1.15%	2.13%
Science Engineering				0.57%	11.96%	16.60%	6.81%	10.83%	5.44%	4.53%
Central				0.44%	2.53%	4.88%	1.99%	3.33%	3.52%	2.74%
Health Science				0.18%	1.93%	3.81%	0.93%	7.13%	7.30%	7.93%
Humanities				0.48%	6.00%	4.82%	3.73%	6.46%	5.54%	5.58%
Other					2.07%	1.17%	1.25%	0.72%	1.07%	0.93%
HIVE				4.44%	11.89%	21.88%	39.35%	21.53%	21.64%	16.34%
Uncategorised	45.94%	45.13%	48.49%	45.44%	15.95%					
	45.94%	45.13%	48.49%	51.72%	51.93%	54.67%	54.69%	55.67%	46.46%	42.41%

HIVE booked time (as a percentage of total bookable hours) by organisational user for indicative months.

It can be observed that usage varies considerably from month to month as various projects scale up and complete. Other months haven't been fully analysed at this stage because of the semi-manual nature of the analysis process.

3.7 Social Media

The HIVE maintains several social media and public data sharing accounts.

YouTube: @CurtinHIVE

Sketchfab: @CurtinHIVE

Facebook: @HistoricalPanoramas

Instagram: @CurtinHIVE

Twitter: @CurtinHIVE, @HistoricalPanos.

Some of these accounts are more active than others. Some of the accounts receive more attention than others.

3.8 YouTube Statistics:

On YouTube, the @CurtinHIVE account has 159 videos available, both publicly listed and unlisted. Most of the videos are HIVE internships related. The most popular videos are mostly shipwreck related.

The Top 5 most viewed public videos on the HIVE's YouTube channel are:

Thumbnail	Title / Link	Views
	Photogrammetric 3D Model of the stern of HMAS AE1 wreck reconstructed from thousands of photographs https://youtu.be/tVt8gDFZOYO	36,350
	American B-17 Bomber "Black Jack" wreck https://youtu.be/NaFK5TkKPI0	25,704
	Photogrammetric 3D model of the HSK Kormoran engine room hull section https://youtu.be/OpFecw-yyNs	17,125
	Project: Healing Center for the Stolen Generation Survivor Unlisted	402
	Photogrammetric 3D Model of the HADT (High Angle Director Tower) of the wreck of HMAS Sydney (II) https://youtu.be/qUzucSq5XZY	363

as of 21 August 2023

3.9 Sketchfab Statistics

Sketchfab is a platform for sharing 3D models. It allows the HIVE to share 3D models in a very accessible way, allowing users to rotate, zoom and navigate 3D models. There are 338 3D models on the HIVE's Sketchfab account – including shipwrecks, meteorites, mammal skulls, and more. Again, shipwrecks rang highly in the most popular 3D models.

The Top 5 most viewed 3D models on the HIVE's Sketchfab account are:

Thumbnail	Title / Link	Views
A 3D model of a B17 bomber aircraft, shown in a dark, textured environment, possibly representing a shipwreck or a crash site.	American B17 Bomber "Black Jack" (lost 1943) https://skfb.ly/oJpZr	1434
A 3D model of a woman's face, rendered in a realistic style, showing facial features and skin texture.	How platforms see influencers https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/x-1607e8967cb34753978a8788fe586656	954
A 3D model of a library room, showing bookshelves, a desk, and a framed picture on the wall.	NTNU Library Special Collections Room https://skfb.ly/6zTqP	859
A 3D model of a shipwreck, showing the stern of the SS Bonnie Dundee, with various debris and structural elements visible.	SS Bonnie Dundee (1877-1879) Shipwreck (Stern) https://skfb.ly/oEWYn	521
A 3D model of an archaeological site, showing a large, circular structure with a central area highlighted in yellow.	Kyrenia https://hive.curtin.edu.au/kyrenia	433

as of 21 August 2023

3.10 Exhibitions

Permanent/Long-term Exhibitions

WA Museum Boola Bardip (November 2021 – current)

Connections Gallery

- Historical Panoramas (Perth Town Hall panoramas)
- Sydney-Kormoran Project footage

Innovations Gallery

- Sydney-Kormoran Project equipment (underwater camera + light)
- HMAS AE1 wreck 3D printed model
- Short documentary footage – Sydney-Kormoran Project at the HIVE

Shark Bay World Heritage Discovery Centre, Denham: (April 2018 – current)

- "Fire on the Water" mini exhibition and 3D short film "Fire on the Water"

Fire on the Water exhibition

Museum of Geraldton: (November 2016 – current)

- "From Great Depths" mini exhibition and 3D short film "From Great Depths"
- "Beacon Virtua" touch-screen virtual exploration of Beacon Island

Australian National Maritime Museum, Sydney: (Nov 2016 – Nov 2022)

- "From Great Depths" short film (in 2D only)

Temporary / Travelling Exhibitions

Creating Perth exhibition

7 Nov 2020 – 19 Mar 2021: State Library of Western Australia.

Included 50" touch-screen running the kiosk version of Historical Panoramas website as part of the exhibition.

Fremantle Then and Now: Historical Panoramas

(Inspired by and based on the Historical Panoramas project which the HIVE has led since 2015)

23 Sep 2022 - 19 Feb 2023: WA Maritime Museum, Fremantle

Attendance Figures: 30,000

Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas exhibition

Brickwrecks: Sunken Ships in Lego Bricks

(includes 4 exhibit items from projects supervised / created by the HIVE)

Jun 2021 - Jan 2022: WA Maritime Museum, Fremantle

Feb 2022 - May 2022: Museum of the Great Southern, Albany

Sept 2022 - Nov 2022: Museum of Geraldton

Dec 2022 - October 2023: Australian National Maritime Museum, Sydney

HMAS AE1 Revealed

Oct 2018 - Mar 2019: John Curtin Gallery

Nov 2019 - Feb 2020: Princess Royal Fortress' Main Barracks Gallery, Albany

Feb 2022 - May 2022: Museum of Geraldton (Attendance Figures: 6822)

Deep Light: Illuminating the Wrecks of Sydney and Kormoran

Oct 2019 - Aug 2020: Museum of the Goldfields, Kalgoorlie

Sep 2020 - Jan 2021: WA Shipwrecks Museum, Fremantle

Aug 2021 - Oct 2021: Museum of the Great Southern, Albany

Sep 2021 - Feb 2022: WA Museum Boola Bardip (Perth city)

Nov 2021 - Feb 2022: Museum of Geraldton

Deep Light travelling exhibition

24 Feb 2020 – 9 Apr 2020: "Beacon Virtua touchscreen" appeared at "Even Keel Exhibition – maritime misadventures and yachting glories" Wanneroo Gallery, City of Wanneroo.

http://www.wanneroo.wa.gov.au/info/20089/wanneroo_gallery/334/wanneroo_gallery

29 May 2018 to 5 May 2019: 'James Cameron: Challenging the Deep' exhibition at the Australian National Maritime Museum

An SEM image of rusticles from HMAS *Sydney* (II) is used in the exhibition thanks to work from Curtin Corrosion Centre and John de Laeter Centre.

20 Nov 2021 – 28 Feb 2022: "Limen 'At the fence' with Stolen Generations Survivors", at State Library of Western Australia. An outcome of the MissionsConnect project led by Professor Reena Tiwari.

18 Aug 2022 - 2 Oct 2022: "Limen 2.0 - 'At the Fence' Exhibition" at Building 418 exhibition area, Curtin University. An outcome of the MissionsConnect project led by Professor Reena Tiwari.

3.11 Expos and External Events

12 – 14 Jul 2019: XR:WA Conference

7 Sep 2019: TEDx 2019, Perth Concert Hall. Rehabilitation VR project presented by Marina Ciccarelli. (below)

1 Aug 2019: SUT Movie Night at SLWA

27 – 28 Nov 2019: Resource Technology Showcase Conference

3 – 6 Dec 2020: XR:WA Conference

16 Apr 2021: Heritage Perth weekend - OldPerth: Mapping Historical Images, and an Experimental VR Experience, State Library Theatre

3.12 Feedback

The HIVE has hosted a wide range of visitors and various feedback has been collected from time to time. Some example feedback are provided below:

Lynwood Senior High School group for National Science Week feedback:

- “My experience at the HIVE Centre at Curtin University was **eye-opening and extremely interesting**. The highlight of my day was the 3D viewing of the shipwreck. It was very **captivating** as it was a new experience for me. To be able to view the shipwreck as if I was down there was amazing. Also, to be able to see the landscape and environment on Mars in such high definition was amazing. I learnt about the research currently occurring on Mars and their search for water and possible life. Seeing the new technological advancements first hand was definitely worth it and recommendable for other students. It gave me a new interest in geology and space research.” **Alison**
- “Heya, HIVE person. **Oh my God, I had such a good time today**. The coloured map of Mars was gorgeous! And it was so fun to look at the surface of Mars on the super high definition screens! I didn’t know how interesting Mars was, with all the craters and river looking things, it was really cool. I’d love to go back and try out the walking on Mars thing, as I accidentally spent all my time looking at the big screens, and it looked really cool too. All up it was a great experience, and I’m glad I got to go.” **Genna**
- “We started our journey not knowing what to expect. When we arrived we were greeted by a smiling face. When we entered the HIVE everyone was unsure what was happening. Once we put those 3D glasses on all was silent and everyone was interested in what the presenter was saying. My highlight of the day was getting to see technology that no one was aware of and being someone who got to see it, I was excited. The most interesting part of the day was getting to see how Mars looks and getting to play around with the technology. **This excursion encourages me to be part of researching to contribute to HIVE.**” **Jad**
- “The HIVE excursion was extremely enjoyable, the speakers and technology being very engaging and fun to test and try out. I found the 3D shipwreck highly interesting and enjoyed learning about the technology used to create it. The Virtual Reality headsets were really cool and I would love to invest in one to try out and possibly learn how to use the software that goes with it. Overall, **I found the whole experience really eye-opening** and I am now curious about the technology I saw today. I would love to go again and would recommend it to others.” **Jordyn**
- “The Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch (HIVE) was an **eye-opening, mind-blowing and very educational experience** about virtual reality. The 3D projection of the sunken submarine that was lost for around 100 years was super interesting. Knowing that researchers had to use special equipment under more than 300 metres of depth and take a lot of still images on every angle just shows how much effort is put into creating the 3D projection. With more students and more events like these, more individuals would help to create more virtual reality images. I am inspired with the technological advancements being made and that technology will never stop advancing. With more

awareness to this, students will come together and support these subjects to create a change and an impact to our world." **Jihan**

- "The Curtin HIVE, Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch was **an amazing experience** and I am incredibly grateful for all the staff at Curtin University. One of my favourite highlights of the experience was the use of the 3D view of the shipwrecked submarines and it amazed me how humans have come to reach such high quality and advanced our technologies have become. The use of virtual reality could be the next biggest technological advancement for the rest of Australia and even the world and I am excited for what new amazing courses that comes from Curtin University. I would like to acknowledge one of the artists which allowed some of us students to view his amazing art exhibition and I loved his piece on 4' 33" By John Cage. Good luck on your PHD and I'm looking forward to more experiences at Curtin Uni!" **Zahli**
- "I enjoyed my time at Curtin HIVE today. I learnt about what it takes to create augmented and virtual reality and what participants are doing to make this technology better. Wearing the VR headset made me feel like I was actually on a spacecraft on Mars, which was **an awesome experience**. Wearing the 3D glasses and looking at a 3D image of 8000 photos of a submarine was also mind-blowing. I could not imagine how sophisticated and detailed working with VR and AR technology can be. The 360-degree video was awesome as well. I felt like I could walk into the film/video and it was interesting how your voice or sound reflects back to you off the curved screen, which distorted our voices. It influenced me to look into more of this technology to gain more general knowledge on how technology works and where it's taking us into the future." **Ashton**
- "I think the thing within the HIVE that I liked the most is the dome screen because it actually felt like I was in the movie without even wearing a VR headset. I also liked the VR driving activity where we were put on Mars with an Xbox controller as it actually sort of felt real, exploring the surface of Mars and of course the tour of the wreck of first Australian sub in 3D was also very interesting, I learnt that there are so many more craters on the surface of Mars than I previously thought, there are actually millions of them, shown by the map of the surface of mars on the 180 Degree screen. I learnt a lot about submarines in the 3D tour, **I think that because of these activities I will think about going to the space program definitely more than I wanted to before these activities**, I found it very interesting and it's a great set of activities where kids can learn in a fun way about space and other planets." **Alex**
- "The most impressive part of the HIVE was the 3D virtualization of the submarine wreck, which was very well done and was the main highlight of the excursion. I have learnt how 3D virtualization of objects are created by taking multiple pictures of it. This excursion has influenced me to be more interested in computer science, since I have been interested in programming. The other interesting part of the HIVE excursion was virtual reality of the Mars surface, which was amazing. The 360 Degree virtual reality of the office was well done as well. **Although it was a short excursion I enjoyed it a lot.**" **Christopher**
- "Today we went to Curtin University in order to experience the Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch (HIVE). We were met at the entrance by Mr Keeling, who was our guide for the day. Once we arrived at the HIVE Centre I was immediately taken back at how different everything looked and at the endless possibilities in which they processed. A personal highlight of mine was the multi-screened moon exhibit, this display featured over 24 million pixels, over the 12 times the amount of standard computers! Throughout this excursion I learned a variety of things including, the shape of both the Moon and Mars surface, the process of filming in VR and how far we have progressed technologically. Although I still process no solid idea of what I wish to do professionally **this excursion has opened my eyes to the unlimited possibilities.**" **Jordon**
- "At the Curtin HIVE today, we started off with a 3D session looking at a sunken submarine that was found 18 months ago. It was pretty cool since it's hard enough for students to come across submarines let alone a 3D image of an entire submarine. There was also a

VR headset that showed parts of Mars from the point of view of a rover, an immersive 180-degree semi dome and a massive screen showing heaps of craters in fine detail. I reckon the submarine talk and viewing was really interesting because I was sitting in the front row and **it's something you don't really see every day**. Definitely want to go to space and explore some planets and whatnot after this and would definitely go back."
Man

The year after this high-school visit to the HIVE, one of the students who attended this session excitedly knocked on the HIVE door to tell us that he was now studying Computer Science at Curtin and it was his very first day!

Leadership WA Innovation Tour Reflections:

- "The visit to The HIVE within Curtin was **literally amazing** in terms of the virtual experiences and insight that people can now provide through the use of technology. This was such a fun session and illustrated what can be done with ideas that start off as imagination or dreams. Thankyou for your time and for demonstrating the abilities of this fantastic technology - **it was awesome!**"
- "**I found this mind-blowing! Absolutely mind-blowing!** The technology, the ways in which technology initially developed for one industry has applications across to other fields. loved it."
- "Thanks to the team at HIVE - it was great to see how information could be presented in so many different ways. I appreciated the opportunities we now have in WA to look at how these could be integrated into other projects and use the techniques / tools and approaches to address real world problems."
- "**Amazing screens Thankyou!!**"
- "I really enjoyed the experiential tour of the HIVE. **What a fabulous space!**"
- "The HIVE was **a great insight** into the technology that is being developed to assist human-kind. The world is changing faster than we think, and the way we learn things and what we learn should be changed. Employers create an engaging learning culture at work by empowering their staff to take ownership of their professional development. No one can predict the future of technology exactly, because no one can see the future. However, there are reasonable arguments that can be made, based on the advances and trends of technology in the past. For instance, it is reasonable to predict that computers will continue to get more powerful, numerous, and cheaper."
- "**Wow what an experience and here we are at the tip of the iceberg. The technology was amazing.** Really enjoyed this part."
- "**This is such a great space/idea and it was fantastic** to get an insight into some of the technology that is helping people conduct research and virtually explore new realms."
- "**Fascinating and so versatile.**"
- "It was **exciting** to see people immersed and passionate about what they do, and doing it day in and day out with such enthusiasm."
- "**Awesome** to see this investment in technology - **very impressive**. Shame more people cannot see it or experience it."
- "Just that it was **fantastic and hugely enjoyable**"
- "**I got a real buzz** out of seeing the amazing images that brought field expedition and research to life. Very impressive (even if it did make me a little woozy)"
- "**Fantastic and fun** experience. New this tech was around however this is at a commercial / elevated level. Reflections - a day will come when the families of crews in the shipwrecks will wander around where their loved ones perished. Loved the idea that following where meteors flew resulted in a 30% success rate in finding the rock"

- "Thanks to the whole team in the Hive. Coming from someone who grew up with the first Star Wars movie **the whole experience was sensational**. I would love all of my colleagues to share the experience."
- "**The HIVE is a great facility, and some of the research it enables is world class**. It's a great example of modern humanities research also, and the role of data in humanities which is often overlooked."
- "**Outstanding technology being used in wonderful applications**. This makes me excited to think of the amazing new developments and solutions that will be discovered using this new technology."

Feedback about the "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" exhibition:

- **This was truly an exceptional exhibition**. We hope it will become a permanent exhibition so that many, many more people understand the unique history and character of Fremantle.
- ...one must congratulate you and others on the **enlightening** journey through the eras of our Fremantle Port and surrounds. Job well done.
- This exhibition should be permanent.
- **Fantastic**. Please present again so we can spread the word again.
- The West Australian online wrote: "This is no ordinary photographic exhibition, but one which invites you to step into it...Who said time travel isn't possible?"
- FreoView wrote: "**wonderful and fascinating** photo exhibition... should not be missed! I loved it, especially the projection shows on the curved screen. I learned a lot of things I did not know about. Go see it!"

"**The HIVE is a jewel at Curtin and you oversee its success with style**." Professor Chris Moran, Deputy Vice-Chancellor of Research, May 2023.

Testimonials – compiled for VC's Awards to Excellence (July 2021)

Professor Gretchen Benedix

School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering

The HIVE Team has been an invaluable partner in helping my research team interrogate our results to the highest possible level. We have created the first database of automatically detected impact craters on planetary surfaces. We achieved this using Machine Learning techniques and analysing huge amounts of image data that is available from NASA. What NASA doesn't provide is an easy way to visualise and interact with the images when they are merged together to form single mosaic images that are 10s of gigabytes in size. Interacting quickly with images of this size requires special visualisation techniques.

We came to the HIVE Team back in 2015 with the first results of our computer algorithm. Our initial use was primarily the big screens to be able to see the whole image at one time. After that introduction, the HIVE Team showed us how they could enhance what we were looking at and used their knowledge and skills to build interactive visualisations that include not only our datasets, but the datasets overlaid on high resolution images of Mars and the Moon.

This was remarkable given that we needed to look at 94 million craters at multiple levels of resolution in a timely fashion. They delivered that ability and provided a way for us to allow

the public to access the imagery as well. The ability to look at the data quickly and at high resolution has led to 5 publications^{1,2,3,4,5} over the last 2 years, including one Nature Communications¹ and one Earth and Planetary Science Letters² in the last 6 months.

The HIVE Team have always gone beyond our expectations to offer ideas on and deliver innovative and excellent visualisation, which not only are publicly pleasing, but scientifically important. Their hard work, knowledge, and collaborative attitude has definitely allowed us to fulfil our strategy of undertaking world class research and sharing it widely and easily.

I fully support and endorse this well-deserved nomination of the HIVE Team for the VC's Excellence Awards.

1. Lagain, A., et al., 2022. Early crustal processes revealed by the ejection site of the oldest martian meteorite. *Nat Commun* 13, 3782. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31444-8>
2. Lagain, A., et al., 2022. Has the impact flux of small and large asteroids varied through time on Mars, the Earth and the Moon? *Earth Planet Sc Lett* 579, 117362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2021.117362>
3. Lagain, A., et al., 2021. Large Meteorite Impacts and Planetary Evolution VI 629–644. [https://doi.org/10.1130/2021.2550\(29\)](https://doi.org/10.1130/2021.2550(29))
4. Lagain, A., et al., 2021. Model Age Derivation of Large Martian Impact Craters, Using Automatic Crater Counting Methods. *Earth Space Sci* 8. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020ea001598>
5. Lagain, A., et al., 2021. The Tharsis mantle source of depleted shergottites revealed by 90 million impact craters. *Nat Commun* 12, 6352. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26648-3>

Associate Professor Marina Ciccarelli
Occupational Therapy, Curtin School of Allied Health, Faculty of Health Sciences

Since its inception, the Curtin HIVE has created opportunities for Curtin researchers from diverse disciplines to meet, collaborate, and be technically supported on the development of visualisation and extended realities projects. I have been a regular collaborator in the HIVE since 2016 after receiving the opportunity to work with a HIVE summer intern on the development of a wayfinding application for people with cognitive impairments. The HIVE Team have provided technical support of interns (and researchers such as myself!) and facilitated the development of their skills and confidence to work with a range of visualisation platforms including virtual reality (VR).

A key innovative partnership with myself and the HIVE has been a VR cooking simulation that was developed as a solution to a consumer-driven problem: How might a home-based immersive VR rehabilitation program be used as an adjunct to conventional therapies for people living with disability? The problem highlighted that while daily participation in therapies were important for restoration of upper limb movement and coordination after injury (such as a spinal cord injury, stroke, or traumatic brain injury), daily attendance at therapy sessions with a physiotherapist or occupational therapist in the community was neither economically viable nor practicable due to the time and cost involved with transport into the community. This issue was magnified for people living in rural and remote areas who had limited access to health professionals.

The HIVE Team were instrumental in the early stages of the prototype development of a virtual reality (VR) cooking simulation for use with people living with cervical spinal cord injuries. The VR cooking simulation provided the user with the opportunity to cook (a steak and then later cheeseburgers) at a stove, that involved a range of arm movements that were related to the user's individual rehabilitation goals. Unlike commercially available VR games. The cooking simulation could be gamified and customised to provide a 'just right challenge' for each user, giving opportunity for success and then progressing to more challenging physical demands. This prototype was showcased in the HIVE to representatives from the Insurance Commission of WA (ICWA) and formed the basis of a successful grant application to ICWA for further development and trial of the VR simulation in the wider community. I

believe that providing the funder with the opportunity to view and trial the prototype in the HIVE was an important factor leading to the success of the grant.

In partnership with Dr Susan Morris (Senior Lecturer, Physiotherapy, Curtin School of Allied Health), a consumer-co-researcher, and a VR programmer, a refined iteration of the VR cooking simulation was developed and trialled with the ICWA funding. The researchers had the opportunity to partner with disability providers in WA identify suitable study participants who were living with cervical spinal cord injuries. The pilot trial determined the home-based VR cooking simulation was feasible, acceptable, and was associated with some improvements in participants' movement coordination over a six-week period. Most importantly, the users of the VR cooking simulation could be supported remotely to customise their use of the home-based rehabilitation program. To our knowledge this is a world-first trial of the VR technology in home-based and remotely supported rehabilitation.

Over the last year, the HIVE Team – particularly Wesley and Carley, have provided the research team with numerous opportunities and technical support to further showcase the simulation to community stakeholders including prospective students at Curtin Open Day, research collaborators at the XRWA conference, and potential end users in the health and disability sector. Such is the support provided by the HIVE Team that they have the confidence to showcase our VR rehabilitation project to community members even when the research team were unavailable to present. For example, the HIVE Team presented the VR simulation to 20-30 members from the WA Country Health Service, highlighting its potential for use with patients living in regional WA.

I am certain that our research team could not have even considered the development of the VR cooking simulation, let alone achieve a successful trial and showcase to the community without the support of the HIVE staff.

Professor Reena Tiwari
School of Design and the Built Environment, Faculty of Humanities

The HIVE Team have played a vital role in supporting the dissemination, outreach, and engagement activities at the HIVE for Professor Reena Tiwari's multi award-winning MissionsConnect Project developed at Curtin's Stolen Generations Immersive Hub. HIVE Team's collective expertise, as well as their access to the necessary equipment and software, have been instrumental in enabling and enhancing the presentation of this Project to a wide variety of public, corporate, and community stakeholders. Between July 2021 and June 2022 alone, these key stakeholders included two WA Ministers for Innovation and ICT, WA Department of Premier and the Cabinet, Member for Cockburn, National Trust WA, Community Arts Network, Minderoo Foundation, and the New Aboriginal Cultural Centre. In addition, the MissionsConnect Project hosted workshops with Stolen Generations Survivors that included deeply emotive viewing sessions at the HIVE. In performing their support role, the HIVE Team not only demonstrated technical knowledge but also cultural competency in terms of familiarity with and sensitivity to Indigenous protocols at these sessions. The Team have also capably supported other engagement activities of the Project at the HIVE including professional development and training programs, for example, for Aboriginal Primary School teachers from Port Hedland, as well as cultural awareness sessions for Curtin staff and students.

For context, the MissionsConnect project (supported by the HIVE Team) has won the following awards in the period Jul 2021 to Jun 2022:

- Winner - Planning Institute of Australia (PIA) National Awards for Planning Excellence 2022, Aboriginal & Torres Strait Islander Planning category. (May 2022)

- Winner - 2022 ACS (Australian Computer Society) Digital Disruptors Award for ICT Service Transformation for the Digital Consumer (NFP/NGO). (Feb 2022)
- Winner (x2) - 2021 WA Awards for Planning Excellence from the Planning Institute of Australia. Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Planning and Technology, and Digital Innovation categories. (Dec 2021)
- Winner – 2021 WA Heritage Awards, Interpretation Category. (Oct 2021)
- Merit Award Winner - 30th INCITE Awards, WA Information Technology and Telecommunications Alliance (WIATTA), Social Impact category. (Jul 2021)

Dr Brian von Konsky FACS CP
Unit Coordinator, ISYS5009 Societal Impact of Technological Innovation
School of Management and Marketing, Faculty of Business and Law

I am grateful for the expertise of the HIVE staff who semester after semester have facilitated a technology rich learning environment for Master of Commerce common core students. Student feedback regularly cites the HIVE visit as one of the best parts of the unit. For example, one student wrote:

"I was very impressed by the indigenous culture which was exhibited in such a way (using AI). I, as a foreigner, had very little knowledge about indigenous culture and the history. I was told some pieces from here and there, but never so impressed, in a way to know that the aboriginal people had such a rich culture, and they lived a pure and balanced life along with the environment. From this experience, as a student learning IT knowhow, it brings inspiration about how new technology (AI) can help to inherit the culture. It showed me a total new way of utilizing IT and more specifically AI. I do believe the local culture in this land worth to being carried forward. In my point of view, the utilisation of AI in culture heritage is a meaningful method. And I hope this method could be also adopted in my home-country for our culture to be shown to the young generations."

Students in ISYS5009 Societal Impact of Technological Innovation learn how technology can be used for the social good. Over the course of the semester, students in this Master of Commerce common core unit examine a range of case studies. These include examples of how technology can be used to address United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, enhance accessibility for those with special needs, and promote inclusivity. One class session is held each semester at the HIVE. Students experienced Virtual Reality (VR) applications and considered how technology can be used to convey the rich culture, history, and language of indigenous Australians, their enduring connection to the land, and the suffering endured by the stolen generation. Experiences during HIVE visits have included Professor Reena Tiwari's work on visualising indigenous missions for truth telling and conveying the stories of the stolen generation; Historical Panoramas showing how Perth has changed over time since the arrival of Europeans; Gnarla Boodja Mili Mili (Our Country on Paper), exploring indigenous placenames associated with sites around Perth; and Virtual Wadjuk. The latter is a significant part of the ISYS5009 HIVE learning experience. Using Oculus VR headsets, together with projection on the video wall, Virtual Wadjuk transports students back in time to a date prior to the arrival of European settlers. Through VR, students experience a smoking ceremony firsthand; participate in food gathering; announce themselves to water spirits by picking up sand using their VR hand controller, and throwing it into the virtual ocean; and the ominous arrival of Europeans as their ship appears on the horizon while catching fish at what is now known as Bather's beach in Fremantle. Without the technical expertise and professional logistical support of the HIVE staff, this enriching VR experiences would not be possible. As the size of this common core unit has grown, these challenges include facilitating multiple Oculus VR headsets in parallel to maximise the number of students who can wear the headset for the first-hand experience, rather than watching it on the video wall; technical issues

associated with audio and projection of headsets to other class attendees; and coordinating the logistics of increasingly large student numbers.

Gary Hale

Chief Security Officer (CSO) and Director, Defence & Space Research Office at Curtin

'During the period 2021 and 2022, we have had over 50 VIP visitors from Defence and Space government and industry entities to Curtin University. These are foundational visits for creating the first step in building enduring partnerships with, for example, defence stakeholders, and therefore first impressions are very important.

To maximise our impact, we have collaborated with the HIVE to create compelling presentations, including demonstration of capabilities and data visualisation relevant to those stakeholders. Encouraging our researchers to share their data through engagement with the HIVE staff has been key to raising awareness of this fundamental visualisation capability that is unique to Curtin (and Australia), but also in how researchers can present their research outcomes in various formats to increase the impact of their work.

The HIVE's staff are often asked to do this at short notice, including a visit last year for the launch of Curtin's Binar-1 CubeSat with the Deputy Premier, and a most recent visit only yesterday (2 Aug 22), where we had two of the Chiefs from Defence Science & Technology Group (DSTG) request a visit to Curtin with two days notice. To their credit, the HIVE staff did a fantastic job of working closely with myself, and the various researchers, to create visualisation themes relevant to the visitors, thereby significantly increasing the impact we can have on these VIP stakeholders.

The HIVE staff do a fantastic job and have been great collaborators in building our defence and space profile. As such, I believe we should recognise the importance of the HIVE, and importantly our staff, as a jewel in Curtin's crown noting the importance of digital transformation, data science and visualisation of data, not just for defence and space, but all the relevant markets for which we can impact.'

Tripadvisor Feedback – Museum of Geraldton

for the HIVE supported exhibit "From Great Depths" and 3D short film about the wrecks of HMAS *Sydney* II and HSK *Kormoran*:

https://www.tripadvisor.com/Attraction_Review-g255365-d2500865-Reviews-Museum_Of_Geraldton-Geraldton_Western_Australia.html

- "A wonderfully designed and engaging museum with original treasures from the wreck of the Batavia, a 3D film of HMAS *Sydney* II and more. Interested and very helpful staff." Christine O, June 2023
- "Worth a visit! Small but an outstanding museum. 3D video about HMAS *Sydney* from 2.5km under water, Dutch shipwrecks, information about the local indigenous people, early settlers plus flora and fauna." Jean M, May 2023
- "Very interesting, the kids love it. Entry was free ... and there is a 3D theatre in which a documentary about the HMAS *Sydney* II was displayed..." Flynalyn, Jan 2023
- "The 3D film, glasses provided, about the wrecks of HMAS *Sydney* and the Batavia is **fascinating**." HDStripad, Sept 2022
- "Do take the time to watch the HMAS *Sydney* movie and the guided tour." Helen W, June 2022
- "We also **loved** the 3D movie about the HMAS *Sydney* II." Bec M, Apr 2022

- "This is such a good museum. The documentary on the HMAS Sydney was **very moving**." Wendy C, Mar 2022
- "This is one of the best museums I have visited. Everything is well laid out and the explanatory wall notes are exceptional. **The highlight of our visit** was the 3D theatre film exploring the wrecks of both the HMAS Sydney and The Kormoran. You actually feel like you are swimming around the wrecks on the seabed. Well done!" Warren M, Nov 2021
- "We spent half a day here at the museum, the time just whizzed by. A number of very interesting exhibits and galleries. One dedicated to the HMAS Sydney with **amazing 3D vision**." PBH, Sep 2021
- "The separate Batavia section was very interesting, however **our preference** was the HMAS Sydney short movie about the wrecks of the Sydney and Kormoran. It was **fascinating**. Staff advised us to also view HMAS Sydney exhibits in Denham and Carnarvon which we did and thoroughly enjoyed." Ron P, Sep 2021
- "**Loved** all the info about the HMAS Sydney II discovery, and it's a good idea to watch the 3-D film and see the museum before heading up to the Sydney II Memorial." Robyn W, Aug 2021

Tripadvisor Feedback – Shark Bay World Heritage Discovery and Visitor Centre for the HIVE supported exhibit "Fire on the Water" and 3D short film about the wrecks of HMAS Sydney II and HSK Kormoran:
https://www.tripadvisor.com.au/Attraction_Review-g488337-d2501084-Reviews-Shark_Bay_World_Heritage_Discovery_and_Visitor_Centre-Denham_Western_Australia.html

- "The fire on the water display was an **amazing tribute** to the brave men aboard the HMAS Sydney II who lost their lives in battle. It was very good to read and learn about our history - I still tell everyone I can about what I learnt!" Rochelle, Aug 2022
- "It is also the home of HMAS Sydney II memorial and 'Fire on the Water' exhibition detailing the battle between HMAS Sydney and HSK Kormoran" Colin, Aug 2022
- "There was also a 3D movie "Fire on the Water" about the HMAS Sydney which was sad and informative." Acineto, June 2022
- "They had an exhibition on the sinking of HMAS Sydney which was **brilliant** ..." BrentFran, June 2021
- "First the Fire and Water exhibit explaining the HMAS Sydney II battle and film of the ship as it is now, under water was **brilliant**. History that we didn't know, explained in a way we understood. Not suitable for children as there was a lot of writing, not narrated. Was 3D too which added to the drama." Janet_Percy, June 2021
- "Fantastic experience, there is something for all ages and interests. The 3D Fire on the water film is an **absolute must see**." Helen G, Sept 2020
- "HMAS Sydney film: The Information Centre run a short 3D film, every 30 minutes, for free. It is **extremely well done**. Factual. The information is written simply, with the backdrop being footage from the ship wrecks. **A presentation well worth seeing**." Ian S, Aug 2020
- "The Fire on the Water exhibit / movie was an added bonus & a thought provoking look at what happened to the HMAS Sydney II." Karen D, July 2020
- "This place is a must! What a wonderful place to visit! So much to experience, especially the 3D movie of the battle between the Sydney and Kormoran... so realistic and poignant! Recommend this as a 'must see' place, before you do anything else in this magnificent world heritage area." BenandJudy, Oct 2019
- "I can't speak highly enough about my experience at the Discovery and Visitor centre. ... The display and film about the HMAS Sydney is **first class** and I was surprised there was no charge for this." Michael C, Aug 2019
- "Worth visiting to find out all about the area, to see the free exhibition, free HMAS Sydney film and museum of the history and area." Marieanddon, Sept 2019

- "Well worth a visit: Mum and I enjoyed wondering around the discovery centre and seeing the [video about the battle between HMAS *Sydney* II and Kormoran](#) where all 645 on the HMAS Sydney died! **Really good presentation** and I was interested to see what the ship wrecks look like now with all the sea life growing on it! Worth a visit." Kay M, Aug 2019
- "**Great presentation** on the battle involving [HMAS SYDNEY](#) and the loss of all crew. Very moving and an integral part of maritime history." Wickards, Aug 2019
- "Brilliant display about the [HMAS Sydney: the HMAS Sydney display](#) was **moving**. The mystery about what happened has been a thing of interest for me since I was a young fella and it was an hour well spent learning about it." AdamLeaves, July 2019
- "we visited a **magnificent short film** on the final hours of [HMAS Sydney and the German raider *Kormoran*](#)." Paul H, July 2019
- "Worth a visit: ... a display about the ship wrecks including detail about [HMAS Sydney](#) include a 3D documentary about it. **Really worthwhile**." AP194R, June 2019
- "An added bonus is the free [3D movie](#) presentation on the [HMAS Sydney](#) with great footage taken on the wreck site. This footage is **remarkable** and with the rest of the photos and information, plus a great soundtrack it paints a very poignant story." jorose17, May 2019
- "Attend one of the best Visitors Information Center in Western Australia. Wonderful Staff. Supplied great information. Make sure you attend the [HMAS Sydney audio visual display](#) and the Local History Display." Andrew B, May 2019
- "The real must do is visit the fire and water display which is about the demise of [HMAS Sydney](#) a **wonderful exhibition**." Jppetty, Apr 2019
- "Lots of information on the area with a **great** [HMAS Sydney 3D presentation](#)." Ron McBride, Apr 2019
- "**Really enjoyed** the [3D film](#) of the [Sydney II / Kormoran](#) encounter" Cameron, Aug 2018
- "**I loved the 3D screening** to view and all the Information on offer for Denham and Shark Bay." Emma O, July 2018
- "**The film about the HMAS Sydney was the highlight and highly recommended**." Liam M, July 2018
- "Absolutely fascinating Discovery centre: Shark Bay Discovery centre - has an **amazing 3D video film** about [HMAS Sydney II](#)" annettelaurie, May 2018
- "The film on the [HMAS Sydney](#) was **well presented**. After seeing the Geraldton Memorial it helped to explain more." SkiGrowingOld, May 2018
- "Haunting display for the [HMAS Sydney](#): ... **I deeply enjoyed the tribute to the HMAS Sydney**. I was very touched as I never knew the battle that took place ..." Leah M, May 2018
- "The [3D film](#) re the wreck of [HMAS Sydney](#) is **worth watching**." Deborah S, May 2018
- "A great info centre with a **fantastic exhibition** of the [HMAS Sydney](#)." SandyFord16, May 2018

Learning and Student Experience

Preparing our students for the future

*"My experience at the HIVE
was eye-opening and
extremely interesting"*

**Lynwood Senior High School
student**

4 Learning and Student Experience

The HIVE contributes to learning and student experience in a wide range of ways – from the HIVE summer internship program, to a plethora of different student visits. This section identifies how the HIVE contributes to learning and student experience.

4.1 HIVE Summer Internships

The HIVE summer internship scheme is one of the HIVE's major student research project schemes each year. Students receive a \$7k scholarship to conduct a 10 week visualisation related research project under the supervision of a discipline expert and with support of the HIVE team. Curtin academics propose the projects and under a competitive process high achieving students are allocated projects, awarded a scholarship and commence the research project. The scheme allows academics to progress research projects that they may have had in mind for some time but have been unable to progress themselves. There have been one round of the HIVE internship scheme active during the period of this report, and a total of five rounds have been run by the HIVE to date.

HIVE internships 2018–2019 (Round 4)

HIVE Intern Showcase held on 15 Feb 2019. Videos of the presentations are available at the links below.

Student Firstname	Lastname	Faculty	Project Title, and HIVE Intern Showcase Presentation Video Link	Supervisor
Lauren	Found	SAE	44 Application of automatic horizon picking software to seismic interpretation https://youtu.be/X4cM4jaYMA4?t=378	Chris Elders
Isaac	McCormack	SLWA/HUM	32 'Living' Historical Documents (Lihido) https://youtu.be/X4cM4jaYMA4?t=1683	Artur Lugmayr
Erin	Jackson	WAM/SAE	43 Converting the Journals of Francisco Pelseart, Commander of the Dutch VOC Ship Batavia into a Web Archive within Linked Open Data https://youtu.be/X4cM4jaYMA4?t=2717	David McMeekin
Andrew	Thomas	CIC2/SAE	48 Visualizing carbon nanostructures https://youtu.be/bBXRCSBQce0?t=23	Carla de Tomas
Jack	McNair	CIC1/SAE	41 Virtual Exploration of Mars Craters https://youtu.be/bBXRCSBQce0?t=1257	Gretchen Benedix
Harrison	Travers	FBL	12 Reducing the burden of disease: exploring behavioural responses to health policy. From virtual world to virtual reality https://youtu.be/NWqK65EiRpY?t=262	Stephanie Thomas
Benjamin	Cheng	HUM	33 Experiencing & modelling experiments in VR https://youtu.be/NWqK65EiRpY?t=2625	Mihye Won
Darp	Nagarsheth	HS/PTA	22 A mobile educational resource for the safe and efficient use of public transportation in Perth. https://youtu.be/NWqK65EiRpY?t=3609	Marina Ciccarelli
Ahmad	Allahham	HIVE/SAE	45 - Scientific Visualization of asteroid strikes and cratered worlds https://youtu.be/NWqK65EiRpY?t=4808	Katarina Miljkovic

Additionally, Daniel Adams, from the Computer Science final year project group presented on their HIVE supported project: "Development of a Camera-Based Projection Mapping System for Non-Flat Surfaces":

<https://youtu.be/NWqK65EiRpY?t=1615>

 Curtin University

Curtin HIVE Intern Showcase

Friday 15 February 2019

Now in its fourth year, the Curtin HIVE Summer Internship Program provides an opportunity for students to gain valuable research project experience in visualisation related topics. Interns are supervised by leading researchers and undertook challenging research projects utilising the resources and support provided by the HIVE. Supervisors and sponsors benefited from the opportunity to explore new techniques and technologies for their research area.

Event Details
Date: Friday 15 February 2019
Time: Morning Session 9am - 12noon
 Afternoon Session 1pm - 4pm
Venue: Curtin HIVE, inside John Curtin Gallery, Building 200A, Curtin University, Bentley, Western Australia. Map: maps.curtin.edu.au

Registration
 Attendees must register to attend via these links:
Morning Session: <http://bit.ly/1Lzom2t>
Afternoon Session: <http://bit.ly/1Lzom2t> (full showcase program available via above links)

Further Information
 If you have any special requirements to enable you to participate at this event, please advise when you RSVP. We will contact you to provide assistance. For information about disability services at Curtin, please visit: disability.curtin.edu.au

At the 2019 HIVE Intern Showcase ten students will provide an overview of their work followed by demonstrations on the HIVE screens – Cylinder, Wedge, Dome, Tile and 4K display.

Make tomorrow better. Telephone: +61 8 3266 3024
www.curtin.edu.au/hive

Isaac McCormack's project – 'Living' historical documents.

Benjamin Cheng's project – Shooting arrows in VR.

Erin Jackson's project – Transforming the journals of Francisco Pelseart.

Andrew Thomas' project - Visualizing carbon nanostructures

Jack McNair's project – Mars VR.

Harrison Travers' project - Profit versus Prevention.

Lauren Found's project - Seismic interpretation

Darp Nagarsheth's project - Mobile educational resource for public transport.

Ahmad Allahham's project - visualisation of asteroid strikes

Daniel Adams' project - Cylindrical projection mapping.

HIVE internships 2019–2020 (Round 5)

HIVE Intern Showcase held on 14 Feb 2020. Videos of the presentations are available at the links below.

Student Firstname	Lastname	Faculty	Project Title, and HIVE Intern Showcase Presentation Video Link	Supervisor
Nicholas	Brajkovich	CIC	AR and VR experience of the Legacy Living Lab https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QMPFKjmskLY&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=2&t=0s	Rebecca Lange
Maria Loraine	Lu	HIVE	Indian Ocean tectonics from detailed bathymetry data https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nGjJ5_a090A&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=3&t=0s	Chris Elders
Michael	Greif	CIC	What happens when you rub on that cream? Understanding how drug molecules penetrate our skin by molecular visualisation https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YWSxV-nhthw&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=4&t=0s	Ricardo L. Mancera
Dior	Etherton	HS	3D visualisation of abnormal gastrointestinal system - when the right is not right and left is not left https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yagSfhgpXWM&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=5&t=0s	Lisa BG Tee
Robyn	Mae Ong	ROC	Impact: Beyond the Night Sky https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PIM7aDSM9k0&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=6&t=0s	Kath Dooley
Max	Collins	SLWA	OldPerth - a Geo-location Visualisation of Images from Around Perth https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dcLY7FFRzQo&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=7&t=0s	Andrew Woods
David (Jiande)	Xing	HIVE	Mars craters visualised across spectrum https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cbbDFxbfq_l&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=8&t=0s	Katarina Miljkovic
Mitchell	O'Sullivan	SAE	Visualising the Orbits of Small Solar System Bodies Using Data from the Desert Fireball Network https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yo1vqbg3uvc&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=9&t=0s	Martin Towner
Mark	Bi	HUM	Building student engagement and supporting learning through interactive virtual reality environments https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wCcQC_2BBdY&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=10&t=0s	Rebecca Walker
Samuel	Bray	FBL	A multiplayer environment for studying health related behavior https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yPPsppoOoql&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=11&t=0s	Stephanie Thomas
Olivia	Spear	MCASI/HIVE	Two Rivers Deep: A Digital Literary Map the Derbal Yarrigan (Swan River) and Djarlgarra (Canning Rivers) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1macwR9pFMg&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=12&t=0s	Jo Jones
Yousif A.	Mousa	CIC	The Canning River in 1841 and today https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pjq191zO6xM&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=13&t=0s	Petra Helmholz
Pierre	Tenedero	WAM	Photogrammetric analysis of 4th century BC Kyrenia shipwreck https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mz_JckLSFfs&list=PLBU9qESTXuc-MQ4vltY78BnxJXoMJpJjx&index=14&t=0s	Petra Helmholz

Curtin HIVE Intern Showcase

Friday 14 February 2020

Now in its fifth year, the Curtin HIVE Summer Internship Program provides an opportunity for students to gain valuable research project experience in visualisation related topics. Interns are supervised by leading researchers and undertook challenging research projects utilising the resources and support provided by the HIVE. Supervisors and sponsors benefited from the opportunity to explore new techniques and technologies for their research area.

Event Details
Date: Friday 14 February 2020
Time: **Session 1** 9am – 10:40am
Session 2 11:00am – 12:30pm
Session 3 1:00pm – 2:50pm
Session 4 3:10pm – 5pm

Venue: Curtin HIVE, inside John Curtin Gallery, Building 200A, Curtin University, Bentley, Western Australia. Map: maps.curtin.edu.au

Registration
Attendees must register to attend via the link below: <https://tinyurl.com/Sobn28>

Further Information
If you have any special requirements to enable you to participate at this event, please advise when you RSVP. We will contact you to provide assistance. For information about disability services at Curtin, please visit: disability.curtin.edu.au

Make tomorrow better.

Telephone: +61 8 9266 9024
www.curtin.edu.au/hive

©2020 Curtin University. All rights reserved.

Nicholas Brajkovich's project - Legacy Living Lab

Mark Bi's project - Building student engagement in VR

Michael Greif's project - understanding how drug molecules penetrate our skin.

Dior Etherton's project – visualising gastrointestinal disease

Maria Loraine Lu's project – Indian Ocean tectonics

Max Collins' project – OldPerth

Robyn Mae Ong's project – Impact: Beyond the Night Sky

David (Jiande) Xing's project – Mars craters across spectrum

Mitchell O'Sullivan's project – Orbits of Solar System Bodies

Olivia Spear's project – Two Rivers Deep

Pierre Tenedero's project – Kyrenia shipwreck

Yousif A. Mousa's project – Mapping the Canning River

Samuel Bray's project – multiplayer environment for health behaviour

HIVE internships 2020–2021 (Round 6)

The HIVE Intern Showcase was held on 14 Feb 2021. Listing of 2020-2021 HIVE internship students, their projects and links to videos of their final presentations.

Student Firstname	Lastname	Funding	Project Title, and HIVE Intern Showcase Presentation Video Link	Supervisor
Cheryl	Zhou	HIVE	Perception of tourism atmosphere at mine sites: A cross-cultural analysis of atmospheric interventions https://youtu.be/7TRZIOkB52s	Dr Michael Volgger
Chloe	Dann	Medtro nic	Virtual reality-assisted assessment of type B aortic dissection for preoperative planning https://youtu.be/oMZ0nesvkcg	Prof Zhonghua Sun
Ponpot	Jartnillap hand	HS	Eye hear your rhythm; drug effect on the pupil and ECG of the heart https://youtu.be/Pon7UpuaUBk	Dr Rima Caccetta, A/Prof Lisa BG Tee
Joshua	Hyde	SAE	3D modelling of hand movement in children with Cerebral Palsy https://youtu.be/00Ji3fZUVPU	Siavash Khaksar, Prof. Iain Murray
Leigh	Abbott	SAE	Remote guide dog training utilising VR https://youtu.be/3A-GNbZE7xs	Siavash Khaksar, Prof. Iain Murray
Robert	Andriamb ololonaha risoamala la	CIC	Tool for visualising planetary and all-sky astronomical data https://youtu.be/SGX7KMgG0Bk	Dr Anthony Lagain, Professor Gretchen Benedix
Shuchi	Ganesh	WAM	Fremantle Panoramas: Exhibition https://youtu.be/nig8aLbIOs0	Dr Bri McKenzie
Hassan	Elsayed	SAE	Creating 3D models of the Kyrenia shipwreck amphora https://youtu.be/1Ts0fiq6Jfw	Dr David Belton
Zachary	Webb	WAM	Batavia 3D Printing https://youtu.be/j3MjuDXtldw	Jonathan Pillai
Aayush	Bhardwaj	SAE	3D Interior Earth https://youtu.be/dxcgkvCLTdE	Luc Doucet
Chloe	Hall	CIC	The spike protein of SARS-Cov-2: its interactions with antibodies and receptors and the role of mutations https://youtu.be/yTiPxxv-EaI	Prof. Ricardo L. Mancera, Lina Rozano, Chris J. Malajczuk
Scott	Bell	HUM	Visualising 21st Century Boulevards https://youtu.be/hvKtaBETxJw	Dr Parisa Izadpanahi, Professor Peter Newman, Jonathan Pillai, Dr Charlie Hargroves, Dr. Mike Mouritz
Yoshua	Kwizera	FBL	Spatially mapping volunteer demand and supply in Australia's South West https://youtu.be/mpDonwKRr2g	Professor Kirsten Holmes

Curtin HIVE Intern Showcase

Friday 19 February 2021

Now in its sixth year, the Curtin HIVE Summer Internship Program provides an opportunity for students to gain valuable research project experience in visualisation related topics. Interns are supervised by leading researchers and undertake challenging research projects utilising the resources and support provided by the HIVE. Supervisors and sponsors benefit from the opportunity to explore new techniques and technologies for their research area.

At the 2021 HIVE Intern Showcase thirteen students will provide an overview of their projects followed by demonstrations on the HIVE screens – Cylinder, Wedge, Dome, Tile, Hologram Table and Head Mounted Displays.

Event Details:
Date: Friday 19 February 2020
Time: **Session 1:** 9:00am – 10:40am AWST
Session 2: 11:00am – 12:30pm AWST
Session 3: 1:00pm – 2:50pm AWST
Session 4: 3:10pm – 5:00pm AWST

To Attend: Online
 Visit the Curtin HIVE YouTube Channel:
<https://bit.ly/2o7Zysaw>

To Attend: In-Person
 To attend in-person, attendees MUST register via this link: <https://bit.ly/2o7Zysaw>
 Seating capacity is limited.

Venue: Curtin HIVE, inside John Curtin Gallery, Building 200A, Curtin University, Bentley, Western Australia. Map: maps.curtin.edu.au

Further Information
 If you have any special requirements to enable you to participate at this event, please advise when you RSVP. We will contact you to provide assistance. For information about disability services at Curtin, please visit: disability@curtin.edu.au

Make tomorrow better.

Telephone: +61 8 9266 9024
www.curtin.edu.au/hive

HIVE interns during a VR development session.

Cheryl Zhao's project – mine tourism.

Chloe Dann's project – aortic dissection visualisation.

Ponpot Jartnillaphand's project – drug effect VR.

Joshua Hyde's project – 3D modelling of hand movement.

Leigh Abbott's project - guide dog VR

Robert Andriambololonaharisoamalala's project - planetary data

Shuchi Ganesh Athreya's project - Fremantle Panoramas

Hassan Elsayed's project - Kyrenia shipwreck amphora

Zachary Web's project - Batavia 3D Printing

Aayush Bhardwaj's project - 3D interior Earth

Chloe Hall's project - spike protein of SARS-Cov-2

Yoshua Kwizera's project - rural volunteer work force

Scott Bell's project - 21st Century Boulevards

HIVE internships 2021-2022 (Round 7)

HIVE Intern Showcase held on 11 Feb 2022. Videos of the presentations are available at the links below.

Student Firstname	Lastname	Funding	Project Title, and HIVE Intern Showcase Presentation Video Link	Supervisor
Grace	Jones	HIVE/FBL	Spatial mapping the evolution of a global, social movement https://youtu.be/3WdPmroudr4	A/Prof Katharina Wolf
Jade	Geerlings-Batt	Discipline of Medical Radiation Science HDR Research Fund	Enhanced Visualisation of Normal Anatomy with Augmented Reality Superimposed on 3D Printed Models https://youtu.be/UEDrhLKxr3Q	Prof Zhonghua Sun
Yasmine	Mnahy	Australian Diving Safety Foundation	Helping Developing World Diving Harvesters Avoid the Bends – A Humanitarian Project https://youtu.be/htyxVfKAeF8	Dr Peter Buzzacott
Corey	Battersby	Fremantle Ports	Fremantle Harbour Animated Panorama Project https://youtu.be/2xSMUWWRnPI	A/Prof Andrew Woods
Mari	Conradie	HIVE	VR Communicating Robots https://youtu.be/TxFGtu7h0Kc	Dr Eleanor Sandry
Samya	Jabbour	Wirlomin Noongar Language and Stories Project Inc	Mapping Wirlomin: Dwoort Baal Kaat https://youtu.be/N-ICtTJu7h0	Prof Kim Scott
Claudia	Dickson	WAM	Fremantle Historical Panorama Audio-Visual Tours https://youtu.be/5NJH1k3YOg	A/Prof Andrew Woods
Rupert	Cotter	HIVE/SAE	Visualisation of Human Brain Function Captured with Near-infrared Spectroscopy https://youtu.be/MA1insYpJkw	Dr Hanieh Bakhshayesh
Harry	Booker	HIVE/HS	Using non-invasive sensors to classify the quantity and quality of spontaneous movement undertaken by adults in a hospital bed when acutely unwell https://youtu.be/_00Yb7ZYwV0	A/Professor Kylie Hill

 Curtin University

Curtin HIVE Intern Showcase Friday 11 February 2022

Now in its seventh year, the Curtin HIVE Summer Internship Program provides an opportunity for students to gain valuable research project experience in visualisation related topics. Interns are supervised by leading researchers and undertake challenging research projects utilising the resources and support provided by the HIVE. Supervisors, sponsors and industry benefit from the opportunity to explore new techniques and technologies for their research area.

At the 2022 HIVE Intern Showcase nine students will provide an overview of their projects followed by demonstrations on the HIVE screens – Cylinder, Wedge, Tile, Hologram Table and Head Mounted Displays.

Event Details
Date: Friday 11 February 2022
Time: **Session 1:** 9:00am – 10:40am AWST
Session 2: 11:00am – 12:30pm AWST
Session 3: 1:30pm – 3:30pm AWST

To Attend: Online Live
 Visit the Curtin HIVE YouTube Channel:
<https://tinyurl.com/CurtinHIVEYouTube>

To Attend: In-Person
 To attend in-person, attendees MUST register via this link: <https://tinyurl.com/35zb8y>.
 Seating capacity is limited. Proof of vaccination required.

Venue: Curtin HIVE, Building 200A (inside John Curtin Gallery), Curtin University, Bentley, Western Australia. Map: <https://tinyurl.com/mxjwpxz>

Further Information
 If you have any special requirements to enable you to participate at this event, please advise when you RSVP. We will contact you to provide assistance. For information about disability services at Curtin, please visit: disability.curtin.edu.au.

Make tomorrow better. Telephone: +61 8 9266 9024
www.curtin.edu.au/hive

Jade Geerlings-Batt's project - 3D Anatomy Models

Grace Jones' project - Global Social Movement

Claudia Dickson's project - Fremantle Historical Panoramas Audio-Visual Tours

Corey Battersby's project - Fremantle Harbour Animated Panorama

Samya Jabbour's project - Mapping Wirlomin

Mari Conradie's project - VR Communicative Robots

Harrison Booker's project - Non-invasive Sensors to Classify Spontaneous Movement

PREVENTION

1

2

3

4

Follow your bubbles.

Yasmine Mnahy's project - Avoiding the Bends

Rupert Cotter's project – Visualising Human Brain Function

HIVE internships 2022-2023 (Round 8)

HIVE Intern Showcase held on 10 Feb 2023. Videos of the presentations are available at the links below.

Student Firstname	Lastname	Funding	Project Title, and HIVE Intern Showcase Presentation Video Link	Supervisor
David (Jinguo)	Xu	HIVE/FBL	Traffic flow in Perth before, during, and post COVID-19 lockdown https://youtu.be/yyOI5MCvV94	Dr. S Zaung Nau
Wan Hui	Teh	HIVE/HS	Ouch! Using virtual reality to manipulate threat and uncertainty in the experience of pain https://youtu.be/YTLFQir6I3c	Dr. Flavia Di Pietro
Gabe	Fransisco	HIVE	Virtual reality-based treatments for fear of spiders with or without control https://youtu.be/ECiNUAiN5go	Dr. Daniel Rudaizky
Bobae	Bak	HIVE/HUM	How platforms see influencers https://youtu.be/E7m-eE7dkEM	Prof. Crystal Abidin
Qing (Yuqing)	Shi	HIVE/SAE	Gamification of joint rehabilitation using non-invasive sensors https://youtu.be/htSzWa9Jh2I	Siavash Khaksar
Jarod	Haris	WAM	3D Reconstruction of two Western Australian Shipwrecks - the Belinda (1824) and the Star (1880) https://youtu.be/ZH6mdFtVWmQ	A/Prof. Petra Helmholz
Kian	Delpech	Discipline of Medical Radiation Science HDR Research Fund	Clinical value of virtual reality in pre-surgical planning of malignant hepatic tumours https://youtu.be/mzVwdphcoPI	Prof. Zhonghua Sun
Jack	Natalotto	Harry Perkins Institute of Medical Research/Heart and Vascular Research Institute	Interactive 3D Virtual Reality imaging of Abdominopelvic Sarcoma to improve surgical planning https://youtu.be/gxXOm-L7p4I	Prof. Zhonghua Sun
Michael	Landman	Curtin HIVE and Prof Warren Mansell	Is consciousness the rate at which people control the integration of novel information? https://youtu.be/UL_HwY-RXro	Prof. Warren Mansell

Curtin HIVE Intern Showcase Friday 10 February 2023

Now in its eighth year, the Curtin HIVE Summer Internship Program provides an opportunity for students to gain valuable research project experience in visualisation related topics. Interns are supervised by leading researchers and undertake challenging research projects utilising the resources and support provided by the HIVE. Supervisors, sponsors, and industry benefit from the opportunity to explore new techniques and technologies for their research area.

At the 2023 HIVE Intern Showcase nine students will provide an overview of their projects followed by demonstrations on the HIVE screens and Head Mounted Displays.

Event Details
Date: Friday 10 February 2023
Time: **Session 1:** 9:00am – 10:40am AWST
Session 2: 11:00am – 12:30pm AWST
Session 3: 1:30pm – 3:00pm AWST

To Attend: Online Live
Visit the Curtin HIVE YouTube Channel:
<https://www.youtube.com/@ourlinhive>

To Attend: In-Person
To attend in-person, attendees MUST register here:
<https://Curtin-HIVE-InternshipShowcase2023.eventbrite.com.au/>
Seating capacity is limited. RSVP essential.

Venue: Curtin HIVE, Building 200A (inside John Curtin Gallery), Curtin University, Bentley, Western Australia. Map: <https://tinyurl.com/mrxnpxsz>

Further Information
If you have any special requirements to enable you to participate at this event, please advise when you RSVP. We will contact you to provide assistance. For information about disability services at Curtin, please visit: disability.curtin.edu.au

Make tomorrow better.

Telephone: +61 8 9226 9024
www.curtin.edu.au/hive

Gabriel Fransisco's project - VR treatments for fear of spiders

Bobae Bak's project - How platforms see influencers.

Yuqing Shi's project - Gamification of joint rehabilitation

Kian Delpech's project - Pre-surgical planning of malignant hepatic tumours

Wan Hui Teh's project - VR to manipulate threat and uncertainty.

Jack Natalotto's project - VR imaging of Abdominopelvic Sarcoma

David Xu's project - Traffic flow in Perth before, during, and post COVID-19 lockdowns

Jarod Harris's project - 3D Reconstruction of the Belinda (1824) and the Star (1880)

Michael Landman's project - *Is consciousness the rate we integrate novel information?*

HIVE Internship student technical reports are available upon request. HIVE internship reports are listed in Section 2.9 "Technical Reports".

4.2 HIVE Internships leading to ongoing Research Projects

In several cases, HIVE internship projects have been continued on by their main supervisor and/or contributed to ongoing projects.

Chemistry Education in VR (2017)

→ ARC Discovery Project "Using Immersive Virtual Reality to Enhance Students' Science Visualisation" (DP190100160)

Mihye Won, David Treagust, Kok-Sing Tang, et al, Curtin School of Education

The 2017 HIVE internship project "Visualizing Molecular Interactions through Immersive Virtual Reality: Comparison of Students' Interactions with 2D and 3D Models" with intern Adam Mathewson was progressed through a number of steps to a successfully awarded ARC Discovery Project which involves three Curtin PhD students.

Drug Effect VR (2020)

→ ViTools Project

Rema Caccetta, Lisa Tee, et al, Curtin Medical School

Ponpot Jartrillaphand's HIVE internship project "Eye hear your rhythm; drug effect on the pupil and ECG of the heart" has been expanded and continued into a much larger project by the project leads.

Batavia 3D Printing (2020)

→ Brickwrecks exhibition

Andrew Woods, Curtin HIVE; WA Museum

The WA Museum funded the 3D printing of two items (Batavia Timbers and Batavia Portico) from Zak Webb's HIVE internship project "Batavia 3D Printing" for inclusion in the exhibition "Brickwrecks: Sunken Ships in LEGO Bricks" alongside two other items from the HIVE. The exhibition has been shown at the WA Maritime Museum (Fremantle), Museum of Geraldton, Museum of the Great Southern (Albany), Australian National Maritime Museum (Sydney), Vasa Museum Sweden, and The Historic Dockyard Museum Chatham UK.

21st Century Boulevards Project (2020)

→ Humanities Industry Collaborative Project

Parisa Izadpanahi, Jonathan Pillai, Curtin School of Design and the Built Environment; Main Roads Western Australia

Scott Bell's internship project "Visualising 21st Century Boulevards" was progressed through to a Humanities Industry Collaborative Project in collaboration with Main Roads Western Australia.

Historical Panoramas Project (2015, 2020, 2021)

→ "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" Exhibition

Andrew Woods, Bri McKenzie, Jo Li Tay, Curtin HIVE, Curtin MCASI and Curtin DBE; WA Museum

Four separate internship projects (Marcia Schneider (2015), Shuchi Ganesh (2020), Claudia Dickson (2021), and Corey Battersby (2021)) have contributed to work that was shown as part of the "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" exhibition that ran from September 2022 to February 2023 at the WA Maritime Museum in Fremantle. That project has inspired the "Albany Then & Now: Historical Panoramas from Menang Noongar Boodja" exhibition project.

OldPerth Projects (2017, 2017, 2020)

→ OldPerth public website

Andrew Woods, Curtin HIVE; State Library of Western Australia

Three separate internship projects (Will Olman (2017), Mark Shelton (2017), and Max Collins (2020)) contributed to work that was launched as a public website in April 2021 at www.OldPerth.org.au. The OldPerth project was further expanded with a 2023 HIVE internship "Interactive kiosk-based version of 'OldPerth'" supported by the State Library of Western Australia.

VR treatments for fear of spiders (2022)

→ Honours Project User Trials

Daniel Rudaizky, Curtin School of Population Health.

The 2022 HIVE internship "Virtual reality-based treatments for fear of spiders with or without control" by intern Gabe Francisco has progressed further with two Honours student projects by Psychology honours students in the Curtin School of Population Health. The first study is being written up for publication. There are also plans for a third study using this VR framework as the basis.

VR to manipulate threat and uncertainty (2022)

→ Honours Project User Trials and publication

Flavia Di Pietro, Curtin School of Population Health

The 2022 HIVE internship project "Ouch! Using virtual reality to manipulate threat and uncertainty in the experience of pain" by intern Wan Hui Teh was also progressed to a user trial conducted by a Biomedical Sciences Honours (BH-BIOMED) student in the Curtin Medical School.

The first honours student project led to a published journal article: David O'Neill, Morgan Titmus, Wesley Lamont, Wan Hui Teh, Enoch Perimal and Flavia Di Pietro (2024) "Validating the Threat of a Virtual Reality Clinical Environment: A Mixed Methods Study" Appl. Sci. 2024, 14(21), 10009; <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/14/21/10009>

The work was also presented at the Australian Pain Society annual meeting in April 2025, Melbourne.

4.3 Visualisation in Curtin Teaching Units

The HIVE hosts a range of undergraduate and post-graduate class visits, usually on a one-off basis, to provide them with insights into and an understanding of visualisation technologies as they apply to many different disciplines.

Classes have included:

Unit Number	Unit descriptive name	Details
ISYS5009	Societal Impact of Tech Innovation	School of Marketing and Management, Faculty of Business and Law – Dr Brian von Kinsky and Dr Rohini Balapumi. This is a large session which has run over several years – this year accommodating for 100 students. This session particularly focusses on indigenous perspectives and exposes students to the following projects: Virtual Wadjuk, Bidi Walbraanini (Path to Healing), Missions Connect, Historical Panoramas.
SPAT5105 / SPAT3011	Drone Mapping and Applications	Spatial Sciences, School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering – A/Prof Petra Helmholtz. (2023 and previous years)
MKTG5007	Consumer Behaviour Postgraduate	School of Management & Marketing, Faculty of Business and Law - Isaac Cheah
ISYSI6014	Knowledge Management and Intelligent Systems (KMIS)	School of Management & Marketing, Faculty of Business and Law - Tomayess Issa
ARCH5006	Master of Architecture	School of Design & Built Environment, Faculty Humanities - Reena Tiwari
ICTE2000 / ICTE5002	Interactive, Virtual and Immersive Environments	School of Media, Creative Arts and Social Inquiry, Faculty Humanities – Artur Lugmayr, Rebecca Kerr
SCST1000	Introduction to Screen Creativity	MCASI, Faculty of Humanities – Dr Antonio Traverso
SCST2009	Experimental Screens	MCASI, Faculty of Humanities – Dr Antonio Traverso
HIST3002	History Students	MCASI, Faculty of Humanities – Dr Bri McKenzie and Dr Andre Brett. (2022 and previous years)
BIOL3001	Exploring Protein Structure	School of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences - Ricardo Mancera
CHEM2003	Medicinal and Natural Product Chemistry	School of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences - Ricardo Mancera
CHEM3003	Bioanalytical and Biophysical Chemistry	School of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences - Ricardo Mancera
OCCT4010	Bachelor Science Occupational therapy	The 2D version of Bidi Walbraaniny was used with the final year capstone units (N=240)
OCCT6008	Master of Occupational Therapy	The 2D version of Bidi Walbraaniny was used with the final year capstone units (N=240)
PHTY2003	Professional Physiotherapy Practice	The 2D version of Bidi Walbraaniny was used with the final year capstone units (N=200)

PHTY5007	Doctor of Physiotherapy	The 2D version of Bidi Walbraaniny was used with the final year capstone units (N=200)
REHT6002	Master of Clinical Exercise Physiology	There are plans to use the VR version of Bidi Walbraaniny with students in the unit which focuses on management of clients with workers' compensation injuries (like Bardi). Peter Edwards is the unit coordinator and keen to integrate the VR technology.
CHEL	Community Health Education and Leadership	VR headset version of Bidi Walbraaniny was used in fieldwork placements with three different cohorts of Bachelor Science Physiotherapy final year students

These sessions serve to reinforce the importance of visualisation and immersive technologies in various Curtin degree units.

Research Infrastructure

"The HIVE staff do a fantastic job and have been great collaborators in building our defence and space profile."
Gary Hale, Research Office at Curtin

5 Research Infrastructure

5.1 Facility

The HIVE facility commands considerable WOW factor. The HIVE provide impressive and memorable immersive visualisation experiences. The HIVE systems provide a very useful canvas to display a wide range of visualisation projects which support Curtin academic staff to deliver valuable research outcomes.

The five large-scale display systems installed at the HIVE each have different capabilities:

Display	Description	

The **Dome** provides an immersive experience via the four-metre diameter domed screen that entirely fills the observer's primary and peripheral vision. The dome can be used to explore 180° or 360° ultra-realistic panoramas, omnidirectional video and virtual worlds. It has many potential uses, including virtual tourism.

Display Resolution: 4k

Content Types: 180° and 360° stills and video (equirectangular and fish-eye), virtual environments (Unity), data visualisations.

The HIVE also has a range of VR and AR headsets. The HIVE regularly purchases new headsets as they are released by various manufacturers. In 2022 the HIVE purchased three of the new Oculus Quest Pro VR headsets which at the time were the flagship headset for Facebook. These headsets allow for the exploration of VR environments in a completely wireless experience. Applications can either be built for the standalone VR headset to be run without a high powered computer, or take advantage Oculus Air Link technology for wireless streaming of more demanding high resolution graphics from a VR capable computer.

5.2 Recent and Future AV Upgrades

HIVE Cylinder and Dome Display

The projection systems powering the HIVE Cylinder and Dome displays have been upgraded providing a significant improvement of resolution, brightness and image quality. New remote-head laser 4K projectors were installed from Digital Projection (UK). The Curtin HIVE was the very first install of this product worldwide. This was a flag-ship installation for the company and the HIVE featured in a range of promotional advertising and industry articles. The HIVE also appeared on the front page of the industry leading Projector Central website.

The upgraded HIVE Cylinder Display with three Digital Projection Satellite MLS projector heads each providing 4K resolution. The project shown is the Goal Striving Bicycle VR project with (L-R) psychology honours student Sarah Paduano, and supervisor Dr Hugh Ridell, and psychology honours student Merrill Lombard. Photo Credit: Frances Andrijich.

The upgraded HIVE Dome Display fitted with a single Digital Projection Satellite MLS projector head fitted with a fish-eye lens. The project shown is the Mars Crater Detection Algorithm visualisation with (L-R) A/Prof Gretchen Benedix and Dr Anthony Lagain (Curtin Space Science and Technology Centre, School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering) and Dr Anthony Lagain (Curtin Space Science and Technology Centre, School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering). Photo Credit: Frances Andrijich.

HIVE Tiled Display

The HIVE Tiled Display based on ten 55" media grade LCD panels has worked well for 10 years but was starting to show its age with various unpredictable failures - although nothing catastrophic. The HIVE Tiled Display will be replaced by a new system from Barco in October 2023. The new system will have much narrower bezels (<0.5mm vs ~8mm) resulting in significantly less visible borders between the individual screens.

5.3 Staff

A productive and technically competent team has been built up to support visualisation research projects and to run the facility. The HIVE is staffed by a full-time manager, two full-time visualisation technology specialists, and a half-time administrator/coordinator.

Over the period of this report the HIVE team has included: Joshua Hollick, Jesse Helliwell, Susannah Soon, Nick Oliver, Michael Wiebrands, Daniel Adams, Andy Bickers, Wesley Lamont, Carley Tillett, Christine Finlay and Ash Doshi.

The HIVE is led by Associate Professor Andrew Woods.

5.4 Technology Partnerships

Fujitsu

In 2021 Fujitsu Australia partnered with the Curtin HIVE and kindly agreed to loan a high-performance PC for testing purposes on the ARC Linkage project "Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences" (LP180100284). The partnership led to a joint application to the NVIDIA Applied Research Accelerator Program which was successful the following year.

<https://corporate-blog.global.fujitsu.com/apac/2021-09-07/unravelling-the-rich-histories-of-shipwrecks-through-3d-virtual-experiences/>

NVIDIA

In March 2022 NVIDIA selected the HIVE project "Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences" for inclusion in the Applied Research Accelerator Program. In support of the project, NVIDIA donated: 2 - RTX A6000 48GB, an NVLink 2-Slot bridge for A6000 and Deep Learning Course Credits. It was an unrestricted gift to support the project to be used for academic purposes and will be used for shipwreck photogrammetry processing.

Dell

As Curtin's enterprise provider, Dell have provided educational discounts on several high-powered workstations, laptops and GPUs which have been widely used across a number of HIVE research projects. These range from photogrammetric 3D reconstruction processing, VR app development alongside driving the HIVE Cylinder and Tiled displays.

Pawsey Supercomputing Centre

The Pawsey Supercomputing Centre hosts one of the fastest supercomputers in the southern hemisphere. Curtin is a joint venture partner in the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre and our academic staff are active users of the advanced computing and visualisation capabilities at Pawsey. Projects include molecular modelling, photogrammetric 3D reconstruction processing, and computational fluid dynamics simulation.

Vulcan / Navigea / Paul Allen Family Trust

An agreement was reached with Vulcan in 2018 to develop deep water digital still cameras for use on their deep-water ROV for shipwreck survey purposes, following the HMAS AE1 shipwreck survey in 2018. These cameras were developed and delivered to Vulcan and used on one survey. Unfortunately, Mr Paul Allen (Microsoft co-founder) passed away in October 2018 which eventually changed the direction of the trust. In 2020 the spread of COVID grounded the research vessel Petrel and it was subsequently sold in 2022. This project served the positive purpose of continuing development of underwater shipwreck imaging technologies previously developed for the Sydney-Kormoran Project and maintaining technology capability for the P3DR (Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction) focus area of HIVE operations.

Various presentations and dialogues have occurred with a wide range of other industry groups and we hope that these will also lead to productive collaborations as opportunities present.

Sustainable Future

"If I could have my office in this space, I would be here every day!"
Professor Gretchen Benedix,
Today Tonight.

6 Sustainable Future

Sustaining the HIVE operations into the future requires a diversity of activities which provide a return on the investment placed into the HIVE.

6.1 Wider Deployment of HIVE Visualisation Technologies

The Stolen Generations Immersive Hub led by Professor Reena Tiwari at the Business Building on Murray Street in the city has installed a 3m iDome (similar to the HIVE 4m Dome Display) to facilitate the demonstration of MissionsConnect visualisations. The HIVE team supported the acquisition of this display and provided the software used to display 360° video sequences created of the mission sites.

The Western Australian Museum has purchased a screen that is an exact clone of the HIVE Cylinder Screen. This screen was initially used for the "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" exhibition (Sept 2022 – Feb 2023) and was also used for the "Australia II: 40 years on" exhibition (opening Sept 2023). This screen will be perfect for future shipwreck related exhibitions at the WA Maritime Museum.

The HIVE team advised on the installation of the new large LED screen at the northern entry to the Curtin Library on Level 3. The HIVE team provided content to display on this screen when it was commissioned.

Many HIVE supported projects across the University are being run using Head-Mounted Displays specified by the HIVE team.

6.2 Key External Collaborations

The HIVE has developed and supported a number of key collaborations with external partners.

Western Australian Museum

Curtin University and the Western Australian museum have been collaborating and working together at least since the early 1970s. Today, the HIVE have been actively engaging with the WA Museum on a wide range of projects.

On 12 January 2018 a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between Curtin and WA Museum to facilitate further collaboration between the two groups.

A brief summary of recent collaborative projects and outcomes/outputs is as follows:

- (2011+) Sydney-Kormoran Project
 - (2011-2015) Project and equipment development
 - (2015) 3D Imaging survey expedition
 - (2015+) Data processing and workflow software development
 - (2016) "From Great Depths" book
 - (2016) "From Great Depths" 3D short film
 - (2016) "From Great Depths" exhibit at Museum of Geraldton
 - (2018) "Fire on the Water" 3D short film
 - (2018) "Fire on the Water" exhibit at Shark Bay Discovery Centre
 - (2019+) "Deep Light" travelling exhibition

- (2013-2018) ARC Linkage Roaring 40s project
 - Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction (P3DR) of Batavia underwater photography
 - (2016) Public launch of guided tour version of Beacon Virtua
 - (2016) Touch-screen version of Beacon Virtua for Travellers and Traders Exhibition
 - (2018) Beacon Virtua installed at Museum of Geraldton (May)
- (2017-2023) P3DR of *Santo Antonio de Tanna* underwater photography (HIVE/WAM internship, Lachlan Shaw, supervised by Dr Petra Helmholtz, EPS)
- (2019-2022) P3DR of *Kyrenia* underwater photography (two HIVE/WAM internships, Pierre Tenedero, Hassan Elsayed)
- (2018) 3D imaging survey of HMAS *AE1* and P3DR processing
- (2018-2019) Transforming the journals of Francisco Pelseart (HIVE/WAM internship, Eric Jackson, supervised by David McMeekin, EECMS)
- (2019-ongoing) ARC Linkage Project "Photogrammetric Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences"
- (2021-2023) "Brickwrecks: Sunken Ships in Lego Bricks" exhibition
 - (2021) Batavia 3D Printing project (HIVE WAM internship, Zachary Web, supervised by Jonathan Pillai, DBE)
- (2022-2023) "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" exhibition
 - (2021) Fremantle Panoramas Exhibition Options (HIVE/WAM internship, Shuchi Athreya, supervised by Bri McKenzie, MCASI)
 - (2022) Fremantle Historical Panoramas Audio-Visual Tours project (HIVE/WAM internship, Claudia Dickson)
- (2022-2023) 3D reconstruction of *Belinda* and *Star* WA shipwrecks (HIVE/WA Museum internship, Jarod Harris)

See Section 3.10 "Exhibitions" for additional information.

Additionally, Andrew Woods is the Curtin representative on the WA Museum Maritime Archaeology Advisory Committee (MAAC).

State Library of Western Australia

The HIVE and SLWA started collaborating on two student projects in 2015 and since that time that collaboration has continued and great value has been achieved from their collective strengths.

A brief summary of the collaborative projects is as follows:

- (2015) Historical Panoramas project (HIVE/SLWA internship, Marcia Schneider)
- (2015) Photographic Archive Visualisation in 3D project (HIVE/SLWA internship, Adam Greenfeld)
- (2016) Launched www.HistoricalPanoramas.com.au
- (2016) Historical Image Archive Browser (Michael Wiebrands – HIVE volunteer)
- (2016) Feature Matching the SLWA collection (Pawsey/HIVE/SLWA internship, Chris Norman)
- (2017) Historical Panoramas Stage 2 (Marcia Schneider and Wesley Lamont)
- (2017) Commendation Award at WA Heritage Awards for Historical Panoramas Project
- (2017) Geo-locating Historical Panoramas (HIVE/SLWA internship, Brent Scheer)
- (2017) P3DR and Geolocation Visualisation (HIVE/SLWA internship, Will Olman)
- (2017) Historical Image Classification (Pawsey internship, Mark Shelton)
- (2018) OldPerth (Geolocated Historical Images Web Portal) – demonstrated at SLWA Disrupted Festival

- (2018-2019) 'Living' historical documents project (HIVE/SLWA internship, Isaac McCormack, supervised by Dr Artur Lugmayr, MCASI)
- (2020) launched www.OldPerth.org.au
- (2020-2021) Historical Panoramas touch-screen featured in the "Creating Perth" exhibition at SLWA
- (2022) SLWA supported the "Fremantle Then & Now: Historical Panoramas" exhibition

See Section 3.10 "Exhibitions" for additional information.

Pawsey Supercomputing Centre

The Pawsey Centre directly supports the ARC Linkage Project "Photogrammetric Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences" via the provision of supercomputer time and technical support for software development.

Other Existing and Developing Collaborations

- Defence Science & Technology Group (DSTG) supported Maritime Visualisation project led by Tele Tan and Susannah Soon
- Australian National Maritime Museum (ANMM) is supporting the ARC Linkage Project "Photogrammetric Reconstruction for Underwater Virtual Heritage Experiences"

7 References

Curtin HIVE (Hub for Immersive Visualisation and eResearch), Curtin University, Perth, Western Australia. Research Organisation ID. <https://ror.org/00hjt591>

Andrew E. Johnson, Luc Renambot, G. Elisabeta Marai, Daria Tsoupikova, Michael E. Papka, Lance Long, Dana Plepys, Jonas Talandis, Maxine D. Brown, Jason Leigh, Daniel J. Sandin, Thomas A. DeFanti; "Electronic Visualization Laboratory's 50th Anniversary Retrospective: Look to the Future, Build on the Past". PRESENCE: Virtual and Augmented Reality 2024; 33 77–127. https://doi.org/10.1162/pres_a_00421

Wiebrands, Michael; Malajczuk, Chris J; Woods, Andrew J; Rohl, Andrew L; Mancera, Ricardo L; (2018). Molecular dynamics visualization (MDV): stereoscopic 3D display of biomolecular structure and interactions using the Unity game engine. *Journal of integrative bioinformatics*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2018-0010>

Woods, Andrew; Bourke, Paul; Oliver, Nick; (2018). Beacon Virtua. 2018 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR), 844-844. <https://doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/VR.2018.8446239>

Joseph, Pauline; (2018). Developing visualisation prototypes from EZproxy server logs to understand information seeking behavior of Curtin Library users. *Preservation, Digital Technologies & Culture*, 47(1), 23-26. <http://doi.org/10.1515/pdct-2018-0007>

Sommer, Björn; Baaden, Marc; Krone, Michael; Woods, Andrew; (2018). From Virtual Reality to Immersive Analytics in Bioinformatics. *Journal of integrative bioinformatics*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2018-0043>

Broderick, M; (2018). Fading Lights: Digital Visualization and the Legacy of Hiroshima and Nagasaki. <https://scholar.google.com.au/scholar?oi=bibs&cluster=2850133461394571749&btnI=1&hl=en> [Book Chapter]

O'Halloran, Kay L; Tan, Sabine; Wiebrands, Michael; Sheffield, Rachel; Wignell, Peter; Turner, Paul; (2018). The Multimodal Classroom in the Digital Age: The Use of 360 Degree Videos for Online Teaching and Learning. *Multimodality Across Classrooms*, 84-102. <http://doi.org/10.4324/9780203701072> [Book Chapter]

Greenfeld, Adam; Lugmayr, Artur; Lamont, Wesley; (2018). Comparative Reality: Measuring User Experience and Emotion in Immersive Virtual Environments. 2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR), 204-209. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00048> [Conference Paper]

Woods, Andrew J; Holliman, Nicolas S; Favalora, Gregg E; Kawai, Takashi; Sommer, Björn; (2018). Stereoscopic Displays and Applications XXIX-Introduction. *Electronic Imaging*, 2018(4), 476-1-476-7. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2018.04.SDA-476>

Sun, Zhonghua; (2018). Coronary CT Angiography in the Quantitative Analysis of Coronary Plaques. https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814725620_0001

Kear, Robin; Joranson, Kate; (2018). Digital humanities, libraries, and partnerships: a critical examination of labor, networks, and community. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2016-0-01794-1>

Sun, Zhonghua; (2018). 3D Printing As a New Technique in Management of Right Heart Pathology. *Right Heart Pathology: From Mechanism to Management*, 641-653. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73764-5_38

Sun, Zhonghua; Liu, Dongting; (2018). A systematic review of clinical value of three-dimensional printing in renal disease. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*, 8(3), 311. <https://doi.org/10.21037/qims.2018.03.09>

Liu, Dongting; Sun, Zhonghua; Chaichana, Thanapong; Ducke, Werner; Fan, Zhanming; (2018). Patient-specific 3D printed models of renal tumours using home-made 3D printer in comparison with commercial 3D printer. *Journal of Medical Imaging and Health Informatics*, 8(2), 303-308. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jmih.2018.2294>

Givehchi, Sogol; Safari, Mohammad Javad; Tan, Sock Keow; Shah, Mohammad Nazri Bin Md; Sani, Fadhli Bin Mohamed; Azman, Raja Rizal; Sun, Zhonghua; Yeong, Chai Hong; Ng, Kwan Hoong; Wong, Jeannie Hsiu Ding; (2018). Measurement of coronary bifurcation angle with coronary CT angiography: A phantom study. *Physica Medica*, 45, 198-204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2017.09.137>

Cozens, Paul; McLeod, Sam; Matthews, Jane; (2018). Visual representations in crime prevention: exploring the use of building information modelling (BIM) to investigate burglary and crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED). *Crime Prevention and Community Safety*, 20(2), 63-83. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41300-018-0039-6>

- Chu, Michael; Matthews, Jane; Love, Peter ED; (2018). Integrating mobile building information modelling and augmented reality systems: an experimental study. *Automation in Construction*, 85, 305-316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2017.10.032>
- O'Halloran, Kay L; Tan, Sabine; Pham, Duc-Son; Bateman, John; Vande Moere, Andrew; (2018). A digital mixed methods research design: Integrating multimodal analysis with data mining and information visualization for big data analytics. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 12(1), 11263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689816651015>
- Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L; (2018). Effect of Optic Flow on Postural Control in Children and Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorder. *Neuroscience*, 393, 138-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2018.09.047>
- Lugmayr, Artur; Lim, Yi Juin; Hollick, Joshua; Khuu, Joyce; Chan, Felix; (2018). Financial Data Visualization in 3D on Immersive Virtual Reality Displays. *International Workshop on Enterprise Applications, Markets and Services in the Finance Industry*, 118-130. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19037-8_8
- Soon, Susannah; Lugmayr, Artur; Woods, Andrew; Tan, Tele; (2018). Understanding Head-Mounted Display FOV in Maritime Search and Rescue Object Detection. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 116-119. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00023>
- Soon, Susannah; Lugmayr, Artur; Woods, Andrew; Tan, Tele; (2018). Head-Mounted FOV Simulator for User Testing of Maritime Object Detection Tasks. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 183-184. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00039>
- Zhu, Kening; Lugmayr, Artur; Ma, Xiaojuan; Mueller, Florian Floyd; Engelke, Ulrich; Simoff, Simeon; Trescak, Tomas; Bogdavych, Anton; Aguilar, Juan Rodriguez; Vu, Huyen; (2018). Interface and Experience Design with AI for VR/AR (DAIVAR'18) and AI/ML for Immersive Simulations (AMISIM'18). *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*, 227-228. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AIVR.2018.00052>
- Beynon, David; Datta, Sambit; Hollick, Joshua; (2018). Digitised connections: Reflections on the image analysis and spatial modelling of Southeast Asian temples. *Proceedings of digital cultural heritage: FUTURE VISIONS Brisbane 2017 Conference*, 36-52. https://dro.deakin.edu.au/articles/conference_contribution/Digitised_connections_reflections_on_the_image_analysis_and_spatial_modelling_of_Southeast_Asian_temples/21027187/1
- Briggs, Peter; (2018). "Research Vessel Petrel Baseline Survey of HMAS AE1" Australian National Maritime Museum. https://www.sea.museum/-/media/anmm/files/support/ae1_petrel_report-final-print-version.pdf?la=en
- Hunter, J; Woods, A; (2018). Imaging Australia's First Naval Loss. *Signals Magazine*, 2-7.
- Woods, Andrew; Oliver, Nick; Bourke, Paul; Green, Jeremy; Paterson, Alistair; (2019). Beacon Virtua: A Virtual Reality Simulation Detailing the Recent and Shipwreck History of Beacon Island, Western Australia. *3D Recording and Interpretation for Maritime Archaeology*, 197-210. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03635-5_13
- Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L; (2019). Effect of visual information on postural control in adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 49, 4731-4739. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-018-3634-6>
- O'Halloran, Kay L; Tan, Sabine; Wignell, Peter; Bateman, John A; Pham, Duc-Son; Grossman, Michele; Moere, Andrew Vande; (2019). Interpreting text and image relations in violent extremist discourse: A mixed methods approach for big data analytics. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 31(3), 454-474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2016.1233871>
- Won, Mihye; Mocerino, Mauro; Tang, Kok-Sing; Treagust, David F; Tasker, Roy; (2019). Interactive immersive virtual reality to enhance students' visualisation of complex molecules. *Research and Practice in Chemistry Education: Advances from the 25th IUPAC International Conference on Chemistry Education 2018*, 51-64. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-6998-8_4
- Joseph, Pauline; Kent, Aaron Justin; Green, Peter Damian; Robinson, Matthew; Bellenger, Amanda; (2019). Analysis of EZproxy server logs to visualise research activity in Curtin's online library. *Library Hi Tech*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-04-2018-0050>

- Adams, Daniel; Steven Pham, Tri Tai; Watts, Kale; Ramakrishnan, Subhash; Ackland, Emily; Tran Ly, Ham; Hollick, Joshua; Woods, Andrew; (2019). "Development of a Camera-Based Projection Mapping System for Non-Flat Surfaces" in *Stereoscopic Displays and Applications, Electronic Imaging*, 2019(3), 660-1-660-8. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2019.3.SDA-660>
- Woods, Andrew J; Holliman, Nicolas S; (2019). "30 Years of the Stereoscopic Displays and Applications conference-Milestones and Statistics" in *Stereoscopic Displays and Applications, Electronic Imaging*, 2019(3), C03-1-C03-12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2019.3.SDA-C03>
- Woods, Andrew J; Holliman, Nicolas S; Favalora, Gregg E; Kawai, Takashi; Sommer, Björn; (2019). "30th Annual Stereoscopic Displays and Applications Conference-Introduction" in *Stereoscopic Displays and Applications, Electronic Imaging*, 2019(3), B03-1-B03-7. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2019.3.SDA-B03>
- Lim, Yi Huey; Lee, Hoe C; Falkmer, Torbjörn; Allison, Garry T; Tan, Tele; Lee, Wee Lih; Morris, Susan L; (2019). Postural control adaptation to optic flow in children and adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Gait & Posture*, 72, 175-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2019.06.007>
- Albahri, Mohammed; Barifcani, Ahmed; Dwivedi, Deepak; Iglauer, Stefan; Lebedev, Maxim; MacLeod, Ian D; Machuca, Laura L; (2019). X-ray micro-computed tomography analysis of accumulated corrosion products in deep-water shipwrecks. *Materials and Corrosion*, 70(11), 1977-1998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/maco.201910842>
- Martin, Jacob W; de Tomas, Carla; Suarez-Martinez, Irene; Kraft, Markus; Marks, Nigel A; (2019). Topology of disordered 3D graphene networks. *Physical Review Letters*, 123(11), 116105. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.123.116105>
- Holliman, Nicolas S; Coltekin, Arzu; Fernstad, Sara J; McLaughlin, Lucy; Simpson, Michael D; Woods, Andrew J; (2019). Visual entropy and the visualization of uncertainty. arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.12879. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1907.12879>
- Lee, Shen-yuan; Squelch, Andrew; Sun, Zhonghua; (2019). Quantitative assessment of 3D printed model accuracy in delineating the normal heart anatomy based on in vitro phantom experiments. *Australasian Medical Journal*. <http://doi.org/10.35841/1836-1935.12.10.276-284>
- Sun, Zhonghua; Jansen, Shirley; (2019). Personalized 3D printed coronary models in coronary stenting. *Quantitative Imaging in Medicine and Surgery*, 9(8), 1356. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8040522>
- Lau, Ivan Wen Wen; Sun, Zhonghua; (2019). Dimensional Accuracy and Clinical Value of 3D Printed Models in Congenital Heart Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 8(9), 1483. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8091483>
- Sun, Zhonghua; Lau, Ivan; Wong, Yin How; Yeong, Chai Hong; (2019). Personalized three-dimensional printed models in congenital heart disease. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 8(4), 522. <https://doi.org/10.21037%2Fqims.2019.06.21>
- Lau, Ivan; Wong, Yin How; Yeong, Chai Hong; Aziz, Yang Faridah Abdul; Sari, Nor Ashikin Md; Hashim, Shahrul Amry; Sun, Zhonghua; (2019). Quantitative and qualitative comparison of low-and high-cost 3D-printed heart models. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*, 9(1), 107. <https://doi.org/10.21037%2Fqims.2019.01.02>
- Aldosari, Sultan; Jansen, Shirley; Sun, Zhonghua; (2019). Patient-specific 3D printed pulmonary artery model with simulation of peripheral pulmonary embolism for developing optimal computed tomography pulmonary angiography protocols. *Quantitative imaging in medicine and surgery*, 9(1), 75. <https://doi.org/10.21037%2Fqims.2018.10.13>
- Fordham, Drew; Lewis, David; Bellenger, Amanda; (2019). Swimming In The Deep End: Curtin Library's Deep Dive Into Data.... <https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/jatul/2019/value/2/>
- Brant, Nicholas; (2019). Seeing clearly. *Create*, 5(8). <https://search.informit.org/doi/pdf/10.3316/informit.906065511533282>
- Dawson, Beata; Joseph, Pauline; Champion, Erik; (2019). The story of the Markham car collection: a cross-platform panoramic tour of contested heritage. *Collections*, 15(1), 62-86. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550190619832381>

- Benedix, GK; Lagain, A; Chai, K; Meka, S; Anderson, S; Norman, C; Bland, PA; Paxman, J; Towner, MC; Tan, T; (2020). Deriving Surface Ages on Mars using Automated Crater Counting. *Earth and Space Science*, e2019EA001005. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019EA001005>
- Sun, Zhonghua; (2020). Use of three-dimensional printing in the development of optimal cardiac CT scanning protocols. *Current medical imaging*, 16(8), 967-977. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1573405616666200124124140>
- Tiwari, Reena; Stephens, John Richard; (2020). Trauma and healing at Western Australia's former native missions. *AlterNative: An International Journal of Indigenous Peoples*, 16(3), 248-258. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1177180120948277>
- Woods, Andrew; Oliver, Nick; Hollick, Joshua; Green, Jeremy; Baker, Patrick; (2020). 3D Reconstruction of the Batavia (1629) Wreck Site from Historical (1970s) Photography. *Shared Heritage: Proceedings of the Sixth International Congress for Underwater Archaeology 2016*, 382-391. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/5245226#page=40>
- Helmholz, Petra; Belton, David; Oliver, Nick; Hollick, Joshua; Woods, Andrew; (2020). The Influence of the Point Cloud Comparison Methods on the Verification of Point Clouds Using the Batavia Reconstruction as a Case Study. *IKUWA6 Shared Heritage: Proceedings of the Sixth International Congress for Underwater Archaeology*, 6, 370-381. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11937/81628>
- Rickard, William DA; Ramos Coelho, Jéssica Fernanda; Hollick, Joshua; Soon, Susannah; Woods, Andrew; (2020). Application of Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction to Scanning Electron Microscopy: Considerations for Volume Analysis. *Journal of Imaging Science and Technology*, 64(6), 60404-1-60404-9. <https://doi.org/10.2352/J.ImagingSci.Technol.2020.64.6.060404>
- Green, Jeremy; Paterson, Alistair; (2020). Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties: Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks, UWA Publishing. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias->
- Green, Jeremy; Shaw, Lachlan; Hollick, Joshua; Woods, Andrew; Helmholz, Petra; Belton, David; (2020). "Working with Legacy Data: Santo Antonio de Tanna." in "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties - Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks", 239-245. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias->
- Woods, Andrew; Oliver, Nick; Hollick, Joshua; Green, Jeremy; Baker, Patrick; (2020). "3D Reconstruction of the Batavia Wreck Site." in "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties - Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks", 232-238. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias->
- Woods, Andrew; Bourke, Paul; Oliver, Nick; (2020). "Beacon Virtua." in "Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties - Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks", 223-232. <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/publications/shipwrecks-of-the-roaring-forties-researching-some-of-australias->
- Adams, Daniel; Baker, Patrick; McAllister, Madeline; Winton, Trevor; Woods, Andrew; (2020). Successful Creation of a Photogrammetric Model of the James Matthews (1841) Wrecksite from Legacy Photography. *Australasian Journal of Maritime Archaeology*, 44, 71-89. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357822825_Successful_3D_digital_modelling_of_the_James_Matthews_1841_excavated_wrecksite_using_legacy_photography
- Etherton, Dior; Tee, Lisa; Tillett, Carley; Wong, Yin Hong; Yeong, Chai Hong; Sun, Zhonghua; (2020). 3D visualization and 3D printing in abnormal gastrointestinal system manifestations of situs ambiguus. *Quantitative Imaging in Medicine and Surgery*, 10(9), 1877. <https://doi.org/10.21037/qims-20-661>
- Helmholz, P; Mousa, Y; Snow, T; Haebich, A; Piggot, G; Tonkin, J; Lamont, W; (2020). GEO-LOCATING HISTORICAL SURVEY DATA AND IMAGES—A CASE STUDY FOR THE CANNING RIVER, PERTH, WESTERN AUSTRALIA. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*, 43. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B4-2020-575-2020>
- Woods, Andrew J; (2021). Sourcing and Qualifying Passive Polarised 3D TVs. *Electronic Imaging*, 2021(2), 100-1-100-6. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2021.2.SDA-100>

- Beynon, David; Datta, Sambit; (2021). Architectonic connections: virtual reconstruction to disseminate understanding of South and Southeast Asian temples. *Access and Control in Digital Humanities*, 130-152. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429259616>
- Lagain, A; Benedix, GK; Servis, K; Baratoux, David; Doucet, LS; Rajšić, A; Devillepoix, HAR; Bland, PA; Towner, MC; Sansom, EK; (2021). The Tharsis mantle source of depleted shergottites revealed by 90 million impact craters. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), 6352. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26648-3>
- Lagain, Anthony; Servis, Konstantinos; Benedix, GK; Norman, Christopher; Anderson, Seamus; Bland, PA; (2021). Model age derivation of large martian impact craters, using automatic crater counting methods. *Earth and Space Science*, 8(2), e2020EA001598. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001598>
- Pears, Jacob B; Tillett, Carley; Tahara, Rui; Larsson, Hans CE; Boisvert, Catherine A; (2022). Imaging With the Past: Revealing the Complexity of Chimaeroid Pelvic Musculature Anatomy and Development. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 9, 999. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.812561>
- Duong, Van Chien; Sung, Billy; Barber, Matthew; Regolini, Emma; Teah, Min; (2022). Exploring store atmospherics of FMCG brands flagship stores with an immersive 180-degree dome-shaped display. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 32(4), 554-578. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21639159.2022.2033131>
- Duong, Van Chien; Regolini, Emma; Sung, Billy; Teah, Min; Hatton-Jones, Siobhan; (2022). Is more really better for in-store experience? A psychophysiological experiment on sensory modalities. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 39(2), 218-229. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-02-2020-3656>
- McCarthy, John Kennington; (2022). Jeremy Green and Alistair Paterson, Editors: *Shipwrecks of the Roaring Forties: Researching Some of Australia's Earliest Shipwrecks*: UWA Publishing, Crawley, 2020, 316 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-021-09321-0>
- Lagain, Anthony; Kreslavsky, Mikhail; Baratoux, David; Liu, Yebo; Devillepoix, Hadrien; Bland, Philip; Benedix, Gretchen K; Doucet, Luc S; Servis, Konstantinos; (2022). Has the impact flux of small and large asteroids varied through time on Mars, the Earth and the Moon?. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 579, 117362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2021.117362>
- Lagain, A; Benedix, GK; Servis, K; Baratoux, D; Doucet, L-S; Rajšić, A; Devillepoix, HAR; Bland, PA; Towner, MC; Sansom, E; (2022). The Tharsis Mantle Source of Depleted Shergottites Revealed by 90 Million Impact Craters. *LPI Contributions*, 2678, 1011. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2022LPICo2678.1011L>
- Geerlings-Batt, Jade; Tillett, Carley; Gupta, Ashu; Sun, Zhonghua; (2022). Enhanced Visualisation of Normal Anatomy with Potential Use of Augmented Reality Superimposed on Three-Dimensional Printed Models. *Micromachines*, 13(10), 1701. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi13101701>
- Khaksar, Siavash; Pieters, Stefanie; Borazjani, Bitia; Hyde, Joshua; Booker, Harrison; Khokhar, Adil; Murray, Iain; Campbell, Amity; (2022). Posture Monitoring and Correction Exercises for Workers in Hostile Environments Utilizing Non-Invasive Sensors: Algorithm Development and Validation. *MDPI Sensors*, 22(24), 9618. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22249618>
- Pears, Jacob B; Tillett, Carley; Tahara, Rui; Larsson, Hans CE; Trinajstić, Kate; Boisvert, Catherine A; (2022). The Development of the Chimaeroid Pelvic Skeleton and the Evolution of Chondrichthyan Pelvic Fins. *Journal of Developmental Biology*, 10(4), 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jdb10040053>
- Green, Jeremy; Adams, Daniel; Woods, Andrew; (2022). The Kyrenia Ship Three-dimensional Modelling Project. *Australasian Institute for Maritime Archaeology*, 39(2), 45112.
- Duncan, Brad; (2022). Wollongbar (II) Shipwreck Inspections 2019 Off Crescent Head, NSW. <https://heritagensw.intersearch.com.au/heritagenswjsui/handle/1/10662>
- Won, Mihye; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Matovu, Henry; Treagust, David F; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Park, Jungho; Mocerino, Mauro; Tasker, Roy; (2022). Diverse approaches to learning with immersion virtual reality identified from a systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 195104701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104701>
- Matovu, Henry; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Won, Mihye; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Treagust, David F; Mocerino, Mauro; Tasker, Roy; (2022). Immersive virtual reality for science learning: Design, implementation, and evaluation. *Studies in Science Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057267.2022.2082680>

- Lau, Ivan; Gupta, Ashu; Ihdahid, Abdul; Sun, Zhonghua; (2022). Clinical Applications of Mixed Reality and 3D Printing in Congenital Heart Disease. *Biomolecules*, 12111548. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12111548>
- Zhao, Ruzhen; Volgger, Michael; Thomas, Ben; Guo, Xiumei; (2022). Perception of tourism atmosphere at mine sites: A cross-cultural analysis of atmospheric interventions. *CAUTHE 2022 Conference Online: Shaping the Next Normal in Tourism, Hospitality and Events: Proceedings of the 32nd Annual Conference*, 638-641. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.417838712901453>
- Volgger, M; Zhao, R; Sung, B; Marques, S; (2022). Atmospheric interventions in anthropogenic and natural landscapes: An inter-cultural analysis. *International colloquium on 'Quo vadis research on spatial atmospheres?'*.
- Titmus, Morgan; Whittaker, Gary; Radunski, Milo; Ellery, Paul; IR de Oliveira, Beatriz; Radley, Hannah; Helmholz, Petra; Sun, Zhonghua; (2023). A workflow for the creation of photorealistic 3D cadaveric models using photogrammetry. *Journal of Anatomy*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joa.13872>
- Delpech, Kian; Tillett, Carley; Bhandari, Mayank; Sun, Zhonghua; (2023). Investigation of 3D virtual reality in pre-surgical planning of malignant hepatic tumours. *Australasian Medical Journal*, 16(3), 556-577. <https://doi.org/10.21767/AMJ.2023.3942>
- Tang, William; Wang, Shijie; Sun, Zhonghua; (2023). Role of three-dimensional printing and virtual reality in medical applications: A medical student's reflection. *Australasian Medical Journal*, 16(4), 604-607. <https://doi.org/10.21767/AMJ.2023.3947>
- Williams, Ally; Tillett, Carley; Wong, Yin How; Yeong, Chai Hong; Sun, Zhonghua; (2023). How 3D Printing Software Enhances and Rewards Student Learning of Brain Anatomy. *Australasian Medical Journal*, 16(3), 552-555. <https://doi.org/10.21767/AMJ.2023.3936>
- Riddell, Hugh; Lamont, Wesley; Lombard, Merrill; Paduano, Sarah; Maltagliati, Silvio; Gucciardi, Daniel F; Ntoumanis, Nikos; (2023). Autonomous motivation promotes goal attainment through the conscious investment of effort, but mental contrasting with implementation intentions makes goal striving easier. *The Journal of Social Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.2022.2163610>
- Matovu, Henry; Won, Mihye; Treagust, David Franklin; Mocerino, Mauro; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Tasker, Roy; (2023). Analysis of students' diagrams of water molecules in snowflakes to reveal their conceptual understanding of hydrogen bonds. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RP00175F>
- Matovu, Henry; Won, Mihye; Treagust, David Franklin; Ungu, Dewi Ayu Kencana; Mocerino, Mauro; Tsai, Chin-Chung; Tasker, Roy; (2023). Change in students' explanation of the shape of snowflakes after collaborative immersive virtual reality. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RP00176D>
- Lim, Yi Huey; (2019). *The Postural Control System in Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Insights from Exploring the Effects of Visual Information on Postural Control*, Curtin University PhD Thesis. <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/bitstream/handle/20.500.11937/78788/Lim%20Y%20H%202019%20partial.pdf?sequence=1>
- Soon, S., Tan, T., Woods, A., 2018, Exploring Target Detection and Tracking in Real-Time Video of Submarine Periscope Imagery for Head Mounted Displays, Technical Report, 55p., Curtin University.
- Soon, S., Tan, T., 2019, Factors Affecting the Human Visual Search Task for Maritime Imagery, Technical Report, 15pp., Curtin University. Prepared for Defence Science Technology Group. [Project Report]
- Allahham, A., Miljkovic, K., 2019, Scientific Visualisation of Asteroid Strikes and Cratered Worlds. Final Report, 28pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Thomas, A., de Tomas, C., 2019, Visualizing carbon nanostructures: a realistic model of activated carbons. Final Report, 28pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Cheng, B., Won, M., 2019, Shooting arrows in an immersive virtual reality: experiencing and modelling science experiments to learn Newtonian physics concepts. Final Report, 34pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Nagarsheth, D., Ciccarelli, M., McMahon, D., Soon, S., Wiebrands, M., 2019, A mobile educational resource for the safe and efficient use of public transportation in Perth. Final Report, 25pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Jackson, E., McMeekin, D., Woods, A., Green, J., 2019, Transforming the Journals of Francisco Pelsaert, Commander of the Dutch VOC Ship Batavia, into a Web Archive moving towards Linked Open Data. Final Report, 26pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Found, L., Elders, C., Cunneen, J., 2019, Application of automatic horizon picking software to seismic interpretation. Final Report, 32pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

McCormack, I., Lugmayr, A., Woods, A., McKenzie, T., Underwood, A., 2019, Living Historical Documents - The Diaries of Frances Bussell (1807-1881). Final Report, 23pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Xing, D(J)., Miljkovic, K., Lagain, A., Soon, S., Wiebrands, M., 2020, Mars Craters. Final Report, 17pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Etherton, D., Tee, L., Sun, Z., Tillett, C., 2020, 3D Visualisation of Abnormal Gastrointestinal System – When the Right is Not Right, and the Left is Not Left. Final Report, 16pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Lu, M., Elders, C., Olierook, H., 2020, Indian Ocean Tectonics from Detailed Bathymetry Data. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Bi, M., Walker, R., Morey, V., Dinham, J., Dobson, M., Sims, C., Lamont, W., 2020, Building student engagement and supporting learning through interactive virtual reality environments. Final Report, 43pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Collins, M., Woods, A., Lamont, W., Jones, D., 2020, OldPerth – Mapping Historical Photographs of Perth. Final Report, 68pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Greif, M., Mancera, R., Ruiz-Perez, L., 2020, What happens when you rub on that cream? Understanding how drug molecules penetrate our skin by molecular visualization. Final Report, 13pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

O'Sullivan, M., Shoher, P., Towner, M., Tillett, C., 2020, Visualising the Orbits of Small Solar System Bodies Using Data from the Desert Fireball Network. Final Report, 47pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Spear, O., Jones, J., Glitsos, L., Jones, C., Tillett, C., 2020, Two Rivers Deep. Final Report, 29pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Tenedero, P., Helmholz, P., Green, J., Woods, J., 2020, Photogrammetric Analysis of 4th Century BC Kyrenia Shipwreck. Final Report, 30pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Mousa, Y., Helmholz, P., Snow, T., Haebich, H., 2020, The Canning River in 1841 and today. Final Report, 22pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Soon, S., Collins, M., McNair, J., Tan, T., 2021, Human Detection and Display Modalities. Final Report, 67pp., Curtin University. Prepared for Defence Science Technology Group (DSTG). [Project Report]

Zhao, R(C)., Volgger, M., Thomas, B., Guo, X., Lamont, W., Tillett, C., 2021, Using Virtual Reality to Explore the Perception of Tourism Atmospheres at Mine Sites: A Cross-Cultural Analysis of Atmospheric Interventions. Final Report, 63pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Hall, C., Mancera, R., Malajczuk, C., Rozano, L., 2021, The spike protein of SARS-Cov-2: its interactions with antibodies and receptors and the role of mutations. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Bell, S., Izadpanahi, P., Pillai, J., Newman, P., Mouritz, M., Hargroves, C., Lamont, W., Woods, A., 2021, Visualising 21st Century Boulevards. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Athreya, S., McKenzie, B., Tillett, C., Woods, A., Wallis-Smith, D., Edwards, T., 2021, Fremantle Panoramas: Exhibition. Final Report, 25pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Dann, C., Sun, Z., Jansen, S., Tillett, C., 2021, Virtual reality-assisted assessment of type B aortic dissection for preoperative planning. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

Hyde, J., Khaksar, S., Lamont, W., 2021, 3D Modelling of Hand Movement in Children with Cerebral Palsy. Final Report, 43pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.

- Abbott, L., Murray, I., Khaksar, S., Lamont, W., 2021, VR Guide Dog Training. Final Report, 67pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Andiambololonaharisoamalala, R., Lagain, A., Benedix, G., Lamont, W., 2021, Tool for visualising planetary and all-sky astronomical data. Final Report, 22pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Elsayed, H., Belton, D., Green, G., Woods, A., Adams, D., 2021, Creating 3D models of the Kyrenia shipwreck amphorae. Final Report, 21pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Dickson, C., Woods, A., Lamont, W., Wallis-Smith, D., Edwards, T., 2022, Fremantle Historical Panoramas Audio-Visual Tours. Final Report, 20pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Battersby, C., Woods, A., Li Tay, J., Lamont, W., Pearce, A., 2022, Fremantle Harbour Animated Panorama Project. Final Report, 24pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Geerlings-Batt, J., Sun, Z., Tillett, C., 2022, Enhanced visualisation of normal anatomy with augmented reality superimposed on three-dimensional printed models. Final Report, 18pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Conradie, M., Sandry, E., Peaty, G., Tillett, C., 2022, VR Communicative Robots. Final Report, 26pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Mnahy, Y., Buzzacott, P., Perera, N., Lamont, W., 2022, Helping Developing World Diving Harvesters Avoid the Bends – A Humanitarian Project. Final Report, 28pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Bak, B., Abidin, C., Tillett, C., 2023, How Platforms See Influencers. Final Report, 23pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Delpech, K., Sun, Z., Bhandari, M., Tillett, C., 2023, Clinical value of virtual reality in pre-surgical planning of malignant hepatic tumours. Final Report, 22pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- Natalotto, J., Sun, Z., Tillett, C., Jansen, S., Hodder, R., Hockley, J., 2023, Interactive 3D Virtual Reality Imaging of Abdominopelvic Sarcoma to Improve Surgical Planning. Final Report, 24pp., Curtin University. Curtin HIVE internship report.
- David O'Neill, Morgan Titmus, Wesley Lamont, Wan Hui Teh, Enoch Perimal and Flavia Di Pietro, 2024, Validating the Threat of a Virtual Reality Clinical Environment: A Mixed Methods Study, *Appl. Sci.* 2024, 14(21), 10009; <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/14/21/10009>

8 Appendices

Appendix A – HIVE Project List

Appendix B – HIVE Supported Grants (Successful and Unsuccessful)

Appendix A and B are not included in the public version of this report.

Australian Prime Minister Anthony Albanese visits Curtin University and the HIVE on 21 October 2022. (Front L-R) Professor Phil Bland, Prime Minister Anthony Albanese, Professor Chris Moran, and Zaneta Mascarenhas, Member for Swan. Photo Credit: Ezra Alcantra